

**Developing and Implementing Request and Approval Modules in the
Information Technology Assets Management System: STORIX Project**

By

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STATEMENT BY THE AUTHOR

I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and to the best of my knowledge, it contains no material previously published or written by another person, not material which to a substantial extent has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma at any educational institution, except where due acknowledgement is made in the thesis.

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ABSTRACT

DEVELOPING AND IMPLEMENTING REQUEST AND APPROVAL MODULES IN THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ASSETS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: STORIX PROJECT

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Schenker Integrated Online Request and IT Inventory Management System or so-called as STORIX put its concern as a project that develop an application that will help Schenker IT department and other departments in any Schenker branches for flattening bureaucracy in requesting IT item assets and Access. It will give detail information and support them in the decision-making process. The application will effectively provide information for IT administrator in PT. Schenker Petrolog Utama.

STORIX project will consist of several modules. The author put his concerns only in request and approval modules, and evaluation module. The request and approval modules are responsible for collecting every request in database records and distribute that records to specific person for authorization process. The evaluation module perform evaluation and calculation for a specific vendor's purchase order and store it on the database. Modules will be designed using a specific web programming language (PHP and HTML). MySQL will be used as the database engine and Apache Server will be used as the web server.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to my parent and sister for all of their love, support, and encouragements during my studies in Swiss German University.

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CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

PT Schenker Petrolog Utama is a leading forwarding company in Indonesia. It has several branches in Indonesia and tries to expand its business.

Recently the IT department in Schenker does not have an IT assets management system applied. All they have is an Excel-based contains some information regarding their IT assets. In reality, these inventory items are provided based on requests from employees. Since both of the assets and the request are still executed manually, they consume a lot of time. It is also difficult to track each asset since the system is a separate process. This condition, however, is not sufficient enough for an evolving company such as Schenker.

To solve this problem and also to improve the effectiveness of these two processes, developing a new system is required. This new system which called STORIX (Schenker Integrated Online Request and IT Inventory Management System) will contain two different integrated modules which are IT assets management system and request form system. To be accessed easily by all employees in every branch in Indonesia, this project will be developed as an online application.

1.2 The Objectives

The request and approval management module will be responsible to perform an interactive request input for end-user and give an informative view for management division to approve the request. Every data that related to this request-approval procedure will be stored into database and it will be useful for analytical report of inventory module. This Request and Approval modules have several major processes, which are collecting users' requests, define its status as a pending request and refer it to hierarchical management involved in the approval process.

1.3 Methodology

This project will be completed through the following steps:

a) Literature review

It will be conducted to support theoretical issues related with this project. The information required for this thesis can be collected from books and the internet.

b) Program design

The Integrated IT Asset Management System as a result from the STORIX project will have a web-based interface design. The user interface will be customized according to the permissions or the status level of the users that login. Several major functions will be implemented into this system by author such as request input form, and hierarchical approval process.

c) Project Implementation

Using structural approach as a programming method considering the performance and simple syntax arrangement of PHP language, the program will be implemented as a web-based application.

1.4 Design Specifications

Following are the specifications for the system:

a) Authentication module

This module would provide an eligible authorization for every user to access the system according to their permission.

b) Request and Approval Module

This module function as the main module that records every request in the database and distribute the record to specific person for authorization and the cycle ended when the request either approved or rejected by the management.

c) Vendor Evaluation Module

Consist of two parts of module; standard and periodic evaluation. This module will perform evaluation and calculation for every vendor's purchase order.

d) Administrative Module

This module handles all administrative functions related to the information exist within the system.

1.5 Thesis Organization

This thesis is organized into 5 chapters. The first chapter, Introduction, gives the big picture of the thesis. Chapter 2, Literature Review, explains the theoretical background used as a reference during the thesis development. While chapter 3 gives the detailed analysis and design of this project using various approaches, the fourth chapter delivers the system implementation by providing some screenshots. Finally, the last chapter explains the conclusion from the thesis. In addition, some work recommendations are also available.

CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Management Information Systems

Management Information Systems is a computer-based or manual system that transforms data into information useful in the support of decision making (Siegel, Joel G & Shim, Jae K 2005). Management information systems allow managers to make decisions for the successful operation of businesses. Management information systems consist of computer resources, people, and procedures used in the modern business enterprise. MIS also refers to the organization that develops and maintains most or all of the computer systems in the enterprise so that managers can make decisions. The goal of the MIS organization is to deliver information systems to the various levels of corporate managers. MIS professionals create and support the computer system throughout the company. Trained and educated to work with corporate computer systems, these professionals are responsible in some way for nearly all of the computers, from the largest mainframe to the desktop and portable PCs.

2.1.1 Background

Management information systems do not have to be computerized, but with today's large, multinational corporations, computerization is a must for a business to be successful. However, management information systems began with simple manual systems such as customer databases on index cards. As early as 1642, the French mathematician and philosopher Blaise Pascal invented the first mechanical adding machine so that figures could be added to provide information. Almost two hundred years later, Charles Babbage, a professor of mathematics at Cambridge University in England, wanted to make a machine that would compute mathematical tables. He attempted to build a computing machine during the 1880s. He failed because his ideas were beyond his technical capabilities, not because

the idea was flawed. Babbage is often called the father of the computer. With the advent of the computer, management information systems became automated.

In the late 1890s, because of the efforts of Herman Hollerith, who created a punch-card system to tabulate the data for the 1890 census, it was possible to begin to provide data-processing equipment. The punch card developed by Hollerith was later used to form a company to provide data-processing equipment. This company evolved into International Business Machines (IBM). Mainframe computers were used for management information systems from the 1940s, 50s, 60s, and up until the 1970s. In the 1970s, personal computers were first built by hobbyists. Then Apple computer developed one of the first practical personal computers. In the early 1980s, IBM developed its PC, and since then, the personal computer industry has mushroomed. Almost every management information system revolves around some kind of computer hardware and software.

Management information systems are becoming more important, and MIS personnel are more visible than in the 1960s and 1970s, when they were hidden away from the rest of the company and performed tasks behind closed doors. So remote were some MIS personnel from the operations of the business that they did not even know what products their companies made. This has changed because the need for an effective management information system is of primary concern to the business organization. Managers use MIS operations for all phases of management, including planning, organizing, directing, and controlling.

2.1.2 The MIS Job

MIS personnel must be technically qualified to work with computer hardware, software, and computer information systems. Currently, colleges and universities cannot produce enough MIS personnel for business needs, and job opportunities are great. MIS managers, once they have risen through their technical ranks of their organization to become managers, must remember that they are no longer doing the technical work. They must cross over from being technicians to become managers. Their job changes from being technicians to being systems managers who manage other people's technical work. They must see themselves as needing to solve the business problems of the user, and not just of the data-processing department (Bartholome, 2001).

MIS managers are in charge of the systems development operations for their firm. According to Rochester (1996), systems development requires four stages when developing a system for any phase of the organization:

a) **Phase I**

Is systems planning. The systems team must investigate the initial problem by determining what the problem is and developing a feasibility study for management to review.

b) **Phase II**

Identifies the requirements for the systems. It includes the systems analysis, the user requirements, necessary hardware and software, and a conception design for the system. Top management then reviews the systems analysis and design.

c) **Phase III**

Involves the development of the systems. This involves developing technical support and technical specifications, reviewing users' procedures control, designing the system, testing the system, and providing user training for the system. At this

time, management again reviews and decides on whether to implement the system.

d) **Phase IV**

Is the implementation of the system. The new system is converted from the old system, and the new system is implemented and then refined. There must then be ongoing maintenance and reevaluation of the system to see if it continues to meet the needs of the business.

2.1.3 Types of Systems

Management information systems can be used as a support to managers to provide a competitive advantage. The system must support the goals of the organization. According to Stair (1996), most organizations are structured along functional lines, and the typical systems are identified as follows:

- a) ***Accounting management information systems***: All accounting reports are shared by all levels of accounting managers.
- b) ***Financial management information systems***: The financial management information system provides financial information to all financial managers within an organization including the chief financial officer. The chief financial officer analyzes historical and current financial activity, projects future financial needs, and monitors and controls the use of funds over time using the information developed by the MIS department.
- c) ***Manufacturing management information systems***: More than any functional area, operations have been impacted by great advances in technology. As a result, manufacturing operations have changed. For instance, inventories are provided just in time so that great amounts of money are not spent for warehousing huge inventories. In some instances, raw materials are even processed on railroad cars waiting to be sent directly to the factory. Thus there is no need for warehousing.

-
- d) **Marketing management information systems:** A marketing management information system supports managerial activity in the area of product development, distribution, pricing decisions, promotional effectiveness, and sales forecasting. More than any other functional areas, marketing systems rely on external sources of data. These sources include competition and customers, for example.
 - e) **Human resources management information systems:** Human resources management information systems are concerned with activities related to workers, managers, and other individuals employed by the organization. Because the personnel function relates to all other areas in business, the human resources management information system plays a valuable role in ensuring organizational success. Activities performed by the human resources management information systems include, work-force analysis and planning, hiring, training, and job assignments.

2.2 IT Assets Management System

IT asset management (ITAM) is the set of business practices that join financial, contractual and inventory functions to support life cycle management and strategic decision making for the IT environment. Assets include all elements of software and hardware that are found in the business environment (Wikipedia, 2007).

2.2.1 Software asset management

Software Asset Management applies to the business practices specific to software management, including software license management, configuration management, standardization of images and compliance to regulatory and legal restrictions—such as copyright law, Sarbanes Oxley and software publisher contractual compliance. Legal software use in an organization is enforced by such compliance companies as Business Software Alliance, SIIA and FAST.

According to Wikipedia (2007), software is referred to as entitlements so that SAM programs confirm the right to use or entitlement to that software by the user. Automation is used to facilitate this management. Microsoft maintains a list of SAM providers to help customers manage their software.

2.2.2 Hardware asset management

Hardware asset management entails the management of the physical components of computers and computer networks, from acquisition through disposal. Common business practices include request and approval process, procurement management, life cycle management, redeployment and disposal management.

2.2.3 Role of ITAM in an organization

The IT Asset Management function is the primary point of accountability for the life-cycle management of information technology assets throughout the organization.

Included in this responsibility are development and maintenance of policies, standards, processes, systems and measurements that enable the organization to manage the IT Asset Portfolio with respect to risk, cost, control, IT Governance, compliance and business performance objectives as established by the business.

IT Asset Management integrates the physical, technological, contractual and financial aspects of information technology assets to enable a holistic and proactive approach to achieving the objectives.

2.2.4 Goals of ITAM

ITAM business practices have a common set of goals:

- a) Uncover savings through process improvement and support for strategic decision making.
- b) Gain control of the inventory.
- c) Increase accountability to insure compliance.
- d) Enhance performance of assets and the life cycle management.
- e) Risk reduction through standardization, proper documentation, loss detection.

2.2.5 Process

ITAM business practices are process-driven and matured through iterative and focused improvements. Most successful ITAM programs are invasive to the organization, involving everyone at some level, such as end users (educating on compliance), budget managers (redeployment as a choice), IT service departments (providing information on warranties), and finance (invoice reconciliation, updates for fixed asset inventories).

IT asset management generally uses automation to manage the discovery of assets, so inventory can be compared to ownership information. Full business management of IT assets requires a repository of multiple types of information about the asset, as well as integration with other systems such as supply chain, help desk, procurement and HR systems.

2.3 Business Intelligence

Business intelligence (BI) is a business management term, which refers to applications and technologies that are used to gather, provide access to, and analyze data and information about company operations. Business intelligence

systems can help companies have a more comprehensive knowledge of the factors affecting their business, such as metrics on sales, production, internal operations, and they can help companies to make better business decisions (Wikipedia, 2007).

2.3.1 Rationale for using BI

Business intelligence applications and technologies can enable organizations to make more informed business decisions, and they may give a company a competitive advantage. For example, a company could use business intelligence applications or technologies to extrapolate information from indicators in the external environment and forecast the future trends in their sector. Business intelligence is used to improve the timeliness and quality of information and enable managers to better understand the position of their firm in comparison to its competitors.

BI systems can help companies develop consistent and "data-based" business decisions--producing better results than basing decisions on "guesswork." In addition, business intelligence applications can enhance communication among departments, coordinate activities, and enable companies to respond more quickly to changes (e.g., in financial conditions, customer preferences, supply chain operations, etc.). When a BI system is well-designed and properly integrated into a company's processes and decision-making process, it may be able to improve a company's performance. Having access to timely and accurate information is an important resource for a company, which can expedite decision-making and improve customers' experience.

2.3.2 Key Intelligence Topics

Business intelligence often uses Key performance indicators (KPIs) to assess the present state of business and to prescribe a course of action. Prior to the widespread adoption of computer and web applications,

when information had to be manually inputted and calculated, performance data was often not available for weeks or months. Recently, banks have tried to make data available at shorter intervals and have reduced delays. The KPI methodology was further expanded with the Chief Performance Officer methodology which incorporated KPIs and root cause analysis into a single methodology.

Businesses that face higher operational/credit risk loading, such as credit card companies and "wealth management" services often make KPI-related data available weekly. In some cases, companies may even offer a daily analysis of data. This fast pace requires analysts to use IT systems to process this large volume of data.

2.3.3 Designing and implementing a BI program

When implementing a BI programme one might like to pose a number of questions and take a number of resultant decisions, such as:

- a) **Goal Alignment queries:** The first step determines the short and medium-term purposes of the programme. What strategic goal(s) of the organization will the programme address? What organizational mission/vision does it relate to?
- b) **Baseline queries:** Current information-gathering competency needs assessing. Does the organization have the capability of monitoring important sources of information? What data does the organization collect and how does it store that data?
- c) **Cost and risk queries:** The financial consequences of a new BI initiative should be estimated. This risk assessment should be converted into a financial metric and included in the planning.
- d) **Customer and Stakeholder queries:** Determine who will benefit from the initiative and who will pay.
- e) **Metrics-related queries:** These information requirements must be operationalized into clearly defined metrics. One must decide what metrics to use for each piece of information being gathered.

- f) **Measurement Methodology-related queries:** One should establish a methodology or a procedure to determine the best (or acceptable) way of measuring the required metrics.
- g) **Results-related queries:** Someone should monitor the BI programme to ensure that objectives are being met. Adjustments in the programme may be necessary. The programme should be tested for accuracy, reliability, and validity.

2.4 Supply-Chain Management

Supply chain management (SCM) is the process of planning, implementing, and controlling the operations of the supply chain with the purpose to satisfy customer requirements as efficiently as possible. Supply chain management spans all movement and storage of raw materials, work-in-process inventory, and finished goods from point-of-origin to point-of-consumption. The term supply chain management was coined by consultant Keith Oliver, of strategy consulting firm Booz Allen Hamilton in 1982 (Wikipedia, 2007).

Supply chain event management (abbreviated as SCEM) is a consideration of all possible occurring events and factors that can cause a disruption in a supply chain. With SCEM possible scenarios can be created and solutions can be planned. Some experts distinguish supply chain management and logistics, while others consider the terms to be interchangeable.

Supply chain management is also a category of software products.

2.4.1 Problems

Supply chain management must address the following problems:

- a) **Distribution Network Configuration:** Number and location of suppliers, production facilities, distribution centers, warehouses and customers.
- b) **Distribution Strategy:** Centralized versus decentralized, direct shipment, Cross docking, pull or push strategies, third party logistics.

- c) **Information:** Integrate systems and processes through the supply chain to share valuable information, including demand signals, forecasts, inventory and transportation etc.
- d) **Inventory Management:** Quantity and location of inventory including raw materials, work-in-process and finished goods.

Supply chain execution is managing and coordinating the movement of materials information and funds across the supply chain. The flow is bi-directional.

2.4.2 Activities/functions

Supply chain management is a cross-functional approach to managing the movement of raw materials into an organization and the movement of finished goods out of the organization toward the end-consumer. As corporations strive to focus on core competencies and become more flexible, they have reduced their ownership of raw materials sources and distribution channels. These functions are increasingly being outsourced to other corporations that can perform the activities better or more cost effectively. The effect has been to increase the number of companies involved in satisfying consumer demand, while reducing management control of daily logistics operations. Less control and more supply chain partners led to the creation of supply chain management concepts. The purpose of supply chain management is to improve trust and collaboration among supply chain partners, thus improving inventory visibility and improving inventory velocity.

Several models have been proposed for understanding the activities required to manage material movements across organizational and functional boundaries. SCOR is a supply chain management model promoted by the Supply-Chain Management Council. Another model is the SCM Model proposed by the Global Supply Chain Forum (GSCF). Supply chain activities can be grouped into strategic, tactical, and operational levels of activities.

a) Strategic

1. Strategic network optimization, including the number, location, and size of warehouses, distribution centers and facilities.
2. Strategic partnership with suppliers, distributors, and customers, creating communication channels for critical information and operational improvements such as cross docking, direct shipping, and third-party logistics.
3. Product design coordination, so that new and existing products can be optimally integrated into the supply chain, load management.
4. Information Technology infrastructure, to support supply chain operations.
5. Where to make and what to make or buy decisions.
6. Align overall organizational strategy with supply strategy.

b) Tactical

1. Sourcing contracts and other purchasing decisions.
2. Production decisions, including contracting, locations, scheduling, and planning process definition.
3. Inventory decisions, including quantity, location, and quality of inventory.
4. Transportation strategy, including frequency, routes, and contracting.
5. Benchmarking of all operations against competitors and implementation of best practices throughout the enterprise.
6. Milestone payments.

c) Operational

1. Daily production and distribution planning, including all nodes in the supply chain.
2. Production scheduling for each manufacturing facility in the supply chain (minute by minute).

-
3. Demand planning and forecasting, coordinating the demand forecast of all customers and sharing the forecast with all suppliers.
 4. Sourcing planning, including current inventory and forecast demand, in collaboration with all suppliers.
 5. Inbound operations, including transportation from suppliers and receiving inventory.
 6. Production operations, including the consumption of materials and flow of finished goods.
 7. Outbound operations, including all fulfillment activities and transportation to customers.
 8. Order promising, accounting for all constraints in the supply chain, including all suppliers, manufacturing facilities, distribution centers, and other customers.

2.4.3 SCM components integration

The SCM management components are the third element of the four-square circulation framework. The level of integration and management of a business process link is a function of the number and level, ranging from low to high, of components added to the link (Ellram and Cooper, 1990; Houlihan, 1985). Consequently, adding more management components or increasing the level of each component can increase the level of integration of the business process link. The literature on business process reengineering, buyer-supplier relationships, and SCM suggests various possible components that must receive managerial attention when managing supply relationships.

Baziotopoulos (2004) suggests the following supply chain components:

-
- a) For **customer service management**: Includes the primary level component of customer relationship management, and secondary level components such as benchmarking and order fulfillment.
 - b) For **product development and commercialization**: Includes the primary level component of Product Data Management (PDM), and secondary level components such as market share, customer satisfaction, profit margins, and returns to stakeholders.
 - c) For **physical distribution, Manufacturing support and Procurement**: Includes the primary level component of enterprise resource planning (ERP), with secondary level components such as warehouse management, material management, manufacturing planning, personnel management, and postponement (order management).
 - d) For **performance measurement**: This includes the primary level component of logistics performance measurement, which is correlated with the information flow facility structure within the organization. Secondary level components may include four types of measurement such as: variation, direction, decision and policy measurements. More specifically, in accordance with these secondary level components total cost analysis (TCA), customer profitability analysis (CPA), and Asset management could be concerned as well. In general, information flow facility structure is regarded by two important requirements, which are a) planning and Coordination flows, and b)operational requirements.
 - e) For **outsourcing**: This includes the primary level component of management methods and the company's cutting-edge strategy and its vital strategic objectives that the company will identify and adopt for particular strategic initiatives in key the areas of technology information, operations, manufacturing capabilities, and logistics (secondary level components).

CHAPTER 3 – ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

STORIX will be a system where the Schenker IT administrators are able to supervise every records of request and maintain their IT assets and process the information into various reports that support the decision making process. This chapter discusses the result of analysis and interview with those who are involved with IT asset management process.

3.1 Analysis

On this chapter part, problems that exist in the Schenker daily activities that related with requesting-approving procedures and evaluating vendors will be discussed. Later on, it will continue with determining appropriate solutions and requirements for the new system.

3.1.1 Problem Analysis

For a long period of time, Schenker still implements paper-based request system. This kind of method is unefficient, especially when another branch of Schenker Indonesia need an acknowledgement and approval form the Schenker Indonesia HQ.

Problems run not only there, evaluating vendor that can give competitive services would also needed, since generally administrators need to perform evaluation and calculation manually based on criterias that already set by Schenker itself.

Diagram below shows the previous business processes of Request-Approval, Standard Vendor Evaluation, and Periodic Vendor Evaluation.

Figure 3.1 Request-Approval Previous Business Process

Figure 3.2 Standard Vendor Evaluation Previous Business Process

Figure 3.3 Periodic Vendor Evaluation Previous Business Process

Below is the new business process for above images using STORIX.

Figure 3.4 Request-Approval New Business Process

Figure 3.5 Standard Vendor Evaluation New Business Process

Figure 3.6 Periodic Vendor Evaluation New Business Process

Based on interviews, the condition above has aroused some problems listed below:

a) Time Consuming

Since both of the request and evaluation system are still executed manually and the information needed is located in different files and format, it needs several days to accomplish the whole request process until its data being processed into various reports.

b) Synchronization and Tracking Difficulties

It is difficult to synchronize the information possessed by one branch to another. Besides, since the information file is scattered, tracking the assets and all of the records from the beginning is difficult to perform.

c) Inaccuracy and uneffectiveness

Each time there are evaluations performed using paper-based model; calculating score and remarks, and generating periodic report for specific vendor would be an obligation to do. If there are any inappropriate results, such as miscalculation and differences on generating periodic evaluation vendor, it would make difficulties on the decision-making process.

3.1.2 Requirements Analysis

Based on problem analysis and interview, the new system expectations are described in the following:

a) Integrated System

It is needed to develop a system that combines request process and assets management process. This system should contain two different integrated modules which are IT assets management system and request form system.

b) Automated System

System is computerized and those two modules should access the same database, so that form preparations, calculations and data entry process can be eliminated. Automated system also enables users to access this application online from all Schenker branch in Indonesia, and the information will be distributed evenly.

c) Reduce time waste

Since it was located in internal system that connect every branches, difficulties for distributing data to specific person in charge for authorizing request and evaluating report will be eliminated.

d) Flexible and modular

Since the system is an integrated system, it should have possibilities for expanding new features without interrupting basic functions that already existed.

3.2 Decision Analysis

Several alternatives are available to build the system. Below will be described the considerations of the options.

3.2.1 Server-Side Scripting

Security will be one of many considerations that had been thought by the author, to hide the process and data flow from the client. server-side scripting is powerful to build an interactive application, therefore

it is determined that new system will use server side scripting.

Resources load that burden the server will be higher than client-side scripting where the load also distributed to the client, but necessity for security and small differences in process loading would be acceptable.

3.2.2 Web-Based System

Web-based system is different from other categories of computer software. It can be continuously evolving and the aesthetic as well as functional content delivery are additional differentiating factors. To be able accessed from any different OS platform is another advantage of a web-based application.

3.3 Design

The goal of designing is to produce a model or representation that exhibits firmness, commodity, and delight. From a generic viewpoint, design results in a model that guides the construction of web-application. The design model, regardless of its form, should contain enough information to reflect how stakeholder requirements are to be translated into context and executable code.

3.3.1 Process Modeling

Process modeling is a process-centered technique popularized by the structured analysis and design methodology that used models of business process requirements to derive effective software designs for a system. Structured analysis introduced a modeling tool called the data flow diagram to illustrate the flow of data through a series of business processes. Structured design converted data flow diagrams into a process model called structure charts to illustrate a top-down software structure that fulfills the business requirements (Whitten & Bentley,2004)

3.3.1.1 Use Case Diagram

In the Unified Modeling Language, a use case diagram is a subclass of behavioral diagrams. The UML defines a graphical notation for representing the relationships between a set of use cases called the Use case model. However, UML does not define standards for the written description of an individual use case, and this misleads some people to believe that the use case model is sufficient by itself to describe a use case. However, the graphical notation is purely an overview - the Use case diagram should not be confused with the use cases themselves. Each use case must be defined (with text) in finer detail than its simple presence on a use case diagram (Wikipedia, 2007).

Figure 3.7 Use Case Diagram

3.3.1.2 Functional Decomposition Diagram

The functional decomposition diagram (FDD) is a planning tool for identifying business functions and the processes that comprise them. The functional decomposition diagram (FDD) is a business planning tool that depicts the hierarchy of business functions, processes, and subprocesses within an organization. The functional decomposition diagram itself does not depict process flows, but rather the hierarchical organization of functions and the processes that they include (SIMS, 2007).

Diagram below describe the functional decomposition diagram of STORIX. This system is mainly consists of three functions; Master File Management, Transactions and Reporting. Each of these functions has several sub-functions. All subfunctions involved within this thesis scope is indicated by the boxes with blue shadow.

Figure 3.8 Functional Decomposition Diagram

3.3.1.2 Context Diagram

A System Context Diagram (SCD) is the highest level view of a system, showing a system as a whole and its inputs and outputs from/to external actors. SCDs are a type of Data Flow Diagram, and they should always be produced as DFDs. Context Diagrams show the interactions between a system and other actors with which the system is designed to face. SCD is very helpful in understanding the context in which the system will be part of software engineering (Wikipedia, 2007).

Request and Approval Modules can be accessed from any user level, but each user level only hold specific function. Such as; coordinator and manager are able to create a request but only manager can authorize the request, administrator can create RFA from authorized request, approver hold decision whether a RFA should be approved or not. An user should login and supply a correct username and password before accessing other services provided. Diagram below shows the context diagram of these modules.

Figure 3.9 Context Diagram

3.3.1.2 DFD

A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the "flow" of data through an information system. A data flow diagram can also be used for the visualization of data processing (structured design). It is common practice for a designer to draw a context-level DFD first which shows the interaction between the system and outside entities. This context-level DFD is then "exploded" to show more detail of the system being modeled (Wikipedia,2007).

In this section, Request and Approval Modules will be described in 5 different data flow diagrams that consist of external entities, processes, data stores and data flow representation involved in the module. The first diagram, DFD Level 1, explains data flow of the whole module. The process of shown in the first diagram is expandable into more detail explanation. The next 4 diagrams will drill down more data flow information exist in each process involved in the first diagram.

DFD Level 1

This diagram shows 3 main functions; authentication, request-approval and administrative management. As explained by the diagram below, authentication process (process 1) is required before users be able to perform any service from request-approval modules (process 2).

Figure 3.10 DFD Level 1

DFD Process 1 level 2

Validation process begins when users insert their username and password, the system will verify whether it matches one of the records on user table or not. If it matches one record, any related data to user from other database table will be stored to session as a key identifier of that user. If the authentication was failed than it will displayed the login page again until user successfully login to the system.

Figure 3.11 DFD Process 1 Level 2

DFD Process 2 level 2

This DFD describe whole picture of request-approval process in general view. User/coordinator create a request, default status for created request is pending. A pending request directed to the manager in same branch and same department. Manager will authorized the pending request. Administrator will create a RFA from authorized request that has accepted request item, by default the RFA status is pending and directed to approver. Approver will open the RFA and decide whether it will be approved or rejected. Each approval or authorization process will be acknowledge to the request or RFA creator by the status on the item.

Figure 3.12 DFD Process 2 Level 2

Figure 3.13 DFD Process 2 level 3

User create request based on the request type and item listed in the database, the request will be stored as pending in request table and the requested details will be stored also as pending in request_details table.

Manager will retrieve request that has pending status on it, after that manager will do authorization process. The system will update the request data stored in database based on manager authorization; authorized or not authorized/rejected.

Figure 3.14 DFD Process 3 Level 2

Administrator will be displayed requested item list that already accepted to be created as RFA. When RFA created, information that related to administrator will stored also as an identifier for the respective RFA.

Stored RFA record and it details have pending status on it, and requested item that belong to the request form will have “RFA-PENDING” status on it.

Approver will have pending RFA on their approver list, whether a RFA approved or rejected, their related status on request form will updated also according to approver decision.

3.3.2 Data Modeling

Data modeling is a data-centered technique used to model business data requirements and design database systems that fulfill those requirements (Whitten,2004).

According to ANSI (1975) a data model instance may be one of three kinds:

- a) a conceptual schema (data model) describes the semantics of an organization. This consists of entity classes (representing things of significance to the organization) and relationships (assertions about associations between pairs of entity classes).
- b) a logical schema (data model) describes the semantics, as represented by a particular data manipulation technology. This consists of descriptions of tables and columns, object oriented classes, and XML tags, among other things.
- c) a physical schema (data model) describes the physical means by which data are stored. This is concerned with partitions, CPUs, table spaces, and the like.

Several tables are needed to build the Request-Approval Modules and Vendor evaluation Modules. Entity Relational Diagram is used to represent the communication between tables.

3.3.2.1 Entity Relationship Diagram

Entity Relationship Modelling is The structure of relation between store data in database, together with other constraints, can be designed using a variety of techniques. The end-product of the ERM process is an entity-relationship diagram or ERD. Data modeling requires a graphical notation for representing such data models. An ERD is a type of conceptual data model or semantic data model.

Figure 3.15 Entity Relationship Diagram

3.3.2.2 Fully Attributes Data Model

In this section listed figures will show specification of the tables used in Request-Approval Modules and Vendor evaluation Module.

Figure 3.16 Fully Attributes Data Model for Authentication Module

Figure 3.17 Fully Attributes Data Model for Request Module

Figure 3.18 Fully Attributes Data Model for Administrative Module

Figure 3.19 Fully Attributes Data Model for Vendor Management Module

3.3.3 Physical Design

Physical design translates business user requirements into a system model that depicts a technical implementation of the users' business requirements (Whitten,2004).

Diagram below shows the physical design of the system. In the client side, several functions that can be done to distributed web process load to the client performed. These functions developed using JavaScript. All main functions that run in the server are developed using PHP. To store information, MySQL engine is installed in the system.

Figure 3.20 Physical Design

3.3.4 Architectural Design

Architectural design represents the structure of data and program components that are required to build a computer-based system. It considers the architectural style that the system will take, the structure and properties of components that constitute the system, and the interrelationships that occur among all architectural components of a system (Pressmann, 2005).

Architectural design begins with data design and then proceeds to the derivation of one or more representations of the architectural structure of the system. STORIX project consists of several modules. For this thesis purpose, only request approval module and vendor evaluation will be explained.

Request approval module has four main elements. The first one, request, enables the user to create, view and perform another administrative options. RFA element also enables the IT administrator

to perform this same functions. Meanwhile, authorization and approval elements only enable the users to perform the respective process and viewing the results.

Vendor evaluation module is separated into two elements, standard and periodic evaluation. IT admin is able to create and manage these evaluation.

Figure 3.21 Architectural Design

3.3.5 Interface Design

User interface design creates an effective communication medium between a human and a computer. Following a set of interface design principles, design identifies interface object and actions and then

creates a screen layout that forms the basis for a user interface prototype (Pressman,2005).

User interface design begins with the identification of user, task, and environmental requirements. Once user tasks have been identified, user scenarios are created and analyzed to define a set of interface objects and actions. These form the basis for the creation of screen layouts that depicts graphical design and placement of icons, definition of descriptive screen text, specification and titling for windows, and specification of major and minor menu items.

Diagram below describe the hierarchical major menu on the system. For this thesis scope, author will have 12 major menu to be describe.

Figure 3.22 Major Menu Interface

Diagram below shows sub-menus under inventory and access menu.

Figure 3.23 Request submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under Authorize menu.

Figure 3.24 Authorize submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under RFA menu.

Figure 3.25 RFA submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus approval menu.

Figure 3.26 Approval submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under requested access menu.

Figure 3.27 Requested access sub menu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under file menu.

Figure 3.28 File submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under vendor evaluation menu.

Figure 3.29 Vendor evaluation submenu

Diagram below shows sub-menus under administrative menu.

Figure 3.30 Administrative submenu

3.4 Development Tools

Web-based application is an application from a web server which is delivered over a network such as World Wide Web or an intranet. As a web-based application, STORIX would require a development environment that suit its conditions to fulfill business requirements.

3.4.1 OpenSuSE 10.2

Another different flavor from Linux distribution or as it calls “distro”. As the base operating system platform used by author for developing and implementing the STORIX system, openSUSE 10.2 from Novell provides everything today's Linux user needs for home computing and computing-on-the-go. Created by the openSUSE.org project, the product includes a stabilized, secure and reliable Linux operating system plus a complete set of desktop applications. It also offers the latest open source applications for developing applications, setting up a home network, running a Web server, and more (novell.com, 2007).

3.4.2 Apache HTTP Server

Any web-based application cannot run without a web server, one of the popular web servers used by author is Apache HTTP server. Apache HTTP Server is a web server for Unix-like systems, Microsoft Windows, Novell NetWare, Mac OS X and other operating systems.

Apache is primarily used to serve both static content and dynamic Web pages on the World Wide Web. Many web applications are designed expecting the environment and features that Apache provides.

3.4.3 MySQL

MySQL is popular for web applications and acts as the database component of the LAMP, MAMP, and WAMP platforms (Linux/Mac/Windows-Apache-MySQL-PHP/Perl/Python), and for open-source bug tracking tools like Bugzilla. Its popularity as a web

application is closely tied to the popularity of PHP, which is often combined with MySQL and nicknamed the ‘Dynamic Duo’ (Wikipedia, 2007).

3.4.4 PHP

PHP is a reflective programming language originally designed for producing dynamic web pages. PHP is used mainly in server-side scripting, but can be used from a command line interface or in standalone graphical applications (Wikipedia,2007).

Used as a base programming language for developing STORIX system, PHP was chosen by author because of several considerations; Fast to implement, reliability as server-side scripting, support, and time efficiency.

PHP generally runs on a web server, taking PHP code as its input and creating Web pages as output, however it can also be used for command-line scripting and client-side GUI applications. PHP can be deployed on most web servers and on almost every OS platform free of charge. Originally designed to create dynamic web pages, PHP's principal focus is server-side scripting.

3.4.5 Javascript

JavaScript is a scripting language developed by Netscape to enable Web authors to design interactive sites. Although it shares many of the features and structures of the full Java language, it was developed independently. Javascript can interact with HTML source code, enabling Web authors to spice up their sites with dynamic content (www.public.asu.edu, 2001).

Many people often see JavaScript referred to as a “scripting language,” with the implication that is somehow easier to script than to program.

CHAPTER 4 – IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Software Testing

The testing of the system is conducted by using Mozilla Firefox with Javascript enabled and monitor resolution 1280x768. Modules that tested are authentication module, request module, approval module, evaluation module, and administrative module. Details of the testing are as followed.

4.1.1 Authentication

To login, the user should fill in username, password and click [LOGIN]. The [RESET] button clears the fields.

USERNAME : aryo
PASSWORD : *****
LOGIN RESET

Best viewed using Mozilla Firefox or Opera browser. Javascript must be enabled.
Copyright © 2007 S.T.O.R.I.X. Project

Figure 4.1 Login Page

If the login were successful then the user will be redirected to the Home page. Every user level has a different view of information shown up on their Home page.

Coordinator

Figure 4.2 Coordinator Home Page

For coordinator, informations displayed on the screen are statistics per-user and message of the day.

Manager

Figure 4.3 Manager Home Page

Not so different from coordinator, information for manager only has additional status for pending request to be authorized by the manager.

Administrator

Figure 4.4 Administrator Home Page

Administrator only get status of request that already authorized by managers and message of the day.

Approver

Figure 4.5 Approver Home Page

Approver only need to know about pending RFA that comes from Administrator and also message of the day.

4.1.2 My Account

This function use to change default password for every user. What user need to do is give their old password as authentication and insert their new password twice as a confirmation. After that click [UPDATE PASSWORD], if there are any failure occurs there will be an error message shown up depends on the invalid user input.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled "MY SETTINGS". Underneath, there is a section labeled "CHANGE PASSWORD". It contains three input fields: "OLD PASSWORD", "NEW PASSWORD", and "RE-TYPE NEW PASSWORD". Below the "OLD PASSWORD" field, there is a note: "(bsd), if you never change your password." At the bottom of the form, there is a button labeled "UPDATE PASSWORD".

Figure 4.6 My Account

4.1.3 Menu for Coordinator

Coordinator is the lowest level in user permission. Users that have this level permission can only create request, other functions not available for this kind of user.

4.1.3.1 Request

Request menu is a feature that enables user to create new request, list every request that user created, and print the request as a copy of proof for IT administrator to audit.

Request Box

Request Box lists IT requests that user have been created. This list is sorted by its request date and status. In this page user can view request detail by clicking [PRINT] icon.

REQUEST BOX

Page 1 of 2 Next | Last

NO.	ID	FILE NO.	REQUESTER	REQ. TYPE	REQ. DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#41	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	User Biasa	Equipment/peripherals Request	28 June 2007 16:01:51	AUTHORIZED	
2.	#40	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	User Biasa	Modify Account	28 June 2007 16:01:41	REJECTED	
3.	#20	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	User Biasa	Equipment/peripherals Request	26 June 2007 16:47:33	REJECTED	
4.	#14	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	User Biasa	New Account	20 June 2007 11:56:30	AUTHORIZED	
5.	#13	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	User Biasa	Equipment/peripherals Request	19 June 2007 15:49:12	REJECTED	

Page 1 of 2 Next | Last

Figure 4.7 Request Box Page

There are three possible status for each of user's request;

a) PENDING

This request requires authorization from user's manager.

b) AUTHORIZED

User's manager has authorized all or several items on user request.

c) REJECTED

User's manager has rejected all items on user request.

These records are able to be deleted as long as they have "PENDING" status and only the requester can delete their request.

ITS Request Form

There are two option for ITS Request Form: Account and Peripheral

REQUEST FORM

REQUEST TYPE

ACCOUNT

PERIPHERAL

NEXT >>

Figure 4.8 Request Form Type

Account request form

ACCOUNT REQUEST FORM

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

TYPE

NEW USER ACCOUNT MODIFY USER ACCOUNT DELETE USER ACCOUNT

ACCOUNT INFORMATION DATE: 2007-07-02

EMPLOYEE'S NAME

DEPARTMENT : Intelligent STATUS:

TITLE: Permanent Part-time/Contract

BRANCH : Jakarta Corporate Office Probation Intern/Temporary

ACCESS REQUESTED

Network

Email

Intranet

Internet

ProCars

SAPSEM

CITRIX

Sales Link

TRAX

ACS

DETAILS/OTHERS

REQUESTER'S NAME AUTHORIZATION

User Biasa

DATE/TGL: 02.07.07 DATE/TGL:

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

Figure 4.9 Account Request Form

a) **TYPE**

Define the type of Account Request. There are 3 options available; New user account, Modify user account and Delete user account.

b) **ACCOUNT INFORMATION**

Specify the information needs for process the respective account that being requested. The default date is today's date but user can change it by clicking the [CALENDAR] icon and choose the desired date.

c) **ACCESS REQUESTED**

Define the access type that can be selected.

Peripheral request form

EQUIPMENT/PERIPHERAL REQUEST FORM

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

DATE: 2007-07-02

PERIPHERALS/EQUIPMENT REQUESTED

- Computer
- Keyboard
- Mouse
- Monitor
- Printer
- Modem
- Scanner
- Optical Drive
- Print Cartridge

DETAILS/OTHERS

REQUESTER'S NAME AUTHORIZATION

User Biasa

DATE/TGL: 02.07.07 DATE/TGL:

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

Figure 4.10 Peripheral Request Form

a) **DATE**

The default date is today's date but user can change it by clicking the [CALENDAR] icon and choose the desired date.

b) **ACCESS REQUESTED**

Define the peripheral type that can be requested.

After a request is submitted, the record will appear on Request Box with 'PENDING' status.

4.1.3.2 Agreement

Agreement page is used to generate user acceptance and agreement. By clicking [I AGREE] in this page, users signify that they have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy.

AGREEMENT BOX

**IT PC Guidelines Policy Reference-No: 1.0.0 -
 User Acceptance and Agreement Form
 Referensi Kebijakan Pedoman PC IT - No: 1.0.0
 Formulir Penerimaan dan Persetujuan Pengguna**

EMPLOYEE NAME/*Nama Pegawai*:
User Biasa

DEPARTMENT/*Departemen*: **Intelligent** BRANCH/*Cabang*: **Jakarta Corporate Office**

**By signing this document, I signify that I have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy.
 If I fail to abide and adhere to the before mentioned guidelines, either willfully or otherwise, I will submit and accept the penalties and consequences of such actions.**

Dengan menandatangani dokumen ini, saya menyatakan bahwa saya telah membaca, mengerti dan menyetujui untuk mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk PT Schenker Petrolog Utama sesuai dengan yang tertuang di dalam kebijakan Pedoman PC Informasi Teknologi. Apabila saya gagal mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk yang disebut sebelumnya, baik secara sengaja ataupun tidak sengaja, saya sanggup dan bersedia menerima sanksi atau akibat dari tindakan tersebut.

YES, I AGREE	I ACKNOWLEDGED
User Biasa	Manager
Date/Tgl.: 19 June 2007	Date/Tgl.: 21 June 2007

— ITS USE ONLY —

FILE NO : XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607 **NOTES:**

CHECKED : -

VALIDATED : -

DATE : 19 June 2007

Figure 4.11 Agreement Form

4.1.4 Menu for Manager

User level manager has same capabilities like coordinator level but it has additional permission to authorized or denied request.

4.1.4.1 Request

Request menu is a feature that enables user to create new request, list every request that user created, and print the request as a copy of proof for IT administrator to audit.

Request Box

Request Box lists IT requests that user have been created. This list is sorted by its request date and status. In this page user can view request detail by clicking [PRINT] icon.

NO.	ID	FILE NO.	REQUESTER	REQ. TYPE	REQ. DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#42	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0707	Manager	New Account	02 July 2007 13:01:46	PENDING	
2.	#30	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Manager	Equipment/peripherals Request	28 June 2007 11:01:01	PENDING	
3.	#19	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Manager	Equipment/peripherals Request	21 June 2007 12:07:35	AUTHORIZED	
4.	#18	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Manager	Equipment/peripherals Request	20 June 2007 14:44:41	AUTHORIZED	
5.	#17	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Manager	Equipment/peripherals Request	20 June 2007 14:44:35	AUTHORIZED	

Figure 4.12 Request Box

There are three possible status for each of user's request;

a) **PENDING**

This request requires authorization from user.

b) **AUTHORIZED**

User has authorized all or several items on the request.

c) **NOT AUTHORIZED**

User has rejected all items on the request.

These records are able to be deleted as long as they have “PENDING” status and only the requester can delete their request.

ITS Request Form

There are two options for ITS Request Form: Account and Peripheral

The screenshot shows a web form titled "REQUEST FORM". Inside the form, there is a section labeled "REQUEST TYPE" containing two radio button options: "ACCOUNT" and "PERIPHERAL". Below the options is a button labeled "NEXT >>".

Figure 4.13 Request Form Type

Account request form

The screenshot shows a web-based form titled "ACCOUNT REQUEST FORM". At the top, there are two buttons: "SUBMIT REQUEST" and "RESET REQUEST". Below this is a "TYPE" section with three radio button options: "NEW USER ACCOUNT", "MODIFY USER ACCOUNT", and "DELETE USER ACCOUNT". The "ACCOUNT INFORMATION" section includes a "DATE" field set to "2007-07-02" with a calendar icon, and several text input fields for "EMPLOYEE'S NAME", "DEPARTMENT : Intelligent", "TITLE:", and "BRANCH : Jakarta Corporate Office". There are also radio button options for "STATUS:" (Permanent, Part-time/Contract) and "Intern/Temporary". The "ACCESS REQUESTED" section contains a list of checkboxes for various services: Network, Email, Intranet, Internet, ProCars, SAPSEM, CITRIX, Sales Link, TRAX, and ACS. Below this is a "DETAILS/OTHERS" section with a large empty text area. At the bottom, there are fields for "REQUESTER'S NAME" (filled with "User Biasa") and "AUTHORIZATION", along with "DATE/TGL:" fields (filled with "02.07.07"). The form concludes with another set of "SUBMIT REQUEST" and "RESET REQUEST" buttons.

Figure 4.14 Account Request Form

a) **TYPE**

Define the type of Account Request. There are 3 options available; New user account, Modify user account and Delete user account.

b) **ACCOUNT INFORMATION**

Specify the information needs for process the respective account that being requested. The default date is today's date but user can change it by clicking the [CALENDAR] icon and choose the desired date.

c) **ACCESS REQUESTED**

Define the access type that can be selected.

Peripheral request form

EQUIPMENT / PERIPHERAL REQUEST FORM

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

DATE: 2007-07-02 [CALENDAR]

PERIPHERALS/EQUIPMENT REQUESTED

- Computer
- Keyboard
- Mouse
- Monitor
- Printer
- Modem
- Scanner
- Optical Drive
- Print Cartridge

DETAILS/OTHERS

REQUESTER'S NAME AUTHORIZATION

User Biasa

DATE/TGL: **02.07.07** DATE/TGL:

SUBMIT REQUEST RESET REQUEST

Figure 4.15 Peripheral Request Form

a) **DATE**

The default date is today's date but user can change it by clicking the [CALENDAR] icon and choose the desired date.

b) **ACCESS REQUESTED**

Define the peripheral type that can be requested.

After a request is submitted, the record will appear on Request Box with 'PENDING' status.

4.1.4.2 Authorize

Authorize menu is used to handle IT request authorization tasks by managerial level.

Authorization Box

Every request needs an authorization from managerial level. Each request record from coordinator is being showed in Authorization Box.

AUTHORIZATION BOX									
Page 1 of 5									Next Last
NO.	ID	FILE NO.	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	REQUESTER	REQ. TYPE	REQ. DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#42	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0707	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	Manager	New Account	02 July 2007 13:01:46	PENDING	
2.	#41	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	User Biasa	Equipment/peripherals Request	28 June 2007 16:01:51	AUTHORIZED	
3.	#40	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	User Biasa	Modify Account	28 June 2007 16:01:41	REJECTED	
4.	#30	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	Manager	Equipment/peripherals Request	28 June 2007 11:01:01	PENDING	
5.	#20	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	User Biasa	Equipment/peripherals Request	26 June 2007 16:47:33	REJECTED	
Page 1 of 5									Next Last

Figure 4.16 Authorization Box

Each request has its own status as described below;

a) **PENDING**

This request requires user's authorization. To perform this task, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

b) **AUTHORIZED**

User have authorized all or several items requested in the respective request record. To view the request detail, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

c) **REJECTED**

User have rejected all items requested in the respective request record. To view the request detail, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

To print the request detail please click [PRINT] icon.

After user clicked [VIEW] icon for a specific request record, the Authorization Form Details page will appear. In this page user will be able to authorize each request items on the request list box.

AUTHORIZATION FORM DETAILS

[Back to the Authorization Page]

AUTHORIZED AUTHORIZED ALL REJECT ALL

ID : #42

TYPE
NEW ACCOUNT

ACCOUNT INFORMATION DATE: 02 July 2007

NAME:
Sss
DEPARTMENT: Intelligent **STATUS:** -
TITLE:
Ssss
BRANCH:
Jakarta Corporate Office

REQ. LIST

- Network -> ACCEPTED
- Email -> ACCEPTED

DETAILS/OTHERS
-

REQUESTER'S NAME: Manager **AUTHORIZATION:**
DATE/TGL: 02 July 2007 **DATE/TGL:** -

AUTHORIZED AUTHORIZED ALL REJECT ALL

ITS USE ONLY

FILE NO : XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0707 **NOTES:**
CHECKED :
VALIDATED :
DATE : 02 July 2007

[Back to the Authorization Page]

Figure 4.17 Authorization Form Details

There are two different options available; Approve and Reject. After user finish authorizing all items in the request list box, [AUTHORIZE] button will submit user's changes and bring user back to Authorization page.

There are two additional buttons both in upper and lower side of authorization form details. The first button, [AUTHORIZE ALL], will set all request items into 'ACCEPTED' state. The second button, [REJECT ALL] will set all items into 'REJECTED' state. These buttons will bring user back to Authorization page immediately. It is not necessary for user to authorize the request items one by one.

4.1.4.3 Agreement

In agreement box, manager can see every status of coordinator from the same branch and department and acknowledge their agreement. Just select the checkbox of the coordinator that manager wants and click the [ACKNOWLEDGE] button.

AGREEMENT BOX

Yes, I agree with the IT policies (For Manager Only)

By signing this document, I signify that I have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy. If I fail to abide and adhere to the before mentioned guidelines, either willfully or otherwise, I will submit and accept the penalties and consequences of such actions.

Dengan menandatangani dokumen ini, saya menyatakan bahwa saya telah membaca, mengerti dan menyetujui untuk mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk PT Schenker Petrolog Utama sesuai dengan yang tertuang di dalam kebijakan Pedoman PC Informasi Teknologi. Apabila saya gagal mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk yang disebut sebelumnya, baik secara sengaja ataupun tidak sengaja, saya sanggup dan bersedia menerima sanksi atau akibat dari tindakan tersebut.

ACKNOWLEDGE										
	NO.	FILE NO.	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	NAME	AGREE	MANAGER	ACKNOWLEDGE	DATE	ACK. DATE
<input type="checkbox"/>	1.	XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	User Biasa	YES	Manager	YES	19 June 2007	21 June 2007

Figure 4.18 Manager Agreement Box

4.1.5 Menu for Administrator

As the highest user level that has permission to control every management aspect in STORIX, administrator also have the permission to create RFA from requests that already authorized by managers.

4.1.5.1 Request For Approval

Request for Approval menu handles peripheral requests that need to be approved by the approver. There are three submenus available; RFA Home, Create RFA and Manual RFA.

RFA Home

RFA Home page shows the list of RFA that have been created by the administrator. This list is sorted by its creation date. In this page user can view the RFA detail by clicking [PRINT] icon.

REQUEST FOR APPROVAL BOX							
NO.	ID	FILE NO.	REQUESTER	FOR BRANCH	DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#21	XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Semarang	29 June 2007	PENDING	
2.	#20	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	29 June 2007	PENDING	
3.	#19	XXXX/RFA/BPN/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Balikpapan	28 June 2007	PENDING	
4.	#17	XXXX/RFA/SUB/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Surabaya	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
5.	#14	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
6.	#12	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	REJECTED	
7.	#11	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	APPROVED	
8.	#9	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	
9.	#8	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	
10.	#5	XXXX/RFA/BDO/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Bandung	14 June 2007	APPROVED	

Figure 4.19 Request For Approval Box

There are three possible statuses for each of Administrator RFA record;

a) **PENDING**

This RFA requires approval from the approver.

b) **AUTHORIZED**

Approver has approved all or several items on user's RFA.

c) **REJECTED**

Approver has rejected all on user's RFA.

These RFA records are able to be deleted by clicking [DELETE] icon as long as they have 'PENDING' status and deleted by the RFA creator.

Create RFA

Create RFA is the page where user can generate RFA based on user's request. At the beginning, this page shows requests in all branches that have been authorized by the managers.

To start creating a single RFA, please specify a branch by choose one of them in the branch list.

Figure 4.20 RFA Box: Select Branch

After specify the branch, the authorized request from the respective branch are displayed. Please notice that a checkbox is available on the left side of each authorized request.

A single RFA document can consist of several items, as long as these items are being requested from a same branch. To choose items user wish to be submitted to the RFA, click the checkbox available on the left side of each item. Then click [CREATE RFA] button to proceed.

REQUEST FOR APPROVAL BOX

RFA for Branch :

CREATE RFA							
	NO.	FILE NO.	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	REQUESTER	ITEM	STATUS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	Manager	Scanner	ACCEPTED
<input type="checkbox"/>	2.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	Manager	Optical Drive	ACCEPTED
<input type="checkbox"/>	3.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	Manager	Computer	ACCEPTED
<input type="checkbox"/>	4.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	Manager	Computer	ACCEPTED
<input type="checkbox"/>	5.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	User Biasa	Mouse	ACCEPTED
<input type="checkbox"/>	6.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	User Biasa	Monitor	ACCEPTED

Figure 4.21 RFA Box: Select Item Request

Now the RFA detail form is appears on user's browser. user can fill in the details needed before this RFA is being sent to the approver.

REQUEST FOR APPROVAL FORM

[Back to the Previous Page]

Submit RFA Reset RFA

NO : [XXXX/RFA/JKT/0707]
REQUESTOR : Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama
DESIGNATION : ssss
DATE : 2007-07-02

NO.	DESCRIPTION
1	SCANNER

PURPOSE: fff
-re

BRANCHES: JKT

REQ. SPECIFICS: re
-po
-kj

VENDOR QUOTATION: [-----]

Submit RFA Reset RFA

[Back to the Previous Page]

Figure 4.22 RFA Form

- a) **DESIGNATION**
Define the position of the RFA requester
(i.e. Administrator)
- b) **PURPOSE**
Define the purpose of each item requeste
- c) **REQUESTED SPECIFICS**
Define the details of each item requested.
- d) **VENDOR QUOTATION**
Determine which vendor will supply the item.

After it finish, please click [SUBMIT RFA] to continue the RFA creation process. User will be directed automatically to the RFA Home page.

Manual RFA

Manual RFA is the page where user can generate RFA based on IT administrator needs. At the beginning, this page shows the options needed to generate a manual RFA.

CREATE MANUAL RFA BOX

RFA for Branch : & Items

Figure 4.23 Manual RFA: Generating Form

When user click [GENERATE] button after fill in the branch and items to be requested, the RFA detail form will be displayed.

CREATE MANUAL RFA BOX

RFA for Branch : Jakarta Corporate Office & 1 Items

NO : XXXX/RFA/JKT/0807
REQUESTOR : Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama
DESIGNATION :
DATE : 2007-08-13

NO.	DESCRIPTION
1.	<input type="text"/>

PURPOSE:

BRANCHES: JKT

REQ. SPECIFICS:

VENDOR QUOTATION:

Figure 4.24 Manual RFA: Form

a) DESIGNATION

Define the position of the RFA requester (i.e. Administrator)

b) PURPOSE

Define the purpose of each item requested

c) REQUESTED SPECIFICS

Define the details of each item requested.

d) VENDOR QUOTATION

Determine which vendor will supply the item.

After it finish, please click [SUBMIT RFA] to continue the RFA creation process. User will be directed automatically to the RFA Home page.

4.1.5.2 Requested Access

Requested Access menu handles access requests that originated from the users. There are two submenus available; List of Access and Modify Access.

List of Access

List of Access is the page where user can view the access request information. To view the detail of each requested access, click [VIEW] icon on the right side of each record.

LIST OF REQUESTED ACCESS

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NO.	FILE NO.	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	REQUESTER	ACCESS	STATUS	CMD
1.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	User Biasa	Network	REJECTED	
2.	XXXX/ITRF/JKT/0607	JKT	Intelligent	User Biasa	Email	REJECTED	
3.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	Internet	REJECTED	
4.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	ProCars	REJECTED	
5.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	Network	APPROVED	
6.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	Email	ACCEPTED	
7.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	SAPSEM	PENDING	
8.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	CITRIX	PENDING	
9.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	Intranet	PENDING	
10.	XXXX/ITRF/SUB/0607	SUB	Ocean Freight	User Surabaya	Internet	PENDING	

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Figure 4.25 List Of Requested Access

There are five possible statuses for each of user's request record;

a) **PENDING**

This requested access requires to be authorized by the manager.

b) **ACCEPTED**

This requested access has been accepted by the manager but required to be approved by the IT Admin.

c) **ADM-APPROVED**

This requested access has been accepted by the manager
and also has been approved by the IT admin

d) **ADM-REJECTED**

This requested access has been rejected by IT admin.

e) **REJECTED**

This requested access has been rejected by manager.

Modify Access

This page enables user to change the requested access status from 'ACCEPTED' into 'ADM-APPROVED' or 'ADM-REJECTED'. The initial view of this page list requested accesses from all branch with 'ACCEPTED' status.

It is possible for user to view the detail of each request by clicking [VIEW] icon located on the right side of each record.

Figure 4.26 Modify Requested Access

Figure 4.28 Modify Requested Access: Select Access

Next, the requests user have changed are disappear from the list.

Figure 4.29 Modif Requested Access: After Modification

4.1.5.3 File

This menu enables the administrator to manage the archive records of Request, RFA and Agreement. The administrator is able to inspect each file.

There are three submenus available; Request, RFA and Agreement. Each submenu performs the same functions. Below is the example of functions available in RFA page.

This page shows the list of RFA File. User can print the detail of each RFA File by clicking [PRINT] icon on the right side of each record. To view or inspect a specific file, please click [VIEW] icon.

FILE MANAGEMENT : RFA

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Next | Last

NO.	ID	FILE NO.	REQUESTER	FOR BRANCH	DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#21	XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Semarang	29 June 2007	PENDING	
2.	#20	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	29 June 2007	PENDING	
3.	#19	XXXX/RFA/BPN/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Balikpapan	28 June 2007	PENDING	
4.	#17	XXXX/RFA/SUB/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Surabaya	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
5.	#15	XXXX/RFA/SUB/0607	Grahita Prajna Anggana	Surabaya	28 June 2007	PENDING	
6.	#14	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
7.	#12	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	REJECTED	
8.	#11	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	APPROVED	
9.	#9	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	
10.	#8	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	

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Figure 4.30 File Management: RFA List

This page shows the RFA details. To inspect this file, user can fill the required information located in [ITS USE ONLY] field set. Click [UPDATE FILE] to submit user's changes.

REQUEST FOR APPROVAL FORM

[Back to the File RFA Page]

ID : #21
NO. : XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607
REQUESTOR : Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama
DESIGNATION : Eee
DATE : 29 June 2007

NO.	DESCRIPTION	APPROVAL
1.	- MOUSE - PURPOSE: rrr yyy REQ. SPECIFICS: yyyy [u[[u VENDOR QUOTATION: Datascrip	PENDING

ITS USE ONLY

FILE NO : XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607	NOTES:
CHECKED : <input type="text"/>	
VALIDATED : <input type="text"/>	
DATE : 29 June 2007	

UPDATE FILE

[Back to the File RFA Page]

Figure 4.31 File Management: Update ITS Info

4.1.5.4 Vendor Evaluation

This menu was created to accommodate IT Admin needs in evaluating each vendor. There are two different evaluation could be generated from this feature; Standard Evaluation and Periodic Evaluation. To support these functions, five submenus are available; List, Form, Period List, Period Form and Edit Criteria.

List

This page shows user the list of Standard Vendor Evaluations that have been made.

VENDOR EVALUATION LIST

NO.	ID	EVALUATOR	VENDOR	P.O.	SCORE	DATE	CMD		
1.	#1	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER	9XXX/062007	4.00	13 June 2007			
2.	#4	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Datascrip	9XXX/062007	3.40	13 June 2007			
3.	#6	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER	9XXX/062007	2.80	13 June 2007			
4.	#3	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER	9XXX/062007	2.40	02 June 2007			

Figure 4.32 Standard Vendor Evaluation List

To view the content of each Standard Vendor Evaluation user can click [PRINT] icon.

User can delete an evaluation using [DELETE] icon as long as this record is not included in Periodic Vendor Evaluation and User is the creator of the evaluation data.

Form

This is the page where user can create a Standard Vendor Evaluation.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "VENDOR EVALUATION FORM". At the top, there are "SUBMIT" and "RESET" buttons. Below these are input fields for "DATE" (2007-07-02), "COMPANY NAME" (ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER), and "P.O. NO." (9XXX/072007). A table with two columns, "CRITERIA" and "MARKS", is present. The "CRITERIA" column lists: "Punctuality & Accuracy Of Quotation Based On Requirement", "Punctuality Of Delivery", "Accuracy Of Product/Service", "Quality Of Product/Service", and "Billing Accuracy". The "MARKS" column shows a dropdown menu with options: "EXCELLENT", "GOOD", "MEDIocre", and "POOR". Below the table is a "REMARKS" text area. At the bottom, it says "EVALUATED BY: Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama" and has another "SUBMIT" and "RESET" button.

CRITERIA	MARKS
Punctuality & Accuracy Of Quotation Based On Requirement	-----
Punctuality Of Delivery	-----
Accuracy Of Product/Service	EXCELLENT
Quality Of Product/Service	GOOD
Billing Accuracy	MEDIocre
	POOR

Figure 4.33 Standard Vendor Evaluation Form

There are four different mark options available for each criteria item; **Excellent** (4 Points), **Good** (3 Points), **Mediocre** (2 Points), and **Poor** (1 Point). By clicking [SUBMIT] user's evaluation score will be calculated and stored into the database.

Period List

This page shows user the list of Periodic Vendor Evaluations that have been made. A Periodic Vendor Evaluation consists of several Standard Evaluations for a specific Vendor in a certain period of time.

VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION LIST							
NO.	ID	VENDOR	PERIOD	SCORE	SUGGESTION	EVAL DATE	CMD
1.	#1	ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER	01 August 2006 - 02 August 2007	3.07	Maintain	02 August 2007	

Figure 4.34 Vendor Periodic Evaluation List

To view the content of each Periodic Vendor Evaluation user can click [DELETE] icon.

The Periodic Vendor Evaluation detail page is shown below;

VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION DETAILS		
[Back to the Previous Page]		
ID	: #1	
EVALUATION PERIOD	: 01 August 2006 - 02 August 2007	
COMPANY NAME	: ABADI CIPTA KOMPUTER	
EVAL. ID	P.O.	GRADE
#1	9XXX/062007	4.00
#3	9XXX/062007	2.40
#6	9XXX/062007	2.80
TOTAL		9.20
AVERAGE		3.07
REMARKS	-	
STATUS	: MAINTAIN	
DATE	: 02 August 2007	
EVALUATED BY	: Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	
[Back to the Previous Page]		

Figure 4.35 Vendor Periodic Evaluation Details

Period Form

This is the page where user can create a Period Vendor Evaluation. First, user should fill in the required parameters showed below;

VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION FORM

START DATE :

COMPANY NAME :

Figure 4.36 Vendor Periodic Evaluation: Generating Form

a) START / END DATE

Define the specific period which contains Standard Evaluation form user wish to generate.

b) COMPANY NAME

Define the vendor name user wish to evaluate periodically.

After user click [GENERATE] button, each Standard Evaluation average score will be displayed. To submit this calculation into the database, user can click [SUBMIT] button.

VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION FORM

START DATE : 2007-06-01 END: 2007-06-30

COMPANY NAME :

EVAL. ID	P.O.	GRADE
#1	9XXX/062007	4
#3	9XXX/062007	2.4
#6	9XXX/062007	2.8
TOTAL		9.2
AVERAGE		3.07

REMARKS

STATUS :

DATE : 02.07.2007

EVALUATED BY : Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama

Figure 4.37 Vendor Periodic Evaluation Details

Edit Criteria

User can add new evaluation criteria by typing the item in [MESSAGE] field available in NEW CRITERIA field set and submit it using [ADD] button.

To edit a criteria item
 [DELETE] icon is also available to delete a criteria item. Both of this icons located on the right side of each records.

CRITERIA LIST

NEW CRITERIA

MESSAGE :

CRITERIA LIST

NO	ID	MESSAGE	CMD
1.	#1	Punctuality & Accuracy Of Quotation Based On Requirement	
2.	#2	Punctuality of Delivery	
3.	#3	Accuracy Of Product/Service	
4.	#4	Quality of Product/Service	
5.	#5	Billing Accuracy	

Figure 4.38 Vendor Evaluation Criteria

4.1.5.5 Administrator Menu

In this menu, user can administer the STORIX configuration.

Members

Member page accommodates functions related to user management tasks. These tasks include view, add new, modify, and delete member records.

To add, user can insert new member's data in Add New Member form. At the beginning, each new member has a default password. Members are able to change their password later by accessing 'My Account' menu.

In case of emergency, it is possible for the IT admin to reset all members' password. To execute this function, [RESET ALL PASSWORD] button is available.

Members List table shows each member's information. At the right side of each record, there are [DELETE] icons available.

MEMBERS LIST

NEW ACCOUNT

FIRST NAME : LAST NAME :

USERNAME : PASSWORD : 'bsd'
(Default password for every user, they must change it after login)

EMAIL :

STATUS :

BRANCH : DEPARTMENT :

MANAGER :

LEVEL :

JOINT DATE : 13 Aug 2007

MEMBERS LIST

NO.	FIRSTNAME	LASTNAME	USERNAME	STATUS	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	LEVEL	REG. DATE	CMD
1.	Approver	-	Approve	-	JKT	-	Approver	01 March 2007	
2.	Grahita Prajna	Anggana	Gita	-	CGK	Information Technology	Admin	01 March 2007	
3.	Manager	-	Manager	-	JKT	Intelligent	Manager	01 March 2007	
4.	Manager	Surabaya	Msby	-	SUB	Ocean Freight	Manager	28 June 2007	
5.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian	Pratama	Aryo	-	JKT	Information Technology	Admin	01 March 2007	
6.	User	Biasa	User	-	JKT	Intelligent	Coordinator	01 March 2007	
7.	User	Surabaya	Usby	-	SUB	Ocean Freight	Coordinator	28 June 2007	

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Figure 4.39 Create New Member And Members List

Each [EDIT] icon guides user to Edit Member Form. This page shows user the detailed information of a respective member. It is possible for user to update the information within this page.

MEMBER DETAILS

[Back to the Members Page]

ACCOUNT INFORMATION

FIRST NAME : Approver LAST NAME :

USERNAME : approve PASSWORD : (Default password : 'bsd')

EMAIL : ar@ghhhh.co.id.gg

STATUS :

BRANCH : Jakarta Corporate Office DEPARTMENT :

MANAGER :

LEVEL : Approver

JOINT DATE : 01 March 2007

[Back to the Members Page]

Figure 4.40 Member Details

Items

Items page accommodates functions related to request items management tasks. These tasks include view, add new, modify, and delete request item records.

To add, user can insert new request item data in Add Item form. Item List table shows each request item information. At the right side of each record, [DELETE] icons are available.

REQUEST ITEM LIST

ADD ITEM

NAME: CATEGORY: CONSUMABLE:

ITEM LIST

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NO	NAME	CATEGORY	CONSUMABLE	CMD
1.	Computer	PERIPHERAL	NO	
2.	Keyboard	PERIPHERAL	NO	
3.	Mouse	PERIPHERAL	NO	
4.	Monitor	PERIPHERAL	NO	
5.	Printer	PERIPHERAL	NO	
6.	Modem	PERIPHERAL	NO	
7.	Scanner	PERIPHERAL	NO	

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Figure 4.41 Request Items List

Each [EDIT] icon enables user to change the description for each specific request item.

REQUEST ITEM LIST

ADD ITEM

NAME:

CATEGORY:

CONSUMABLE:

ITEM LIST

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NO	NAME	CATEGORY	CONSUMABLE	CMD
1.	Computer	PERIPHERAL	NO	UPDATE
2.	Keyboard	PERIPHERAL	NO	
3.	Mouse	PERIPHERAL	NO	
4.	Monitor	PERIPHERAL	NO	
5.	Printer	PERIPHERAL	NO	
6.	Modem	PERIPHERAL	NO	
7.	Scanner	PERIPHERAL	NO	

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Figure 4.42 Modify Request Item List

Navigation

Navigation page accommodates functions related to navigational menu management tasks. These tasks include view, add new, modify, and delete navigation records.

To add, user can insert new navigation data in Add New Menu form. Navigation List table shows each navigation's information. At the right side of each record, [EDIT] and [DELETE] icons are available.

MENU EDITING

PERMISSION INFO

1 = Admin, 2 = Approver, 3 = Manager, 4 = Coordinator,

ADD NEW MENU

SORT:

NAME:

LINK:

CATEGORY:

IMAGE LINK:

PERMISSION:

NAVIGATION LIST

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NO	ID	SORT	NAME	LINK	CATEGORY	IMAGE LINK	PERMISSION	CMD
1.	#1	1	Home	./index.php	MAIN	./img/home.png	1,2,3,4	
2.	#2	2	Request	./req.php	MAIN	./img/request.png	3,4	
3.	#3	3	Authorize	./authorize.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	3	
4.	#4	4	Request For Approval	./rfa.php	MAIN	./img/request.png	1	
5.	#5	5	Approve	./approve.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	2	
6.	#6	6	Requested Access	./req_access.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	1	
7.	#7	7	File	./file_request.php	MAIN	./img/file.png	1	
8.	#8	8	Inventory And Access	./inventory.php	MAIN	./img/inventory.png	1	
9.	#9	9	Vendor Evaluation	./vendor_eval_home.php	MAIN	./img/vendor.png	1	
10.	#10	10	Report	./6_acc_br_per.php	MAIN	./img/report.png	1	

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Figure 4.43 Navigation Menu List

a) SORT

Define the menu's sequence shown on the page. Menu with sort 1 appears on the upper position.

b) NAME

Define the name of the menu inserted.

c) LINK

Define the address path of the displayed page.

d) PARENT ID

Define the parent ID of the new menu.

e) IMAGE LINK

Define the address path of the image used for each menu.

f) PERMISSION

Define the user permission which have an access to the menu.

Each [EDIT] icon enables user to change the description for each specific navigation menu.

MENU EDITING

PERMISSION INFO
 1 = Admin, 2 = Approver, 3 = Manager, 4 = Coordinator,

ADD NEW MENU

SORT: NAME: LINK: CATEGORY: IMAGE LINK: PERMISSION:

NAVIGATION LIST

Page 1 of 6 Next | Last

NO	ID	SORT	NAME	LINK	CATEGORY	IMAGE LINK	PERMISSION	CMD
1.	#1	1	Home	./index.php	main	./img/home.png	1,2,3,4	UPDATE
2.	#2	2	Request	./req.php	MAIN	./img/request.png	3,4	
3.	#3	3	Authorize	./authorize.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	3	
4.	#4	4	Request For Approval	./rfa.php	MAIN	./img/request.png	1	
5.	#5	5	Approve	./approve.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	2	
6.	#6	6	Requested Access	./req_access.php	MAIN	./img/approve.png	1	
7.	#7	7	File	./file_request.php	MAIN	./img/file.png	1	
8.	#8	8	Inventory And Access	./inventory.php	MAIN	./img/inventory.png	1	
9.	#9	9	Vendor Evaluation	./vendor_eval_home.php	MAIN	./img/vendor.png	1	
10.	#10	10	Report	./6_acc_br_per.php	MAIN	./img/report.png	1	

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Figure 4.44 Modify Navigation Menu

MOTD

MOTD page accommodates functions related to Message of the Day management tasks. Message of the day is a random selected quote appears on the Home page. These tasks include view, add new, modify, and delete department records.

To add, user can insert new message in New Message form.

Message List table shows each message that already stored in the database. At the right side of each record, [DELETE] icons are available.

MOTD : MESSAGE OF THE DAY LIST

NEW MESSAGE

MESSAGE :

MOTD LIST

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NO	ID	MESSAGE	CMD
1.	#1	May The Force Be With You	
2.	#2	To Be Or Not To Be, That Is The Question	
3.	#3	Laziness Is The Mother Of All Inventions	
4.	#4	Lack Of Funds Is The Mother Of All Innovations	
5.	#5	Lack Of Staff Is The Mother Of All Collaborations	
6.	#6	Air Beriak Tanda Tak Dalam	
7.	#7	Muke Jauh Bukan Salah Orang Lain	
8.	#8	If Loving You Is Wrong, Then I Don't Want To Be Right	
9.	#9	It Is Better To Be An "expert" Than It Is To Do Actual Work.	
10.	#10	Orang Pintar Pantang Menanggung Rugi Buta	

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Figure 4.45 Modify MOTD

Each [EDIT] icon enables user to change the message.

MOTD : MESSAGE OF THE DAY LIST

NEW MESSAGE

MESSAGE :

MOTD LIST

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NO	ID	MESSAGE	CMD
1.	#1	May The Force Be With You	
2.	#2	To Be Or Not To Be, That Is The Question	
3.	#3	Laziness Is The Mother Of All Inventions	
4.	#4	Lack Of Funds Is The Mother Of All Innovations	
5.	#5	Lack Of Staff Is The Mother Of All Collaborations	
6.	#6	Air Beriak Tanda Tak Dalam	
7.	#7	Muke Jauh Bukan Salah Orang Lain	
8.	#8	If Loving You Is Wrong, Then I Don't Want To Be Right	
9.	#9	It Is Better To Be An "expert" Than It Is To Do Actual Work.	
10.	#10	Orang Pintar Pantang Menanggung Rugi Buta	

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Figure 4.46 Modify MOTD

Log History

Log History menu shows records of user login history.

LOG HISTORY

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NO	NAME	IP ADDRESS	TIME	STATUS
1.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	13 August 2007 14:52:08	LOGIN
2.	Manager	127.0.0.1	13 August 2007 14:52:05	LOGOUT
3.	Manager	127.0.0.1	13 August 2007 14:50:03	LOGIN
4.	User Biasa	127.0.0.1	13 August 2007 14:49:59	LOGOUT
5.	User Biasa	127.0.0.1	13 August 2007 14:48:25	LOGIN
6.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	02 August 2007 23:00:05	LOGOUT
7.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	02 August 2007 05:31:29	LOGIN
8.	User Biasa	127.0.0.1	02 August 2007 05:31:26	LOGOUT
9.	User Biasa	127.0.0.1	02 August 2007 05:29:35	LOGIN
10.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 17:22:35	LOGOUT
11.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 17:12:24	LOGIN
12.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 16:49:30	LOGOUT
13.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 16:07:30	LOGIN
14.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 15:34:40	LOGOUT
15.	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	127.0.0.1	31 July 2007 15:12:20	LOGIN

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Figure 4.47 Log History List

4.1.5.6 Agreement

Agreement page is used to generate user acceptance and agreement. By clicking [I AGREE] in this page, users signify that they have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy.

AGREEMENT BOX

Yes, I agree with the IT policies (For Admin Only)

By signing this document, I signify that I have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy. If I fail to abide and adhere to the before mentioned guidelines, either willfully or otherwise, I will submit and accept the penalties and consequences of such actions.

Dengan menandatangani dokumen ini, saya menyatakan bahwa saya telah membaca, mengerti dan menyetujui untuk mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk PT Schenker Petrolog Utama sesuai dengan yang tertuang di dalam kebijakan Pedoman PC Informasi Teknologi. Apabila saya gagal mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk yang disebut sebelumnya, baik secara sengaja ataupun tidak sengaja, saya sanggup dan bersedia menerima sanksi atau akibat dari tindakan tersebut.</p>

UPDATE AGREEMENT TEXT

NO.	FILE NO.	BRANCH	DEPARTMENT	NAME	AGREE	MANAGER	ACKNOWLEDGE	DATE	ACK. DATE
1.	XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	-	Approver	YES	-	PENDING	14 June 2007	-
2.	XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	Manager	YES	-	PENDING	13 June 2007	-
3.	XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Information Technology	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	YES	-	PENDING	13 June 2007	-
4.	XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607	Jakarta Corporate Office	Intelligent	User Biasa	YES	Manager	YES	19 June 2007	21 June 2007

Figure 4.48 Administrator Agreement Box

4.1.6 Menu for Approver

Approver is the user level that decide whether an RFA will be approved or rejected. Any RFA will stop their request-approval cycle in this highest bureaucracy level.

4.1.6.1 Approve

Every request that has been accepted by manager and IT admin will need user’s approval. Approval box lists all RFA documents.

Each document has its own status as described below;

a) PENDING

This RFA requires user’s approval. To perform this task, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

b) APPROVED

User have approved all or several items requested in the respective RFA. To view the RFA detail, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

c) REJECTED

User have rejected all items requested in the respective RFA. To view the RFA detail, please click [VIEW] icon at the right side of the table.

To print the RFA document detail, please click [PRINT] icon.

APPROVAL BOX

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NO.	ID	FILE NO.	REQUESTER	FOR BRANCH	DATE	STATUS	CMD
1.	#21	XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Semarang	29 June 2007	PENDING	
2.	#20	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	29 June 2007	PENDING	
3.	#19	XXXX/RFA/BPN/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Balikpapan	28 June 2007	PENDING	
4.	#17	XXXX/RFA/SUB/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Surabaya	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
5.	#15	XXXX/RFA/SUB/0607	Grahita Prajna Anggana	Surabaya	28 June 2007	PENDING	
6.	#14	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	28 June 2007	APPROVED	
7.	#12	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	REJECTED	
8.	#11	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	21 June 2007	APPROVED	
9.	#9	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	
10.	#8	XXXX/RFA/JKT/0607	Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama	Jakarta Corporate Office	20 June 2007	APPROVED	

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Figure 4.49 Approval Box

Approval Process

After user clicked [VIEW] icon for a specific RFA record, the RFA Form page will appear. In this page user will be able to approve each request items on the item approval box.

There are two different options available on each item approval box; APPROVE and REJECT. After user finish approving all items in the item approval box, [APPROVE] button will submit user's changes and bring user back to Approval Box page.

APPROVAL DETAILS

[Back to the Approval Page]

ID : #21
NO : XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607
REQUESTOR : Muhammad Aryo Nurdian Pratama
DESIGNATION : Eee
DATE : 29 June 2007

NO.	DESCRIPTION	APPROVAL
1.	- MOUSE - PURPOSE: rrr yyy REQ. SPECIFICS: yyyy [u][u] VENDOR QUOTATION: Datascrip	BRANCHES: SRG <input type="button" value="APPROVE"/>

ITS USE ONLY

FILE NO : XXXX/RFA/SRG/0607 **NOTES:**
CHECKED : -
VALIDATED : -
DATE : 29 June 2007

[Back to the Approval Page]

Figure 4.50 Approval Process

There are two additional buttons both in upper and lower side of RFA form details. The first button, [APPROVE ALL], will set all request items into 'RFA-APPROVED' state. The second button, [REJECT ALL] will set all items into 'RFA-REJECT' state. These buttons will brings user back to Approval Box page immediately. It is not necessary for user to authorize the request items one by one.

4.1.6.2 Agreement

Agreement page is used to generate user acceptance and agreement. By clicking [I AGREE] in this page, users signify that they have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy.

AGREEMENT BOX

IT PC Guidelines Policy Reference-No: 1.0.0 -
User Acceptance and Agreement Form
Referensi Kebijakan Pedoman PC IT - No: 1.0.0
Formulir Penerimaan dan Persetujuan Pengguna

EMPLOYEE NAME/Nama Pegawai:

Approver

DEPARTMENT/Departemen:

-

BRANCH/Cabang:

Jakarta Corporate Office

**By signing this document, I signify that I have read, understood, and agree to abide and adhere to the guidelines of PT Schenker Petrolog Utama as documented in the IT PC Guidelines Policy.
If I fail to abide and adhere to the before mentioned guidelines, either willfully or otherwise, I will submit and accept the penalties and consequences of such actions.**

Dengan menandatangani dokumen ini, saya menyatakan bahwa saya telah membaca, mengerti dan menyetujui untuk mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk PT Schenker Petrolog Utama sesuai dengan yang tertuang di dalam kebijakan Pedoman PC Informasi Teknologi. Apabila saya gagal mentaati dan memenuhi petunjuk yang disebut sebelumnya, baik secara sengaja ataupun tidak sengaja, saya sanggup dan bersedia menerima sanksi atau akibat dari tindakan tersebut.

YES, I AGREE

Approver

Date/Tgl.: 14 June 2007

ITS USE ONLY

FILE NO : XXXX/ITAF/JKT/0607 NOTES:
CHECKED : -
VALIDATED : -
DATE : 14 June 2007

Figure 4.51 Approver Agreement Box

4.2 User Acceptance Test

User Acceptance Testing (UAT) is a process to obtain confirmation by a Subject Matter Expert (SME), preferably the owner or client of the object under test, through trial or review, that the modification or addition meets mutually agreed-upon requirements (Wikipedia,2007). In software development, UAT is one of the final stages of a project and often occurs before a client or customer accepts the new system. Prior to implementation, the program is tested first to ensure that the database is connected properly, the queries are correct, and the program is free from errors. After testing, the program is uploaded to Schenker application server while the database is uploaded in to Schenker database server. Another test is conducted to make

sure that the program is work in the respective server. This test is performed by the user on 4th – 8th, 2007.

4.2.1 Time Evaluation

Based on interview with Schenker IT staff, below is the comparison table of time between the previous system and STORIX.

Processes	Previous System	STORIX
From Request to Authorization	10 – 30 mnt	5 – 7 mnt
From RFA to Approval	10 – 30 mnt	5 – 7 mnt
Archiving File	Process N/A	Automatically Generated
Calculate and Search Related PO for Vendor Evaluation	15 – 60 mnt	3 mnt
Create and Calculate Periodic Vendor Evaluation	15 – 30 mnt	3 mnt

Table 4.52 Time Evaluation Table

4.2.2 Document Size Evaluation

Also included below is comparison table of document size evaluation. Test performed using Acer Travelmate 803 Lci, with Open SuSE 10.2 and Mozilla Firefox 2.0 browser.

Document	Previous System	STORIX
ITS Request Form	55 KB	9.1 KB
Request For Approval Form	100 KB	7.2 KB
Vendor Evaluation Form	56 KB	8.6 KB
Periodic Vendor Evaluation Form	62 KB	9.2 KB

Table 4.53 Document Size Evaluation Table

*Comparison between maximum file size in .doc with HTML generated file complete with image.

4.3 Construction

This system is constructed by taking information from the database.

Following explanation describe the construction process for each module involved.

4.3.1 Authentication Module

Authentication process deliver by “login.php” file. This file compares given username and password from the user with the stored data in database. If the data match with the user that access STORIX, it will store any parameters that requires by the user to access the STORIX system into Session.

Listed below is the query used in authorization process;

```
SELECT CONCAT(user.name, ' ',user.given_name) AS fullname,
branch.branch_id AS bid,
user.username,
user.id as uid,
departments.name AS department,
departments.id AS did,
CONCAT(manager.name, ' ',manager.given_name) AS mgr_name,
manager.id AS mid,
user.level_id_fk AS user_level,
branch.name AS branches
FROM user LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk)
LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id = user.branch_id_fk)
LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id = user.mgr_id_fk)
WHERE user.username = '$username' AND user.password =
'$password' ;
```

After authenticating the user, this file also logs user into database for security record.

```
INSERT INTO log_history VALUES
(NULL, '$_SESSION['uid'].', '$_SERVER['REMOTE_ADDR'].', '$_SESSION['inTime'].', 'LOGIN');
```

When all of the authentication process succeeds, the browser will redirect the user to the Home page.

4.3.2 Request and Approval Module

This module involve several phases that have to be done to complete the circle of Request and Approval process. The phases are; Request, Authorization, RFA, and Approval.

In Request Phase, the user will input any data that required by the system to process the request according to their type; Account or Peripheral (`req_its_form.php`).

```
INSERT INTO request VALUES
(NULL, '$file_id_fk', '$_SESSION['uid'].', '$req_type_txt', '$date', '$time', '$emp_name', '$_SESSION['bid'].', '$_SESSION['did'].', '$_SESSION['mid'].', '$title', '$status', '$req_details', 'PENDING', '');
```

After a request created, it needs to be authorized whether the status details of each item or access will be accepted or rejected. The process of authorization would be explained by the script below

(`auth_details.php`).

```
if(isset($_POST['authorized'])) {
    $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {
        $upd_det_stat = $_POST['req_det_stat'][$row];
        $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = '$upd_det_stat' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id';";
        mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);
    }
    $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status =
'AUTHORIZED', auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id =
'$req_id_fk';";
    mysql_query($upd_req_query);
}
```

```
        header("location:$this_page");
    } elseif(isset($_POST['auth_all'])){
        $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];
        foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {
            $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = 'ACCEPTED' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id'";
            mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);
        }
        $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status =
'AUTHORIZED', auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id =
'$req_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_req_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    } elseif(isset($_POST['reject_all'])){
        $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];
        foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {
            $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = 'REJECTED' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id'";
            mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);
        }
        $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status =
'REJECTED', auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id =
'$req_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_req_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }
}
```

There are two ways to create RFA. First, it can be created from item based request type that already authorized by manager and the specific item has “ACCEPTED” as the status. after RFA created the item status in the request will be changed to “RFA-PENDING” and for the RFA form itself the item status will be mark as “PENDING”. Second, using `rfa_manual.php`, Administrator define the branch and how many item would be placed in the RFA and generate it.

Account-based request type do not need approval from approver, the bureaucracy stops in administrator level, the administrator only need to mark the accepted requested access from authorized request into “ADM-APPROVE” or “ADM-REJECTED”.

Below is the query needed to insert details of RFA information into database (`rfa_create_form.php` & `rfa_manual.php`).

```
INSERT INTO rfa_details VALUES
(NULLL, '$rfa_id_fk', '$value_rfa_det_id',
'$item_name_info', '$purpose', '$specific_note', '$vendor_id_fk',
'PENDING');
```

For Account-type request, below is the script that responsible to run the approval process for administrator (`req_acc_act.php`).

```
if(isset($_POST['approve_access']) AND
isset($_POST['req_det_id']!='')) {

$req_det_id = $_POST['req_det_id'];

    foreach ($req_det_id as $req_id) {
        $act_acc_query = "UPDATE request_details
SET status = 'ADM-APPROVED' WHERE id = '$req_id'";
        mysql_query($act_acc_query);
    }
    header("location:$this_page");
}

if(isset($_POST['reject_access']) AND
isset($_POST['req_det_id']!='')) {
    $req_det_id = $_POST['req_det_id'];
    foreach ($req_det_id as $req_id) {
        $act_acc_query = "UPDATE request_details
SET status = 'ADM-REJECTED' WHERE id = '$req_id'";
        mysql_query($act_acc_query);
    }
    header("location:$this_page");
}
```

Process and phase for account-type request will be stop right here, but for the item-based request it continues. In approval process, approver will decide which item in RFA would be eligible to approve based on the company requirements.

Here are the script that runs the approval process

(`approval_details.php`).

```
if(isset($_POST['approve'])) {
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key =>
    $rfa_det_id_value) {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat = $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET
        status = '$upd_rfa_det_stat' WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);
        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM
        rfa_details WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);
        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1)
        {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
            mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE request_details SET status
                = 'RFA-".$upd_rfa_det_stat."' WHERE id =
                '>".$select_req_det_id_array[0]."'";
                mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
            }
        }
        $upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'APPROVED',
        appr_id_fk = '". $_SESSION['uid'] ."', appr_date = '".date('Y-m-
        d')." ' WHERE id = '$rfa_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }
}
elseif(isset($_POST['appr_all'])) {
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key =>
    $rfa_det_id_value) {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat =
        $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET
        status = 'APPROVED' WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);
        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM
        rfa_details WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);
        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1) {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
            mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE
                request_details SET status = 'RFA-APPROVED' WHERE id =
```

```
        ".$select_req_det_id_array[0]."';";
        mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
    }
}
}
$upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'APPROVED',
appr_id_fk = '". $_SESSION['uid'] ."', appr_date = '". date('Y-m-
d') ."' WHERE id = '$rfa_id_fk'";
mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
header("location:$this_page");
}
elseif(isset($_POST['reject_all'])){
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key =>
$rfa_det_id_value) {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat = $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET status =
'REJECTED' WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);
        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM
rfa_details WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);
        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1) {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE request_details SET status = 'RFA-
REJECTED' WHERE id = '". $select_req_det_id_array[0]."';";
                mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
            }
        }
    }
}
$upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'REJECTED',
appr_id_fk = '". $_SESSION['uid'] ."', appr_date = '". date('Y-m-
d') ."' WHERE id = '$rfa_id_fk'";
mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
header("location:$this_page");
}
```

4.3.3 Evaluation Module

There are two types of evaluation; Standard and Periodic Evaluation.

In Standard Evaluation, file `vendor_eval.php` would ask for information about the vendor, PO number, date for evaluation, and remarks for each evaluated criteria. This file will generate score from remarks input and store it in database.

Listed below, queries that used to insert evaluation criterias with their respective score.

```
$insert_vdr_eval_query="INSERT INTO vendor_eval VALUES
(NULL, '$date.', '$vendor.', '$po_number.', '$avg_score
.', '$remarks.', '$evaluator.', '');";

mysql_query($insert_vdr_eval_query);
$vendor_eval_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
foreach($crit_id as $crit_id_key => $crit_id_value) {
    $score_array = $score[$crit_id_key];
    $insert_vdr_eval_det_query = "INSERT INTO vendor_eval_details
VALUES
(NULL, '$vendor_eval_id_fk.', '$crit_id_value.', '$score_a
rray.');";
        mysql_query($insert_vdr_eval_det_query);
    }
}
```

Periodic Evaluation file `vendor_eval_pr.php` collects several standard evaluation based on their evaluation period and calculate the total and average score. Administrator will decide whether the vendor would be maintain in AVL or eliminate from AVL.

```
$insert_eval_pr_query = "INSERT INTO vendor_eval_period ";
$insert_eval_pr_query .= "VALUES
(NULL, '$startdate', '$enddate', '$vendor_id_fk',
'$total', '$average', '$remarks', '$suggestion', '$evaldate', '$use
r_id_fk');";
mysql_query($insert_eval_pr_query);
$vdr_ev_pr_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
foreach($eval_id_fk as $vdr_eval_id_fk) {
    $insert_eval_pr_det_query = "INSERT INTO
vendor_eval_period_details ";
    $insert_eval_pr_det_query .= "VALUES
(NULL, '$vdr_ev_pr_id_fk.',
'$vdr_eval_id_fk.');";
}
```

```
mysql_query($insert_eval_pr_det_query) or die
(mysql_error());
$update_eval_query = "UPDATE vendor_eval SET period = '1'
WHERE id = '". $vdr_eval_id_fk. "'";
mysql_query($update_eval_query);
}
```

4.3.4 Administrative Module

In this module there are several files involved; `members.php`, `member_details.php`, `item_type.php`, `navigation.php`, `motd.php`, and `log_history.php`. Each query used to construct those pages will be described below.

`Members.php` enables user to add new user and view the list of all users in the system. Query used to add new user into database is

```
INSERT INTO user VALUES
(NULL, '". $fname. "', '". $lname. "', '". $username. "',
' ". $password. "', '". $email. "', '". $status. "', '". $branch. "', '". $d
epartment. "', '". $manager. "', '". $level. "', '". $jointdate. ');
```

And query for displaying list of all members

```
SELECT user.id, user.name, user.given_name, user.username,
user.status, branch.branch_id, departments.name,
user_level.name, user.jointdate
FROM user LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk)
LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id = user.dept_id_fk)
LEFT JOIN user_level ON (user_level.id = user.level_id_fk)
ORDER BY user.name ASC
LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage;
```

`Members_details.php` used to update informations about specific user.

Here is the query for updating the data.

```
UPDATE user SET name = '". $fname. "', given_name = '". $lname. "',
email = '". $email. "', status = '". $status. "',
```

```
branch_id_fk='". $branch. "', dept_id_fk='". $department. "',  
mgr_id_fk='". $manager. "', level_id_fk='". $level. '''  
WHERE id = '". $update_id. '";
```

Every item and access that listed in ITS Request Form are flexible to generate because of `item_type.php` functioned to view, insert, update, and delete every of them. Here are the queries that responsible to view all of the listed item and access.

```
SELECT request_items.id, request_items.name, request_type.id,  
request_type.name, request_items.consumable  
FROM request_items LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id  
= request_items.req_type_id_fk)  
ORDER BY request_items.id ASC  
LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";
```

`Navigation.php` has similar function like `item_type.php`. Query used by `navigation.php` to view the menu list is

```
SELECT id, sort, name, link, category, img_link, permit FROM  
navigation ORDER BY sort ASC";  
$nav_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage;
```

MOTD or Message Of The Day (`motd.php`) also has similar function. Query used by `motd.php` to view list of messages is

```
SELECT id, message FROM motd ORDER BY id ASC  
LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage;
```

`Log_history.php` only functioned for displaying the authentication log. Administrator can track the log-in/out information of each user. Listed below is the query to perform the operation.

```
SELECT log_history.id, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name)  
AS fullname, log_history.ip_addr, log_history.time,  
log_history.activities
```

```
FROM log_history LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id =  
log_history.user_id_fk)  
ORDER BY log_history.time DESC  
LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage;
```

CHAPTER 5 – CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

After analyzing, designing, building and testing of the web-based Request and Approval modules and additional modules that support the process, several conclusions can be made;

- a) The Request and Approval modules have run well according to the business requirements.
- b) The Vendor Evaluation module has fulfill the basic needs for Administrator to evaluate vendors.
- c) Flexibility and modularity of system helps administrators to build a new modules with different feature based on the module template and registered it to the system.
- d) Reduce time waste and efficient file size generated by STORIX.

5.2 Recommendation

Some recommendations to improve the module are as follows;

- a) It is expected to have a notification system that can inform user if their request or RFA has been authorized or approved.
- b) A more objective and comparative process would be better to improve the vendor evaluation process.
- c) A Function for estimating delivery time in Request and Approval modules would be helpfull for user to know when their request will be arrived.

GLOSSARY

Apache

The most common web server (or HTTP server) software on the Internet. Apache is an open-source application originally created from a series of changes (“patches”) made to a web server written at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications, the same place the Mosaic web browser was created. Apache is designed as a set of modules, enabling administrators to choose which features they wish to use and making it easy to add features to meet specific needs including handling protocols other than the web-standard HTTP.

Browser

A client program (software) that is used to look at various kinds of Internet resources.

Client

A system that accesses a (remote) service on another computer by some kind of network. The term was first applied to devices that were not capable of running their own stand-alone programs, but could interact with remote computers via a network.

Database

Collection of information organized into related tables of data and definitions of data objects. The data within a database can be easily accessed and manipulated through computer program.

Decision Support System (DSS)

Computer-based information systems that combine models and data in an attempt to solve nonstructured problems with extensive user involvement through a friendly user interface.

FAST

A hypothetical methodology which used to demonstrate a representative systems development process. The acronym's letter stands for Framework for the Application of Systems Thinking.

Foreign key

A key field (column) that identifies records in a table by matching a primary key in a different table. The foreign keys are used to cross-reference tables.

Graphical User Interface (GUI)

A method of interacting with a computer through a metaphor of direct manipulation of graphical images and widgets in addition to text.

HTML

HyperText Markup Language is a markup language designed for the creation of web pages and other information viewable in a browser. HTML is used to structure information – denoting certain text as headings, paragraphs, lists and so on.

Internet

The vast collection of inter-connected networks that are connected using the TCP/IP protocols and that evolved from the ARPANET of the late 60's and early 70's. The Internet connects tens of thousands of independent networks into a vast global internet and is probably the largest Wide Area Network in the world.

Intranet

A private network inside a company or organization that uses the same kinds of software that you would find on the public Intranet, but that is only for internal use. Compare with extranet.

JavaScript

A programming language that is mostly used in web pages, usually to add features that make the web page more interactive. When JavaScript is included in an HTML file, it relies upon the browser to interpret the JavaScript. When JavaScript is

combined with Cascading Style Sheets (CSS), and later versions of HTML (4.0 and later) the results often called DHTML.

MySQL

An open source relational database management system. MySQL can be used on various platforms including UNIX, Linux and Windows. MySQL is widely used as a backend database for Web applications and it is a cheaper alternative to enterprise database systems like MS SQL Server and Oracle.

Module

A portion of a program that carries out a specific function and may be used alone or combined with other modules of the same program.

Network

A number of interconnected computers, machines or operations.

Open-source

A program in which the source code is available to the general public for use and/or modification from its original design free of charge.

PHP (PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor)

A programming language used almost exclusively for creating software that is part of a web site. The PHP language is designed to be intermingled with the HTML that is used to create web pages. Unlike HTML, the PHP code is read and processed by the web server software.

Primary Key

The primary key of a relational table holds a unique value, which identifies each record in the table. It can either be a normal field (column) that is guaranteed to be unique or it can be generated by the database system itself (GUID or Identity field in MS SQL Server for example). Primary keys may be composed of more than 1 field (column) in a table.

Programming language

Or computer language is a standardized communication technique for expressing instructions to a computer. It is a set of syntactic and semantic rules used to define computer programs.

Relational Database

A database whose records are organized into tables that can be processed by either relational algebra or relational calculus.

Query

The main way to make a request for information from a database. Queries consist of questions presented to the database in a predefined format, in most cases SQL (Structure Query Language) format.

Scripting language

A high-level programming language that is interpreted by another program at runtime rather than compiled by the computer's processor as other programming languages (such as C and C++) are. Scripting languages, which can be embedded within HTML, commonly are used to add functionality to a Web page.

Server

A computer on a network that controls access to data. A single server machine can (and often does) have several different server software packages running on it, thus providing many different servers to clients on the network.

System

A group of interdependent items that interact regularly to perform a task.

User friendly

Easy to use or understand.

Web Server

A computer that deliver (serves up) Web pages.

Web-based application

An application from a web server which is delivered over a network such as World Wide Web or an intranet.

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APPENDIX A – TABLE SPECIFICATIONS

Access table

Primary Key : access_id
 Foreign Key 1 : req_items_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : request_id_fk
 Foreign Key 3 : user_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
access_id	int(11)	No		access code
req_items_id_fk	int(11)	No		request items code
request_id_fk	int(11)	No		request code
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		user code
name	varchar(64)	No		access name
acc_group	varchar(64)	No	-	access group
sec	varchar(64)	No	-	access sector
email	varchar(64)	No		access owner's email
position	varchar(64)	No	-	access owner's position
branch_id_fk	varchar(16)	No		branch code
date_active	date	No		access creation date
date_delete	date	No		access deletion date

Agreement Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : file_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : user_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Agreement ID
file_id_fk	int(11)	No		File ID
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		User
status	varchar(32)	No	0	Agreement status
manager_id	int(11)	No		User's manager
mgr_status	varchar(32)	No	0	Acknowledge status
date	date	No		Agreement date
ackdate	date	No		Acknowledge date

Branch Table

Primary Key : branch_id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
branch_id	varchar(32)	No		Branch Code
name	varchar(255)	No		Branch Name
city	varchar(255)	No		Branch Location
emp_num	int(11)	No		Number of Employee

Departments Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Department Code
name	varchar(255)	No		Department Name

Detail_type Table

Primary Key : detail_type_id

Foreign Key : inv_type_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
detail_type_id	int(255)	No		Detail Inventory Item Code
inv_type_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Request Item Code
type_name	varchar(255)	No		Detail Type Name

File Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		File ID
code	varchar(64)	No		File code
date	date	No		File date
checked	int(11)	No		Checker
validated	int(11)	No		Validator
notes	mediumtext	No		File notes

Inventory Table

Primary Key : inv_id

Foreign Key 1 : req_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : vendors_id_fk

Foreign Key 3 : branch_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
inv_id	int(11)	No		Inventory Code
req_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Request Code
vendors_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Vendor Code
branch_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Branch Code
price_usd	double	No		Price in USD
currency	varchar(3)	No		Currency
usd_rate	double	No		Currency Rate to USD
life	int(255)	Yes	NULL	Life Expectation
buy_date	date	No		Purchase Date
inv_type_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Request Item Code

Inventory_details Table

Foreign Key 1 : inv_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : detail_type_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
inv_id_fk	int(11)	No		Request Item Code
detail_type_id_fk	int(11)	No	0	Detail Inventory Item Code
description	varchar(255)	No		Inventory Detail Description

Log_history Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Log ID
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		User
ip_addr	varchar(32)	No		IP Address
time	datetime	No		Log time
activities	varchar(32)	No		Login or logout

MOTD Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		MOTD ID
message	mediumtext	No		The message

Navigation Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Menu ID
sort	int(11)	No		Sorting
name	varchar(64)	No		Menu name
link	varchar(255)	No		Menu link
category	varchar(11)	No		Menu category
img_link	varchar(255)	No		Menu image link
permit	varchar(32)	No		Menu permission

Request Table

Primary Key : id

Foreign Key 1 : file_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : user_id_fk

Foreign Key 3 : branch_id_fk

Foreign Key 4 : dept_id_fk

Foreign Key 5 : mgr_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Request ID
file_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Request file ID
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		Requester
req_type	varchar(32)	No		Req. type
req_date	date	No		Req. date
req_time	time	No		Req. time
employee_name	varchar(32)	No		Employee name
branch_id_fk	varchar(255)	No		Req. branch
dept_id_fk	int(11)	No		Req. department
mgr_id_fk	int(11)	No		Authorizator
title	varchar(32)	No		Employee title
status	varchar(32)	No		Employee status
req_details	mediumtext	No		Req. notes
req_status	varchar(32)	No		Req. status
auth_date	date	No		Authorization date

Request_details Table

Primary Key : id

Foreign Key 1 : req_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : req_item_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Req. details ID
req_id_fk	int(11)	No		Req. ID FK
req_item_id_fk	int(11)	No		Item requested
status	varchar(32)	No		Status of the item

Request_items Table

Primary Key : id

Foreign Key 1 : req_type_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Item ID
name	varchar(32)	No		Item name
req_type_id_fk	int(11)	No		Item's type
consumable	tinyint(1)	No		Consumable or not?

Request_type Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Type ID
name	varchar(255)	No		Type Name

RFA Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : file_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : user_id_fk
 Foreign Key 3 : branch_id_fk
 Foreign Key 4 : appr_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		RFA ID
file_id_fk	int(11)	No		Filing ID
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		RFA Requester
branch_id_fk	varchar(32)	No		RFA Branch origin
designation	varchar(32)	No		RFA Requester's Designation
date	date	No		RFA date creation
appr_id_fk	int(11)	No		RFA approver
appr_date	date	No		RFA approve date
status	varchar(32)	No		RFA approve status

Rfa_details Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : rfa_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : req_details_id_fk
 Foreign Key 3 : vendor_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		RFA Details ID
rfa_id_fk	int(11)	No		RFA FK
req_details_id_fk	int(11)	No		Item/Access FK from req. details
item_name	varchar(32)	No		Item name
purpose	mediumtext	No		Purpose
spec_notes	mediumtext	No		Specific Notes
vendor_id_fk	int(11)	No		Vendor
status	varchar(32)	No		RFA Item details status

User Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : branch_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : dept_id_fk
 Foreign Key 3 : mgr_id_fk
 Foreign Key 4 : level_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		User ID
name	varchar(32)	No		First Name
given_name	varchar(32)	No		Last Name

username	varchar(32)	No		User Name
password	varchar(255)	No		Password
email	varchar(127)	No		Email
status	varchar(32)	No		User's status
branch_id_fk	varchar(8)	No		Branch Code
dept_id_fk	int(11)	No		Department Code
mgr_id_fk	int(11)	No		User's Manager
level_id_fk	int(11)	No		User's Level
jointdate	date	No		Registration Date

User_level Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Level ID
name	text	No		Level Type

Vendor_criteria Table

Primary Key : id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Criteria ID
name	mediumtext	No		Criteria message

Vendor_eval Table

Primary Key : id

Foreign Key 1 : vendor_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : user_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Evaluation ID
date	date	No		Evaluation date
vendor_id_fk	int(11)	No		Evaluated vendor
po_number	varchar(32)	No		PO number
avg_score	double	No		Average score
remarks	mediumtext	No		Remarks
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		Evaluator
period	tinyint(1)	No		Status: Already in Periodic or Not

Vendor_eval_details Table

Primary Key : id

Foreign Key 1 : vendor_eval_id_fk

Foreign Key 2 : vendor_criteria_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Evaluation details ID
vendor_eval_id_fk	int(11)	No		Evaluated vendor
vendor_criteria_id_fk	int(11)	No		Criteria

score	double	No	Score
-------	--------	----	-------

Vendor_eval_period Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : vendor_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : user_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Eval period. ID
startdate	date	No		Eval. periodic start date
enddate	date	No		Eval. periodic end date
vendor_id_fk	int(11)	No		Evaluated vendor
total	double	No		Total score
average	double	No		Average score
remarks	mediumtext	No		Remarks
suggestion	varchar(32)	No		Suggestion
evaldate	date	No		Evaluation date
user_id_fk	int(11)	No		Evaluator

Vendor_eval_period_details Table

Primary Key : id
 Foreign Key 1 : vdr_ev_pr_id_fk
 Foreign Key 2 : vdr_ev_id_fk

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
id	int(11)	No		Periodic eval details ID
vdr_ev_pr_id_fk	int(11)	No		Vendor periodic eval ID FK
vdr_ev_id_fk	int(11)	No		Vendor standard eval ID FK

Vendors Table

Primary Key : vendor_id

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
vendor_id	int(11)	No		Vendor Code
name	varchar(255)	No		Vendor Name
address	mediumtext	No		Vendor Address
phone	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL	Phone
fax	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL	Fax
contact	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL	Vendor Contact Person
branch_serves	varchar(255)	No		Branch Code Serves by Vendor

APPENDIX B –STORIX PROJECT GANTT CHART

APPENDIX C – FORMS

1. ITS Request Form

ITS REQUEST FORM

- ^{0.1} New User Account ^{0.3} Modify Account
 ^{0.2} Delete User Account ^{0.4} Peripherals/Equipment Request Only

A. Account Information ^{A.A} Date: / / ^{A.B} Time:

^{A.1} Employee Name: _____

First Name Middle Name(s) Last/Family Name

^{A.2} Department: _____ ^{A.3} Status: _____

^{A.3.1} Permanent ^{A.3.2} Part-time/Contract

^{A.3.3} Probation ^{A.3.4} Intern/Temporary

^{A.4} Title: _____

^{A.5} Location: _____

B. Peripherals/Equipment Requested

^{B.1} Computer ^{B.2} Monitor ^{B.3} Printer ^{B.4} Scanner
 ^{B.5} Keyboard/Mouse ^{B.6} CD/CDRW ^{B.7} Modem ^{B.8}

C. Access Requested

^{C.1} Network ^{C.2} Intranet ^{C.3} ProCarS ^{C.4} Citrix/Faktur Pajak
 ^{C.5} Email ^{C.6} Internet ^{C.7} HAI*EUROP ^{C.8}

D. Details / Others

Requester's Name/Nama Pemohon:** _____ *Authorization/Otorisasi** _____

Date: _____ **Date:** _____

Tgl.: _____ **Tgl.:** _____

ITS USE ONLY		Notes:
File No.	/TRF/ /	
Checked		
Validated		
Date		

*: At least Coordinator Level **: Manager/Management Level

2. Request For Approval Form

Request for Approval

NO: 0277/RFA/JKT/0707
 Requestor IMAM MALIK
 Designation SUPERVISOR
 Date July 17, 2007

No.	Description	APPROVAL
1.	<p style="text-align: center;">Mainboard ASUS P5GC-MX</p> <p>Purpose: For IT Spare & Replacement for CGK</p> <p>Branches: JKT</p> <p>Requested Specifics: Mainboard ASUS P5GC-MX Include : - Hyper Trading LGA 775, 2xPCI, Intel Audio 945 8 x USB 2.0, LAN 10/100, Integrated VGA - Memory DDR2 2 GB PC 4400 - Processor Intel Pentium 4 3.0 Ghz Hypertrading FSB800</p> <p>Vendor Quotation: PT Osher Computer</p>	

3. Standard Vendor Evaluation

VENDOR P.O. EVALUATION FORM INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY DEPARTMENT

Date : _____
 Company Name : _____
 P.O. No. : _____

Criteria	Excellent	Good	Mediocre	Poor	Score
Punctuality & Accuracy of Quotation based on requirement					
Punctuality of Delivery					
Accuracy of Product/Service					
Quality of Product/Services					
Billing Accuracy					
Average					

Remarks

Evaluated By:

4. Periodic Vendor Evaluation

VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION FORM
 INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY DEPARTMENT

Evaluation Period : / - /
 Company Name : _____
 P.O. Evaluation :

P.O.	Grade	P.O.	Grade	P.O.	Grade
Sub Total		Sub Total		Sub Total	
Total					
Average					

Remarks

Maintain in AVL		Eliminate from AVL	
-----------------	--	--------------------	--

Date: / /

Evaluated By:

APPENDIX D – SOURCE CODE

1. config.inc.php

```
<?php
$host = 'localhost';
$user = 'erequest';
$password = 'erequest';
$db_use = 'storix';

$db = @mysql_connect($host, $user, $password);
@mysql_select_db($db_use, $db);
?>
```

2. functions.inc.php

```
<?php
require_once('constant.inc.php');

function source_header($id,$title) {
    $main_page_cat = "main";
    $main_page_pst = "left"; ?>
<html>
<head>
<title><?=$title?> - eRequest Portal <?=STORIX_VERSION?></title>
<script language="javascript" type="text/javascript"
src="./js/popup.js"></script>
<script language="javascript" type="text/javascript"
src="./js/date.js"></script>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
@import url('./css/style.css');
-->
</style>
</head>
<body leftmargin="0" topmargin="0" marginwidth="0" marginheight="0">
<table border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" width="100%" height="100%">
<tr><td colspan="2" height="60">
<?php if (!empty($_SESSION['ctRedirect'])) {
    session_unregister($_SESSION['ctRedirect']);
}
?>
    <table border="0" height="100%" width="100%">
        <tr>
            <td valign="top" align="left" width=100></td>
            <td valign="top" align="left">&nbsp;</td>
            <td valign="top" align="left"><br/>Hello,
<b><?=$_SESSION['username']?></b>
                <br /><a href="./logout.php" target="_top">Sign
Out</a>,
                    <a
href="javascript:openAbout()">About</a></td>
            <td valign="middle" height="60"></td>
            <td width="3"></td>
        </tr>
    </table>
</td></tr>
<tr><td colspan="2" height="10" bgcolor="#000066"></td></tr>
<tr><td width="160" valign="top" bgcolor="#6699cc">
    <table bgcolor="#ffffff" border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
width="160">
```



```
        }
        else {
            echo "";
        }
    }
}
}
//-----
function sub_menu($page_id_right, $category) {
    $position="right";?>
    <table border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0" width="165">
    <tr align="right"><td valign="middle" height="24" bgcolor="#ccccff"
>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr align="right"><td valign="middle" height="1" bgcolor="#6699cc"
></td></tr>
    <?nav_menu($page_id_right, $category, $position)?>
    </table>
<?php }
//-----
function source_footer() { ?>
    <tr height="20">
        <td bgcolor="#ccccff" width="5">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
        <td bgcolor="#ccccff">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;&copy; 2007 <a
href="javascript:openCredits()">S.T.O.R.I.X. Project</a></td>
        <td bgcolor="#ccccff" width="10">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
    </tbody>
    </table>
</td></tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>
<?php }
//-----
function chkSession(){
session_start();
    if (!isset ($_SESSION['auth_erequest']) || $_SESSION['auth_erequest'] ==
false) {
        $_SESSION['ctRedirect'] = $_SERVER['REQUEST_URI'];
        Header('Location:./login.php');
        exit();
    }
}
//-----
function vendor_list_selection(){
    $vendor_list_query ="SELECT vendors.vendor_id, vendors.name FROM vendors
ORDER BY vendors.name ASC;";
    $vendor_list_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_list_query); ?>
    <select name="vendor[]">
    <option value="-"-----</option>
<?php while($vendor_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($vendor_list_SQL)){?>
    <option
value="<?=$vendor_list_array[0]?>"><?ucwords($vendor_list_array[1])?></option>
<?php }
        echo "</select>";
    }
//-----
function item_list_selection(){
    $item_list_query ="SELECT id, name FROM request_items WHERE
req_type_id_fk = '2' ORDER BY name ASC;";
    $item_list_SQL = mysql_query($item_list_query); ?>
    <select name="items[]">
    <option value="-"-----</option>
<?php while($item_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($item_list_SQL)){?>
    <option
```

```
value="<?=$item_list_array[1]?>"><?=strtoupper($item_list_array[1])?></option>
<?php }
        echo "</select>";
    }
//-----
function paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$count_query) {

$count_SQL = mysql_query($count_query);
$numrows = mysql_num_rows($count_SQL);
$maxPage = ceil($numrows/$rowsPerPage);
$self = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF'];
$nav = '';

if ($maxPage == 1 || $maxPage == 0) {}

else {
    for($page = 1; $page <= $maxPage; $page++) {
        if ($page == $pageNum) {
            $nav .= " $page | ";
        }
        else {
            $nav .= " <a href=\"\$self?page=$page\">$page</a> | ";
        }
    }
    if ($pageNum > 1) {
        $page = $pageNum - 1;
        $prev = " <a href=\"\$self?page=$page\">Prev</a> | ";
        $first = " <a href=\"\$self?page=1\">First</a> | ";
    }
    else {
        $prev = '';
        $first = '';
    }
    if ($pageNum < $maxPage) {
        $page = $pageNum + 1;
        $next = " <a href=\"\$self?page=$page\">Next</a> | ";
        $last = " <a href=\"\$self?page=$maxPage\">Last</a> ";
    }
    else {
        $next = '';
        $last = '';
    }
    echo "<table border=\"0\" width=\"100%\">";
    echo "<tr><td align=\"left\">Page ".$pageNum." of ".$maxPage."</td>";
    echo "<td align=\"right\">".$first." ".$prev." ".$next."
    ".$last."</td></tr></table>";
}
//-----
?>
```

3. libbutton.inc.php

```
<?php
function approve_button() {
    echo "<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>";
    echo "<tr><td bgcolor=\"#6699cc\" height=\"24\" valign=\"middle\" >\n";
    echo " \t&nbsp;<input type=\"submit\" name=\"approve\" value=\"APPROVE\"
class=\"button\" />\n";
    echo " \t&nbsp;<input type=\"submit\" name=\"appr_all\" value=\"APPROVE
ALL\" class=\"button\" />\n";
    echo " \t&nbsp;<input type=\"submit\" name=\"reject_all\" value=\"REJECT
ALL\" class=\"button\" />\n";
    echo "</td></tr>\n";
}
}
```



```
</tr>
<?php
}
//-----
-
function file_update_button() {?>
<tr><td colspan="11" bgcolor="#6699cc" height="24" valign="middle">
    &nbsp;<input type="submit" name="update_file" class="button" value="    UPDATE
FILE    "/>
</td></tr>
<?php }
//-----
-
function back_button() { ?>
    <tr><td>[&nbsp;<a href="javascript:history.back(-1)">Back to the Previous
Page</a>&nbsp;<input type="submit" name="back" class="button" value="Back" />]
</td></tr>
<?php }
//-----
-
function submit_rfa() { ?>
<tr><td colspan="9" bgcolor="#6699cc" height="24" valign="middle">
    &nbsp;<input type="submit" class="button"
name="submit_rfa_temp" value="Submit RFA"/>
&nbsp;<input type="reset" class="button" value="Reset
RFA"/></td></tr>
<?php }
//-----
-
?>
```

4. login.php

```
<?php
session_start();
require('./inc/config.inc.php');

if (isset($_POST['submit'])) {
    $username = trim($_POST['username']);
    $password = md5(trim($_POST['password']));
    $login_query = "SELECT CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name) AS fullname,
branch.branch_id AS bid, user.username, user.id as uid, departments.name AS
department, departments.id AS did, CONCAT(manager.name, ' ', manager.given_name)
AS mgr_name, manager.id AS mid, user.level_id_fk AS user_level, branch.name AS
branches ";
    $login_query .= "FROM user LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
    $login_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
    $login_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id =
user.mgr_id_fk) ";
    $login_query .= "WHERE user.username = '$username' AND user.password =
'$password' ";
    $result = @mysql_query($login_query);
    if (mysql_num_rows($result) >= 1) {
        $row = mysql_fetch_array($result, MYSQL_ASSOC);
        $_SESSION['fullname'] = $row['fullname'];
        $_SESSION['bid'] = $row['bid'];
        $_SESSION['username'] = $row['username'];
        $_SESSION['uid'] = $row['uid'];
        $_SESSION['department'] = $row['department'];
        $_SESSION['did'] = $row['did'];
        $_SESSION['branch'] = $row['branches'];
        $_SESSION['mgr_name'] = $row['mgr_name'];
        $_SESSION['mid'] = $row['mid'];
        $_SESSION['level'] = $row['user_level'];
    }
}
```

```
$_SESSION['auth_erequest'] = true;
if (!empty($_SESSION['ctRedirect'])) {
    $redirPage = $_SESSION['ctRedirect'];
}
else {
    $redirPage = "./index.php";
}

$inTime = date('Y-m-d H:i:s');
$query = "INSERT INTO log_history VALUES
(NULL, '$_SESSION['uid'].', '$_SERVER['REMOTE_ADDR'].', '$_SESSION['uid'].', 'LOGIN
');";

mysql_query($query);
$serverHost = $_SERVER['HTTP_HOST'];
Header ("Location:http://$serverHost$redirPage");
exit();
}
else {
    $status = "<table class=yellowbox>";
    $status .= "<tr><td>Wrong Username or Password !</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table>";
}
}
else {
    $status="&nbsp;";
}
?>
<html>
<head>
<link rel=stylesheet type=text/css href=./css/style.css>
<title>Login Page</title>
<script language="javascript" type="text/javascript"
src=./js/popup.js"></script>
</head>
<body leftmargin="0" topmargin="0" marginwidth="0" marginheight="0">
<center>
<table border="0" width="100%" height="100%" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
<tr><td height=10%>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td height=15% align="center"><?=$status;?><br /><br />
<noscript>
<center>
<table class=yellowbox>
<tr><td>You must activate your
Javascript support on your browser <br>
because some of facilities in
this portal are using Javascript</td></tr>
</table>
</center>
</noscript></td></tr>
<tr><td height=60 align="left"><img src=./img/storixlogo.png"></td></tr>
<tr><td height=20 align="left">&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr bgcolor="#000066" height="7"><td colspan=2 valign="middle"
align="center"></td></tr>
<tr><td height="150" align="center" bgcolor="#d8d8d8">
<form action="<?=$_SERVER['PHP_SELF']?>" method=POST name="login">
<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="0"
width="300">
<tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td align="left"><b>USERNAME</b></td>
<td>:</td>
<td><input type=text name="username"
size="30"></td></tr>
<tr><td align=right height="5"></td></tr>
<tr><td align=left><b>PASSWORD</b></td>
```

```

                <td>:</td>
                <td><input name="password" type=password
size="30"></td></tr>
                <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td><input type="submit" name="submit"
class="button" value=" LOGIN ">&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="reset" class="button"
value=" RESET "></td></tr>
                <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>(Note : Javascript must be
enabled)</td></tr>
        </table><br>
        </form>
</td></tr>
<tr bgcolor="#000066" height="7">
    <td colspan=2 valign="middle" align="center"></td></tr>
<tr><td height="15%" align="center" valign="top"><br />
    Copyright&nbsp;&copy; 2007 <a
href="javascript:openCredits()">S.T.O.R.I.X. Project</a></td></tr>
<tr><td height=45%>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</center>
</body>
</html>
```

5. index.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$count_pending_rfa_query = "SELECT * FROM rfa WHERE rfa.status = 'PENDING' ";
$count_pending_rfa_SQL = mysql_query($count_pending_rfa_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_pending_rfa = mysql_num_rows($count_pending_rfa_SQL);

$count_req_access_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_access_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_access_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_access_query .= "WHERE request_type.id = '1' AND request.user_id_fk =
'".$_SESSION['uid']."'";
$count_req_access_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_access_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_access = mysql_num_rows($count_req_access_SQL);

$count_req_items_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_items_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_items_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_items_query .= "WHERE request_type.id = '2' AND request.user_id_fk =
'".$_SESSION['uid']."'";
$count_req_items_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_items_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_items = mysql_num_rows($count_req_items_SQL);
```

```
$count_req_appr_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_appr_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_appr_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_appr_query .= "WHERE request_details.status = 'RFA-Approved' AND
request.user_id_fk = '". $SESSION['uid'] ."' ";
$count_req_appr_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_appr_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_appr = mysql_num_rows($count_req_appr_SQL);

$count_req_rfa_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_rfa_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_rfa_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_rfa_query .= "WHERE request_details.status = 'rfa' AND
request.user_id_fk = '". $SESSION['uid'] ."' ";
$count_req_rfa_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_rfa_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_rfa = mysql_num_rows($count_req_rfa_SQL);

$count_req_auth_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_auth_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_auth_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_auth_query .= "WHERE request_details.status = 'accepted' AND
request.user_id_fk = '". $SESSION['uid'] ."' ";
$count_req_auth_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_auth_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_auth = mysql_num_rows($count_req_auth_SQL);

$count_req_pdg_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_pdg_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_pdg_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_pdg_query .= "WHERE request_details.status = 'pending' AND
request.user_id_fk = '". $SESSION['uid'] ."' ";
$count_req_pdg_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_pdg_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_pdg = mysql_num_rows($count_req_pdg_SQL);

$count_req_rjc_query = "SELECT * ";
$count_req_rjc_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN request_details ON
(request_details.req_id_fk = request.id) LEFT JOIN request_items ON
(request_items.id = request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$count_req_rjc_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_type ON (request_type.id =
request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";
$count_req_rjc_query .= "WHERE request_details.status = 'rejected' AND
request.user_id_fk = '". $SESSION['uid'] ."' ";
$count_req_rjc_SQL = mysql_query($count_req_rjc_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_req_rjc = mysql_num_rows($count_req_rjc_SQL);

$count_acc_item_query = "SELECT * FROM request_details WHERE status
='ACCEPTED' ";
$count_acc_item_SQL = mysql_query($count_acc_item_query) or die
("".mysql_error());
$count_acc_item = mysql_num_rows($count_acc_item_SQL);
```



```
$req_list_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id =
request.user_id_fk) ";
$req_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$req_list_query .= "WHERE request.user_id_fk = '". $_SESSION['uid']. "' ";
$req_list_query .= "ORDER BY request.req_date DESC, request.req_time DESC";
$req_list_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";

$req_list_and_limit = $req_list_query." ".$req_list_limit_query;
$req_list_SQL = mysql_query($req_list_and_limit);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?page=".$pageNum;

$status = "";

if (isset($_GET['del_id'])){
    $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);

    $chk_del_stat_q = "SELECT request.user_id_fk, request.req_status FROM
request WHERE request.id = '$did.'";
    $chk_del_stat_SQL = mysql_query($chk_del_stat_q);
    $chk_del_stat_array = mysql_fetch_array($chk_del_stat_SQL);

    if ($chk_del_stat_array[0] == $_SESSION['uid'] AND $chk_del_stat_array[1]
== "PENDING") {
        $select_req_file_code_query = "SELECT request.file_id_fk FROM
request WHERE id = '$did.'";
        $select_req_file_code_SQL =
mysql_query($select_req_file_code_query);

        while($select_req_file_code_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_file_code_SQL)) {
            $delete_req_file_query = "DELETE FROM file WHERE file.id =
'".$select_req_file_code_array[0].'";
            mysql_query($delete_req_file_query);
        }

        $delete_req_query = "DELETE FROM request ";
        $delete_req_query .= "WHERE id = '$did.'";
        mysql_query($delete_req_query);

        $delete_req_det_query = "DELETE FROM request_details ";
        $delete_req_det_query .= "WHERE req_id_fk = '$did.'";
        mysql_query($delete_req_det_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    } else {
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>You don't have privilege to delete the request
data or the data status doesn't allowed to be deleted</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
    }
}

$page_title = "Request Page";
$page_id = "2";
$page_id_right = "16";
$category_page = "request";
?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
<!--//>
<form method="POST" action="">
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr><td><h2>REQUEST BOX</h2></td></tr>
```

```

        <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td><?=$status?></td></tr>

        <tr><td><?=$paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$req_list_query)?></td></tr>
        <tr><td>
            <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
                <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
                    <tr class="listview" valign="middle">
                        <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO.</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>ID</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>FILE NO.</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>REQUESTER</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>REQ. TYPE</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>REQ. DATE</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>STATUS</b>&nbsp;</td>
                        <td colspan="3" align="center">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                    <?php
                        if (mysql_num_rows($req_list_SQL) >= 1) {
                            ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
                            while($data = mysql_fetch_array($req_list_SQL)){
                                $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
                                <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
                                valign="top">
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[0]?></td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[1]?></td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[2]?></td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[3]?></td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[4]?>&nbsp;<?=$data[5]?></td>
                                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$data[6]?></td>
                                    <td align="center" width="25"><a href="./req_details.php?id=<?=$data[0]?>"></a></td>
                                    <td align="center" width="25"><a href="javascript:openPrint('./print_req.php?id=<?=$data[0]?>', 'Print Request');"></a></td>
                                    <td align="center" width="25">
                                        <?php if ($data[6] == "PENDING") { ?>
                                        <a href="<?=$this_page?>" onclick="return confirmDel(this, 'Request ', '<?=$data[0]?>')"></a>
                                        <?php } else {?><?php } ?>
                                    </td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php $count++;
                                }
                            } else {?>
                                <tr><td colspan="9" align="center" bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /></td></tr>
                                <?>
                            ?>
                        </table></div></td></tr>

        <tr><td><?=$paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$req_list_query)?></td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table>

```

```

</form>

<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-->

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                            </tr>
                        </tbody>
                    </table>
                </td>
            <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
        </tr>
    <?php source_footer()?>
    
```

7. req_its_form.php

```

<?php
require_once('../inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('../inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('../inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$status = "&nbsp;";

if(isset($_POST['subReq'])) {
    $req_type_txt = (isset($_POST['req_type_radio']) !=
    "")?strtolower(trim($_POST['req_type_radio'])):"";
    $file_id = "XXXX/ITRF/" . $_SESSION['bid'] . "/" . date('my');
    $date = $_POST['date'];
    $time = date('H:i:s');
    $emp_name = (isset($_POST['employee']) !=
    "")?strtolower(trim($_POST['employee'])):"";
    $title = (isset($_POST['title']) != "")?trim($_POST['title']):"";
    $status = (isset($_POST['emp_status']) !=
    "")?trim($_POST['emp_status']):"";
    $req_details = trim($_POST['req_details']);
    $req_content_array =
    (isset($_POST['req_content_items']))?$_POST['req_content_items']:"";

    if (!empty($req_content_array)) {
        $insert_file_req_query = "INSERT INTO file VALUES (NULL,'" . $file_id . "',
        '" . $date . "', ' ', ' ', ' ');";
        mysql_query($insert_file_req_query);
        $file_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();

        $req_input_query = "INSERT INTO request ";
        $req_input_query .= "VALUES
        (NULL, '$file_id_fk', '" . $_SESSION['uid'] . "', '$req_type_txt', '$date', '$time', '$emp
        p_name', '" . $_SESSION['bid'] . "', '" . $_SESSION['did'] . "', '" . $_SESSION['mid'] . "', '$
        title', '$status', '$req_details', 'PENDING', '');"
        mysql_query($req_input_query);

        $req_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();

        foreach($req_content_array as $req_content_details) {
            $req_details_input_query = "INSERT INTO request_details VALUES
            (NULL, '$req_id_fk', '$req_content_details', 'PENDING');"
            mysql_query($req_details_input_query);
        }
        header("location:./req.php");
    } else {
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>You can't create an empty request !</td></tr>";
    }
}
    
```



```
cellspacing="1">
    <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="1"
    <tr><td>REQUESTER'S NAME </td>
        <td>AUTHORIZATION</td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="2">&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td><b><?=ucwords($_SESSION['fullname'])?></b></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="2">&nbsp;</td></tr>

    <tr><td>DATE/TGL: &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<b><?=date('d.m.y')?></b></td>
        <td>DATE/TGL: &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
<?=req_its_button();?>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</form>
<?php
} else { ?>
<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
<tr><td><h2>REQUEST FORM</h2></td></tr>
<tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
<tr><td><?=$status?></td></tr>
<tr><td>
    <table>
        <tr><td>
            <fieldset><legend>REQUEST TYPE</legend>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="0">
                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
            </table>
        </td>
    </tr>
</table>
$req_type_query = "SELECT * FROM request_type";
$req_type_SQL = mysql_query($req_type_query);

while($reqTypeArray = mysql_fetch_array($req_type_SQL)) {?>
    <tr><td><input type="radio" name="req_type"
value="<?=$reqTypeArray[0]?>"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=strtoupper($reqTypeArray[1])?></td>
</tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</tr>
</td></tr>
</table></td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td><input type="submit" class="button" name="submit" value="NEXT
>>"></td></tr>
</table>
</form>
<?php } ?>

</-----CONTENT-END----->
</tr>
<td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
<td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
```

```
<?php source_footer()??>
```

8. req_details.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$req_id = $_GET['id'];

$display_request_query = "SELECT request.id, file.code, request.req_type,
request.req_date, request.employee_name, departments.name, request.title,
branch.name, request.status, request.req_details, CONCAT(requester.name,'
',requester.given_name) AS fullname, CONCAT(manager.name,'
',manager.given_name) AS mgr_name, request.auth_date, file.date,
CONCAT(chk.name,' ',chk.given_name) AS chkname, CONCAT(val.name,'
',val.given_name) AS valname, file.notes ";
$display_request_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN user AS requester ON
(requester.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
request.dept_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
request.branch_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id =
request.mgr_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS chk ON (chk.id = file.checked) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS val ON (val.id = file.validated) ";
$display_request_query .= "WHERE request.id = '". $req_id. "'";
$display_request_SQL = @mysql_query($display_request_query) ;
$display_request_array = @mysql_fetch_array($display_request_SQL);

$display_request_details_query = "SELECT request_details.id,
request_items.name, request_details.status ";
$display_request_details_query .= "FROM request_details INNER JOIN request_items
ON (request_details.req_item_id_fk = request_items.id) ";
$display_request_details_query .= "WHERE request_details.req_id_fk =
'". $req_id. "'";
$display_request_details_SQL = @mysql_query($display_request_details_query);

$page_title="Request Details Page";
$page_id = "2";
$page_id_right = "16";
$category_page = "request";

?>
<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title)?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
<!--//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
  <tr><td><h2>REQUEST FORM DETAILS</h2></td></tr>
  <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
  <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
  <tr><td><?=<back_button()??></td></tr>
  <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
  <tr><td>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="0" width="400">
      <tr><td><b>ID :</b>#?(($display_request_array[0])?strtoupper($display_request_array[0]):"&nbsp;
&nbsp; -"?></td></tr>
      <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table>
  </td></tr>
</table>
```



```
<tr><td>
    <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="1"
cellspacing="1">
        <tr><td><b>REQUESTER'S NAME:</b></td>
            <td><b>AUTHORIZATION:</b></td></tr>
        <tr><td colspan="2">&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td><?=ucwords($display_request_array[10])?></td>
            <td><?=ucwords($display_request_array[11])?></td></tr>
        <tr><td colspan="2">&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td><b>DATE/TGL:</b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$display_request_array[3]?></td>
            <td><b>DATE/TGL:</b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=( $display_request_array[12] != "0000-00-00" )?$display_request_array[12]:"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td></tr>
    </table>
</td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td>
    <fieldset><legend>ITS USE ONLY</legend>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1">
        <tr><td align="left"><b>FILE NO</b></td>
            <td align="left">:</td>
        <td><?=( $display_request_array[1] )?ucwords($display_request_array[1]):"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td>
            <td align="left" rowspan="4">&nbsp;</td>
            <td rowspan="4" align="left"
valign="top"><b>NOTES</b>:<br/>
                <?=( $display_request_array[16] )?nl2br($display_request_array[16]):"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td></tr>
                <tr><td align="left"><b>CHECKED</b></td>
                    <td align="left">:</td>
                <td><?=( $display_request_array[1] )?ucwords($display_request_array[14]):"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td></tr>
                <tr><td align="left"><b>VALIDATED</b></td>
                    <td align="left">:</td>
                <td><?=( $display_request_array[1] )?ucwords($display_request_array[15]):"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td></tr>
                <tr><td align="left"><b>DATE</b></td>
                    <td align="left">:</td>
                <td><?=( $display_request_array[13] )?$display_request_array[13]:"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;-";?></td></tr>
    </table></fieldset>
</td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</td></tr></table>
</-----CONTENT-END----->
</>

</td>
    <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
```

```
</tr>  
<?php source_footer()?>
```

9. auth_details.php

```
<?php  
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');  
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');  
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');  
chkSession();  
  
$req_id = $_GET['id'];  
  
$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?id=".$req_id;  
  
if(isset($_POST['authorized'])) {  
    $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];  
    foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {  
        $upd_det_stat = $_POST['req_det_stat'][$row];  
        $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status =  
'$upd_det_stat' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id';";  
        mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);  
    }  
    $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status = 'AUTHORIZED',  
auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id = '$req_id_fk';";  
    mysql_query($upd_req_query);  
  
    header("location:$this_page");  
}  
  
elseif(isset($_POST['auth_all'])) {  
    $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];  
    foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {  
        $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status =  
'ACCEPTED' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id';";  
        mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);  
    }  
    $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status = 'AUTHORIZED',  
auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id = '$req_id_fk';";  
    mysql_query($upd_req_query);  
  
    header("location:$this_page");  
}  
  
elseif(isset($_POST['reject_all'])) {  
    $req_id_fk = $_POST['req_id_fk'];  
    foreach ($_POST['req_det_id'] as $row => $upd_req_id) {  
        $upd_req_det_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status =  
'REJECTED' WHERE id = '$upd_req_id';";  
        mysql_query($upd_req_det_query);  
    }  
    $upd_req_query = "UPDATE request SET req_status = 'REJECTED',  
auth_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." WHERE id = '$req_id_fk';";  
    mysql_query($upd_req_query);  
  
    header("location:$this_page");  
}  
  
function authorize_status() {  
    $approval_status = array("ACCEPTED", "REJECTED");  
    echo "<select name = \"req_det_stat[]\">";  
    foreach($approval_status as $status) {
```

```
        echo "<option value = \"\$status\"> \$status</option>";
    }
    echo "</select>";
}

$display_request_query = "SELECT request.id, file.code, request.req_type,
request.req_date, request.employee_name, departments.name, request.title,
branch.name, request.status, request.req_details, CONCAT(requester.name, '
', requester.given_name) AS fullname, CONCAT(manager.name, '
', manager.given_name) AS mgr_name, request.auth_date, file.date,
CONCAT(chk.name, ' ', chk.given_name) AS chkname, CONCAT(val.name, '
', val.given_name) AS valname, file.notes, request.req_status ";
$display_request_query .= "FROM request LEFT JOIN user AS requester ON
(requester.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
request.dept_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
request.branch_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id =
request.mgr_id_fk) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS chk ON (chk.id = file.checked) ";
$display_request_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS val ON (val.id = file.validated) ";
$display_request_query .= "WHERE request.id = '$req_id.'";
$display_request_SQL = @mysql_query($display_request_query);
$display_request_array = mysql_fetch_array($display_request_SQL);

$display_request_details_query = "SELECT request_details.id,
request_items.name, request_details.status ";
$display_request_details_query .= "FROM request_details INNER JOIN request_items
ON (request_details.req_item_id_fk = request_items.id) ";
$display_request_details_query .= "WHERE request_details.req_id_fk =
'$req_id.'";
$display_request_details_SQL = @mysql_query($display_request_details_query);

$page_title = "Authorization Details Page";
$page_id = "3";

?>
<?php source_header($page_id, $page_title)?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
<!--//>
<form method="POST" action="">
<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>AUTHORIZATION FORM DETAILS</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td><input type="hidden" name="req_id_fk"
value="<?=$display_request_array[0]?>"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>[&nbsp;<a href="./authorize.php">Back to the Authorization
Page</a>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="0" width="400">
            <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
            <tr><td><b>ID :
</b>#<?=$display_request_array[0]?>ucwords($display_request_array[0]): "&nbsp;&nbsp;
-"?></td></tr>
            <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
            <tr><td>
                <fieldset><legend>TYPE</legend>
                <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="1"
cellspacing="0">
```



```

        <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="1"
cellspacing="1">
        <tr><td><b>REQUESTER'S NAME:</b></td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td><b>AUTHORIZATION:</b></td></tr>
        <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td><?=ucwords($display_request_array[10])?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td><?=ucwords($display_request_array[11])?></td></tr>
        <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td><b>DATE/TGL:</b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$display_request_array[3]?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td><b>DATE/TGL:</b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=( $display_request_array[12] != "0000-
00-00" )?$display_request_array[12]:"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp; -";?></td></tr>
        </table>
        </td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <?=( $display_request_array[17]=="PENDING" )?auth_button():" ";?>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td>
        <fieldset><legend>ITS USE ONLY</legend>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1">
            <tr><td align="left"><b>FILE NO</b></td>
                <td align="left">:</td>
            <tr><td align="left"><b>CHECKED</b></td>
                <td align="left">:</td>
            <tr><td align="left"><b>VALIDATED</b></td>
                <td align="left">:</td>
            <tr><td align="left"><b>DATE</b></td>
                <td align="left">:</td>
            <tr><td align="left"><?=( $display_request_array[13] )?$display_request_array[13]:"&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp; -
";?></td></tr>
        </table></fieldset>
        </td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td>[&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<a href="./authorize.php">Back to the Authorization
Page</a>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;]</td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table>
</td></tr></table>
</form>
</-----CONTENT-END----->
</>

        </td>
        <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>

```

```
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
<td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
```

10. rfa_create_form.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 10;
$pageNum = 1;
$branch_opt = "";

if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

//Tampilkan daftar request item yang accepted
$req_det_list_query = "SELECT request_details.id, request.id, file.code,
branch.branch_id, departments.name as dept, CONCAT(user.name, '
',user.given_name) AS fullname, request_items.name as items,
request_details.status ";
$req_det_list_query .= "FROM request ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_details ON (request_details.req_id_fk
= request.id) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_items ON (request_items.id =
request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "WHERE request_items.req_type_id_fk = '2' AND
request_details.status = 'ACCEPTED' ";

//Tampilkan daftar sesuai branchnya
if(isset($_POST['pick_branch'])){
    $branch_opt = $_POST['branch'];
    if($branch_opt != "ALL") {$req_det_list_query .= "AND request.branch_id_fk
= '". $branch_opt. "'"; }
    else { $req_det_list_query .= ""; }
} else { $req_det_list_query .= ""; }

$req_det_list_SQL = mysql_query($req_det_list_query);

$branch_list_query = "SELECT branch.branch_id, branch.name FROM branch;";
$branch_list_SQL = mysql_query($branch_list_query);

$vendor_list_query = "SELECT vendors.vendor_id, vendors.name FROM vendors ORDER
BY vendors.name ASC;";
$vendor_list_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_list_query);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?page=".$pageNum;

if (isset($_GET['del_id'])){
    $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
```

```
$select_req_det_stat_query ="SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM rfa_details
WHERE rfa_id_fk='".$did."'";
$select_req_det_stat_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_stat_query);

while($select_req_det_stat_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_stat_SQL)){
    $update_req_det_stat_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status =
'ACCEPTED' WHERE id = '".$select_req_det_stat_array[0].'";
    mysql_query($update_req_det_stat_query);
    echo $select_req_det_stat_array[0];
}

$delete_rfa_query = "DELETE FROM rfa ";
$delete_rfa_query .= "WHERE id = '".$did."'";
mysql_query($delete_rfa_query);

$delete_rfa_det_query = "DELETE FROM rfa_details ";
$delete_rfa_det_query .= "WHERE rfa_id_fk = '".$did."'";
mysql_query($delete_rfa_det_query);

header("location:$this_page");
exit();
}

if(isset($_POST['submit_rfa_temp'])) {
    $designation = trim($_POST['designation']);
    $branch = trim($_POST['rfa_branch']);
    $file_id = trim($_POST['file_id']);
    $date = trim($_POST['date']);
    $req_to_rfa_det_id = $_POST['req_detail_id'];

    if (!in_array("-", $_POST['vendor'])) {
        $insert_file_rfa_query = "INSERT INTO file VALUES
(NULL, '".$file_id."', '".$date.',',',',',');";
        mysql_query($insert_file_rfa_query);

        $file_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
        $insert_rfa_query = "INSERT INTO rfa VALUES
(NULL, '".$file_id_fk.', '$_SESSION['uid'].', '$branch', '$designation', '$date',
',',',', 'PENDING');";
        @mysql_query($insert_rfa_query);

        $rfa_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();

        foreach($req_to_rfa_det_id as $key_rfa_det_id =>
$value_rfa_det_id) {
            $specific_note = $_POST['specific_note'][$key_rfa_det_id];
            $purpose = $_POST['purpose'][$key_rfa_det_id];
            $vendor_id_fk = $_POST['vendor'][$key_rfa_det_id];
            $item_name_info =
$_POST['rfa_temp_item_name'][$key_rfa_det_id];
            $insert_rfa_det_query = "INSERT INTO rfa_details VALUES
(NULL, '$rfa_id_fk', '$value_rfa_det_id', '$item_name_info', '$purpose', '$specific_
note', '$vendor_id_fk', 'PENDING');";
            @mysql_query($insert_rfa_det_query);

            $update_req_details_to_rfa_query = "UPDATE request_details
SET status = 'RFA-PENDING' WHERE id = '$value_rfa_det_id' ";
            @mysql_query($update_req_details_to_rfa_query);
        }
        header("location:./rfa.php");
    } else {
        echo "<table border=\"0\">";
        echo "<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>";
        echo back_button();
        echo "<tr><td>";
    }
}
```



```

    }
}
else { ?>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>REQUEST FOR APPROVAL BOX</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>
        <form method="POST" action="<?=$_SERVER['PHP_SELF']?>">
            RFA for Branch :
            <select name="branch">
                <option value="ALL" <?=$selected?>>ALL</option>
                <option >-----</option>

<?php while($branch_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($branch_list_SQL)){
    $selected = ($branch_opt == $branch_list_array[0])?"SELECTED":"";
?>
    <option value="<?=$branch_list_array[0]?>"
<?=$selected?>><?ucwords($branch_list_array[1])?></option>
<? } ?>

        </select>
        &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="submit" class="button" name="pick_branch"
value="    OK    " />
    </form></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>
        <form method="POST" action="">
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) {
                create_rfa_button();
            } else { ?><?php } ?>
            <tr class="listview" align="left" valign="middle">
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) { ?>
                    <td width="20"><input type="hidden"
name="rfa_branch_id" value="<?=$branch_opt?>"></td>
<?php } else { ?><?php } ?>
                    <td width="25"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&NO.</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&FILE NO.</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&BRANCH</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&DEPARTMENT</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&REQUESTER</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&ITEM</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&STATUS</b></td>
                    <?php
                    if (mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) {
                        $count = 1;
                        while($req_det_list_array = mysql_fetch_array
($req_det_list_SQL)){
                            $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
                            <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left" >
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) { ?>
                                    <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&<input type="checkbox"
name="req_id[]" value="<?=$req_det_list_array[0]?>"></td>
<?php } else { ?><?php } ?>
                                    <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&<?=$count?>.</td>
                                    <td><a
href="./req_details.php?id=<?=$req_det_list_array[1]?>">
                                        &nbsp;&nbsp;&<?=$req_det_list_array[2]?></a></td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&<?=$req_det_list_array[3]?></td>

```

```

                                <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[4]?></td>

                                <td>&nbsp;<?ucwords($req_det_list_array[5])?></td>
                                <td>&nbsp;<input type="hidden"
name="items_name[]"
value="<?=$req_det_list_array[6]?>"><?ucwords($req_det_list_array[6])?></td>
                                <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[7]?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php $count++;
                                }
                                } else {?>
                                <tr><td colspan="7" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
                                <?}?>
                                </table></div>
                                </form>
                                </td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
<?php } ?>
</-----CONTENT-END----->
-//>

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                                </tr>
                                </tbody>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
                                </tr>
<?php source_footer()?>

```

11. rfa_manual.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

//Tampilin daftar request item yang accepted
$req_det_list_query ="SELECT request_details.id, request.id,
request.file_id_fk, branch.branch_id, departments.name as dept,
CONCAT(user.name,' ',user.given_name) AS fullname, request_items.name as items,
request_details.status ";
$req_det_list_query .="FROM request ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN request_details ON (request_details.req_id_fk
= request.id) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN request_items ON (request_items.id =
request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="WHERE request_items.req_type_id_fk = '2' AND
request_details.status = 'ACCEPTED' ";

//Tampilin daftar sesuai branchnya
if(isset($_POST['pick_branch'])){
    $branch_opt=$_POST['branch'];
}

```

```
        if($branch_opt != "ALL") {$req_det_list_query .= "AND request.branch_id_fk
= '". $branch_opt. "'"; }
        else { $req_det_list_query .=""; }
    } else { $req_det_list_query .=""; }

$req_det_list_SQL = mysql_query($req_det_list_query);

$branch_list_query = "SELECT branch.branch_id, branch.name FROM branch;";
$branch_list_SQL = mysql_query($branch_list_query);

$vendor_list_query = "SELECT vendors.vendor_id, vendors.name FROM vendors ORDER
BY vendors.name ASC;";
$vendor_list_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_list_query);

$status = "&nbsp;";

if(isset($_POST['submit_rfa_temp'])) {
    $designation = trim($_POST['designation']);
    $branch = trim($_POST['rfa_branch']);
    $file_id = trim($_POST['file_id']);
    $date = trim($_POST['date']);
    $items = $_POST['items'];

    if (!in_array("-", $_POST['vendor']) AND !in_array("-", $_POST['items'])) {
        $insert_file_rfa_query = "INSERT INTO file VALUES
(NULL, '$file_id', '$date', '', '', '');";
        mysql_query($insert_file_rfa_query);

        $file_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
        $insert_rfa_query = "INSERT INTO rfa VALUES
(NULL, '$file_id_fk', '$SESSION[uid]', '$branch', '$designation', '$date',
'', '', 'PENDING');";
        mysql_query($insert_rfa_query);

        $rfa_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
        foreach($items as $key_items => $value_items) {
            $specific_note = $_POST['specific_note'][$key_items];
            $purpose = $_POST['purpose'][$key_items];
            $vendor_id_fk = $_POST['vendor'][$key_items];

            $insert_rfa_det_query = "INSERT INTO rfa_details VALUES
(NULL, '$rfa_id_fk', '$value_items', '$purpose', '$specific_note', '$vendor_id_fk',
'PENDING');";
            mysql_query($insert_rfa_det_query);
        }
        header("location:../rfa.php");
    } else {
        $status = "<table border=\"0\">";
        $status .= "<tr><td>";
        $status .= "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>Missing Information! could not create RFA,
Press back button to repeat input</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
        $status .= "</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table>";
    }
}

$page_title="Manual RFA Page";
$page_id = "4";
$page_id_right = "20";
$category_page = "rfa";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>
```



```
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rfa_id = $_GET['id'];

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?id=".$rfa_id;

if(isset($_POST['approve'])){
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key => $rfa_det_id_value)
    {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat = $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET status =
'$upd_rfa_det_stat' WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);

        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM rfa_details
WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);

        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1) {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = 'RFA-".$upd_rfa_det_stat."' WHERE id =
'".$select_req_det_id_array[0]."'";
                mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
            }
        }
        $upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'APPROVED', appr_id_fk =
'".$_SESSION['uid']."', appr_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." ' WHERE id =
'$rfa_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }
}

elseif(isset($_POST['appr_all'])){
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key => $rfa_det_id_value)
    {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat = $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET status = 'APPROVED'
WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);

        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM rfa_details
WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);

        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1) {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = 'RFA-APPROVED' WHERE id = '".$select_req_det_id_array[0]."'";
                mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
            }
        }
        $upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'APPROVED', appr_id_fk =
'".$_SESSION['uid']."', appr_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." ' WHERE id =
'$rfa_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }
}
```

```
elseif(isset($_POST['reject_all'])){
    $rfa_id_fk = $_POST['rfa_id_fk'];
    foreach ($_POST['rfa_det_id_fk'] as $rfa_det_id_key => $rfa_det_id_value)
    {
        $upd_rfa_det_stat = $_POST['rfa_det_status'][$rfa_det_id_key];
        $upd_rfa_det_query = "UPDATE rfa_details SET status = 'REJECTED'
WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_det_query);

        $select_req_det_id_q = "SELECT req_details_id_fk FROM rfa_details
WHERE id = '$rfa_det_id_value'";
        $select_req_det_id_SQL = mysql_query($select_req_det_id_q);

        if (mysql_num_rows($select_req_det_id_SQL) >= 1) {
            while($select_req_det_id_array =
mysql_fetch_array($select_req_det_id_SQL)) {
                $upd_req_det_rfa_q = "UPDATE request_details SET
status = 'RFA-REJECTED' WHERE id = '". $select_req_det_id_array[0]."'";
                mysql_query($upd_req_det_rfa_q);
            }
        }

        $upd_rfa_query = "UPDATE rfa SET status = 'REJECTED', appr_id_fk =
'".$_SESSION['uid']."' , appr_date = '".date('Y-m-d')." ' WHERE id =
'$rfa_id_fk'";
        mysql_query($upd_rfa_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }

    $rfa_info_query = "SELECT rfa.id, file.code, CONCAT(user.name, '
',user.given_name) AS fullname, branch.branch_id, rfa.designation, rfa.date,
CONCAT(chk.name, ' ',chk.given_name) AS chkname, CONCAT(val.name, '
',val.given_name) AS valname, file.date, file.notes, rfa.status ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "FROM rfa LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = rfa.user_id_fk) ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = rfa.file_id_fk) ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS chk ON (chk.id = file.checked) ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS val ON (val.id = file.validated) ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id = rfa.branch_id_fk) ";
    $rfa_info_query .= "WHERE rfa.id = '$rfa_id' ";
    $rfa_info_SQL = mysql_query($rfa_info_query);
    $rfa_info_array = mysql_fetch_array($rfa_info_SQL);

    $rfa_det_info_query = "SELECT rfa_details.id, rfa_details.item_name,
rfa_details.purpose, rfa_details.spec_notes, vendors.name, rfa_details.status
";
    $rfa_det_info_query .= "FROM rfa_details LEFT JOIN vendors ON
(vendors.vendor_id = rfa_details.vendor_id_fk) ";
    $rfa_det_info_query .= "WHERE rfa_details.rfa_id_fk = '$rfa_id' ";
    $rfa_det_info_SQL = mysql_query($rfa_det_info_query);

    function approval_status() {
        $approval_status = array("APPROVED", "REJECTED");
        $approval_name = array("APPROVE", "REJECT");
        echo "<select name = \"rfa_det_status[]\">\n";
        foreach($approval_status as $key => $status) {
            $name = $approval_name[$key];
            echo "\t<option value = \"\$status\">$name</option>\n";
        }
        echo "</select>\n";
    }

    $page_title = "Request for Approval Page";
    $page_id = "5";
    ?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>
```



```
<tr
valign="top"><td><?=( $rfa_det_info_array[2] )?nl2br( $rfa_det_info_array[2] ): "&nb
sp; - "?></td>
    <td><?ucwords( $rfa_info_array[3] )?></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="2" ><b>REQ.
SPECIFICS:</b></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="2"
><?=( $rfa_det_info_array[3] )?nl2br( $rfa_det_info_array[3] ): "&nbsp; -
"?></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="2"><b>VENDOR
QUOTATION:</b></td></tr>
    <tr><td
colspan="2"><?=( $rfa_det_info_array[4] )? $rfa_det_info_array[4] : "&nbsp; -
"?></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="4"><input
type="hidden" name="rfa_det_id_fk[]"
value="<?=$rfa_det_info_array[0]?>"></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="4" bgcolor="#ccccff"
height="1"></td></tr>
    <tr><td colspan="4">&nbsp;</td></tr>
    </table>
</td></tr>
<?php
$count++;
} ?>
    <tr><td>
    <fieldset><legend>ITS USE ONLY</legend>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1">
        <tr><td align="left"><b>FILE NO</b></td>
        <td align="left">:</td>
        <td><?=( $rfa_info_array[1] )?ucwords( $rfa_info_array[1] ): "&nbsp; -
";?></td>
        <td align="left" rowspan="4">&nbsp;</td>
        <td rowspan="4" align="left"
valign="top"><b>NOTES</b>:<br/>
        <?=( $rfa_info_array[9] )?nl2br( $rfa_info_array[9] ): "&nbsp; - ";?></td></tr>
        <tr><td align="left"><b>CHECKED</b></td>
        <td align="left">:</td>
        <td><?=( $rfa_info_array[6] )?ucwords( $rfa_info_array[6] ): "&nbsp; -
";?></td></tr>
        <tr><td align="left"><b>VALIDATED</b></td>
        <td align="left">:</td>
        <td><?=( $rfa_info_array[7] )?ucwords( $rfa_info_array[7] ): "&nbsp; -
";?></td></tr>
        <tr><td align="left"><b>DATE</b></td>
        <td align="left">:</td>
        <td><b><?=( $rfa_info_array[8] )? $rfa_info_array[8] : "&nbsp; -
";?></b></td></tr>
    </table></fieldset>
    </td></tr>
    </table>
    <td><?=( $rfa_info_array[10] == "PENDING" )?approve_button(): "&nbsp; ";?>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>[&nbsp;<a href="./approve.php">Back to the Approval
Page</a>&nbsp;]</td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</form>
```

```

</-----CONTENT-END----->
---//>
        </td>
                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table>
</td>
        <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"></td></tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
    
```

13. req_access.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();
$rowsPerPage = 10;
$pageNum = 1;
if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;
$req_det_list_query = "SELECT request_details.id, request.id, file.code,
branch.branch_id, departments.name as dept, CONCAT(user.name, '
',user.given_name) AS fullname, request_items.name as items,
request_details.status ";
$req_det_list_query .= "FROM request ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_details ON (request_details.req_id_fk
= request.id) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN request_items ON (request_items.id =
request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .= "WHERE request_items.req_type_id_fk = '1' ";
$req_det_list_query .= "ORDER BY request.req_date DESC, request.req_time DESC";
$req_det_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";
$req_det_list_limit_query = $req_det_list_query." ".$req_det_limit_query;
$req_det_list_SQL = mysql_query($req_det_list_limit_query);
$page_title="Requested Access Page";
$page_id="6";
$page_id_right = "21";
$category_page = "access";
?>
<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>
</-----CONTENT-START----->
---//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>LIST OF REQUESTED ACCESS</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td
><?php paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$req_det_list_query) ?></td></tr>
    <tr><td>
        <form method="POST" action="">
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
                <tr class="listview" align="left" valign="middle">
                    <td width="25"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;NO.</b></td>
                    <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;FILE NO.</b></td>
    
```

```

        <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;BRANCH</b></td>
        <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;DEPARTMENT</b></td>
        <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;REQUESTER</b></td>
        <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;ACCESS</b></td>
        <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;STATUS</b></td>
        <td width="*" align="center"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;CMD</b></td>
<?php if (mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) {
    ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
    while($req_det_list_array = mysql_fetch_array
($req_det_list_SQL)){
        $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even";  ?>
        <tr class="<?=$row_color?" align="left"
valign="top">
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[2]?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[3]?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[4]?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=ucwords($req_det_list_array[5])?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="hidden"
name="items_name[]"
value="<?=$req_det_list_array[6]?>"><?=ucwords($req_det_list_array[6])?></td>
            <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[7]?></td>
            <td width="*" align="center"><a
href="./req_details.php?id=<?=$req_det_list_array[1]?>"></a></td>
            </tr>
        <?php $count++;
    }
} else {?>
        <tr><td colspan="8" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
        <?>?>
        </table></div>
    </form>
    </td></tr>
    <tr><td
><?=paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $req_det_list_query) ?></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>

</-----CONTENT-END----->
-//>
            </td>
            <td width="3">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>

```

14. req_acc_act.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$branch_opt = "";

```

```
//Tampilin daftar request item yang accepted
$req_det_list_query ="SELECT request_details.id, request.id, file.code,
branch.branch_id, departments.name as dept, CONCAT(user.name,'
',user.given_name) AS fullname, request_items.name as items,
request_details.status ";
$req_det_list_query .="FROM request ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = request.file_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN request_details ON (request_details.req_id_fk
= request.id) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN request_items ON (request_items.id =
request_details.req_item_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = request.user_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$req_det_list_query .="WHERE request_items.req_type_id_fk = '1' AND
request_details.status = 'ACCEPTED' ";

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF'];

//Tampilin daftar sesuai branchnya
if(isset($_POST['pick_branch'])){
    $branch_opt=$_POST['branch'];
    if($branch_opt != "ALL") {$req_det_list_query .="AND request.branch_id_fk
= '". $branch_opt.'" "; }
    else { $req_det_list_query .=" "; }
} else { $req_det_list_query .=" "; }

$req_det_list_query .="ORDER BY request.req_date DESC, request.req_time DESC";
$req_det_list_SQL = mysql_query($req_det_list_query);

$branch_list_query ="SELECT branch.branch_id, branch.name FROM branch;";
$branch_list_SQL = mysql_query($branch_list_query);

if(isset($_POST['approve_access']) AND isset($_POST['req_det_id'])!='') {
    $req_det_id = $_POST['req_det_id'];
    foreach ($req_det_id as $req_id) {
        $act_acc_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status
='APPROVED' WHERE id = '$req_id'";
        mysql_query($act_acc_query);
    }
    header("location:$this_page");
}

if(isset($_POST['reject_access']) AND isset($_POST['req_det_id'])!='') {
    $req_det_id = $_POST['req_det_id'];
    foreach ($req_det_id as $req_id) {
        $act_acc_query = "UPDATE request_details SET status
='REJECTED' WHERE id = '$req_id'";
        mysql_query($act_acc_query);
    }
    header("location:$this_page");
}

$page_title="Modify Requested Access Page";
$page_id="6";
$page_id_right ="22";
$category_page = "access";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>
```

```

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
---//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
  <tr><td><h2>MODIFY REQUESTED ACCESS</h2></td></tr>
  <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
  <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
  <tr><td>
    <form method="POST" action="<?=$_SERVER['PHP_SELF']?>">
    ACCESS FOR BRANCH :
      <select name="branch">
        <option value="ALL" <?=$selected?>>ALL</option>
        <option >-----</option>
<?php while($branch_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($branch_list_SQL)){
  $selected = ($branch_opt == $branch_list_array[0])?"SELECTED":"";
?>
  <option value="<?=$branch_list_array[0]?>"
<?=$selected?>><?ucwords($branch_list_array[1])?></option>
<? } ?>
  </select>
  &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="submit" name="pick_branch" value=" OK
" />

  </form></td></tr>
  <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
  <tr><td>
    <form method="POST" action="">
    <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
      <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) { ?>
  <tr><td colspan="9" bgcolor="#6699cc" height="28" valign="middle">
    &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="submit" name="approve_access"
class="button" value=" APPROVE "/>
    &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<input type="submit" name="reject_access"
class="button" value=" REJECT "/>
  </td></tr>
<?php } else { ?><?php } ?>
  <tr class="listview" align="left" valign="top">
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) { ?>
  <td width="20"><input type="hidden"
name="rfa_branch_id" value="<?=$branch_opt?>"></td>
<?php } else { ?><?php } ?>
  <td width="25"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&NO.</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&FILE NO.</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&BRANCH</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&DEPARTMENT</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&REQUESTER</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&ACCESS</b></td>
  <td width="*"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&STATUS</b></td>
  <td width="*" align="center"><b>&nbsp;&nbsp;&CMD</b></td>

<?php
  if (mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) {
    $count = 1;
    while($req_det_list_array = mysql_fetch_array
($req_det_list_SQL)){
      $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
      <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
valign="top">
<?php if($branch_opt && $branch_opt != "ALL" &&
mysql_num_rows($req_det_list_SQL) >= 1) { ?>
  <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&<input type="checkbox"
name="req_det_id[" value="<?=$req_det_list_array[0]?>"></td>
<?php } else { ?>
<?php } ?>
  <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&<?=$count?>.</td>

```

```

        <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[2]?></td>
        <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[3]?></td>
        <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[4]?></td>

        <td>&nbsp;<?=ucwords($req_det_list_array[5])?></td>

        <td>&nbsp;<?=ucwords($req_det_list_array[6])?></td>
        <td>&nbsp;<?=$req_det_list_array[7]?></td>
        <td width="*" align="center"><a
href=" ./req_details.php?id=<?=$req_det_list_array[1]?>"></a></td>
    </tr>
        <?php $count++;
        }
    } else {?>
        <tr><td colspan="9" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
        <?}?>
    </table></div>
</form>
</td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
<!-------CONTENT-END-----
-->

        </td>
        <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>

```

15. vendor_eval.php

```

<?php
require_once(' ./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once(' ./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once(' ./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$status = "&nbsp;";

function vendor_list_static(){
    $vendor_list_query = "SELECT vendors.vendor_id, vendors.name FROM vendors
ORDER BY vendors.name ASC;";
    $vendor_list_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_list_query); ?>
    <select name="vendor">
    <option value="-" selected>-----</option>
<?php while($vendor_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($vendor_list_SQL)){?>
    <option
value="<?=$vendor_list_array[0]?>"><?=ucwords($vendor_list_array[1])?></option>
<?php }
        echo "</select>";
    }

function criteria_marks() { ?>
    <select name="score[]">
    <option value="-">-----</option>
    <option value="4">EXCELLENT</option>

```

```
        <option value="3">GOOD</option>
        <option value="2">MEDIocre</option>
        <option value="1">POOR</option>
    </select>
<?php }

if (isset($_POST['submit'])){
    $date = ((isset($_POST['date']) && $_POST['date'] != '')?trim
($_POST['date']):'');
    $vendor = ((isset($_POST['vendor']) && $_POST['vendor'] != '')?trim
($_POST['vendor']):'');
    $po_number = ((isset($_POST['po_number']) && $_POST['po_number'] !=
'')?trim($_POST['po_number']):'');
    $crit_id = ((isset($_POST['crit_id']) && $_POST['crit_id'] !=
'')?$_POST['crit_id']):'');
    $remarks = ((isset($_POST['remarks']) && $_POST['remarks'] != '')?trim
($_POST['remarks']):'');
    $evaluator = $_SESSION['uid'];
    $score = $_POST['score'];
    $avg_score = array_sum($score)/count($score);

    if ($vendor != "-" AND !in_array("-", $score)) {
        $insert_vdr_eval_query="INSERT INTO vendor_eval VALUES (NULL, ".$date.",
'".$vendor."', '".$po_number."', '".$avg_score."', '".$remarks."',
'".$evaluator."', '');"
        mysql_query($insert_vdr_eval_query);

        $vendor_eval_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
        foreach($crit_id as $crit_id_key => $crit_id_value) {
            $score_array = $score[$crit_id_key];
            $insert_vdr_eval_det_query = "INSERT INTO vendor_eval_details
VALUES
(NULL, ".$vendor_eval_id_fk.", '".$crit_id_value."', '".$score_array."');"
            mysql_query($insert_vdr_eval_det_query);
        }
        header("location:./vendor_eval_home.php");
    }
    else { $status ="<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .="<tr><td>Missing Information! unable to create
the vendor evaluation.</td></tr>";
        $status .="</table><br>"; }
}

$vendor_criteria_query = "SELECT id, name FROM vendor_criteria;";
$vendor_criteria_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_criteria_query);

$page_title ="Vendor Evaluation Form Page";
$page_id ="9";
$page_id_right = "30";
$category_page = "vendor_eval";
?>
<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
---//>
<form method="POST" action="">
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr><td><h2>VENDOR EVALUATION FORM</h2></td></tr>
        <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
        <tr><td><?=$status?></td></tr>
        <?=$vdr_eval_button();?>
        <tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td>
            <table border="0">
                <tr><td align="left"><b>DATE</b></td><td></td>
                <td><input type="text" name="date" value="<?=$date('Y-
```

```

m-d')?>" id="cal" size="10" maxlength="10">&nbsp;
                                <a href="javascript:NewCal('cal','yyyymmdd')">
                                </a></td></tr>
                                <tr><td align="left"><b>COMPANY
NAME</b></td><td></td><td><?=>vendor_list_static()?</td></tr>
                                <tr><td align="left"><b>P.O.
NO.</b></td><td></td><td><input type="text" name="po_number"
value="9XXX/<?=>date('mY')?>" maxlength="11"></td></tr>
                                </table>
                                </td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td>
                                <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" style='border:
1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
                                    <tr class="listview" valign="top">
                                        <td align="left"><b>&nbsp;</td>
                                        <td align="center"><b>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <?php
                                $count = 1;
                                while($vendor_criteria_array = mysql_fetch_array($vendor_criteria_SQL)) {
                                    $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
                                    <tr class="<?=$row_color?>">
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=>ucwords($vendor_criteria_array[1])?>&nbsp;</td>
                                        <td align="center">
                                            <input type="hidden" name="crit_id[]"
value="<?=>ucwords($vendor_criteria_array[0])?>"/>
                                            <?=>criteria_marks()?></td></tr>
                                <?php
                                $count++;
                                } ?>
                                </table>
                                </td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td><b>REMARKS</b><br /><textarea cols="60" rows="5"
name="remarks" wrap="virtual"></textarea></td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td><b>EVALUATED BY:</b><br /><br
/><?=>ucwords($_SESSION['fullname'])?></td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <?=>vdr_eval_button()?>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                </table></form>

<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-//>

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                                </tr>
                                </tbody>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=>sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php source_footer()?>
    
```

16. vendor_eval_pr.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
    
```

```
chkSession();

function vendor_list_static($vendor_id_sl){
    $vendor_list_query = "SELECT vendors.vendor_id, vendors.name FROM vendors
ORDER BY vendors.name ASC;";
    $vendor_list_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_list_query); ?>
    <select name="vendor">
    <option value="-">-----</option>
<?php while($vendor_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($vendor_list_SQL)){
    $selected = ($vendor_id_sl ==
$vendor_list_array[0])?"SELECTED":"";
    ?>
    <option value="<?=$vendor_list_array[0]?>"
<?=$selected?>><?ucwords($vendor_list_array[1])?></option>
<?php }
    echo "</select>";
}
$status = "&nbsp;";
function vendor_eval_sugg(){ ?>
    <select name="suggestion">
    <option value="-">-----</option>
    <option value="maintain">Maintain in AVL</option>
    <option value="eliminate">Eliminate from AVL</option>
    </select>
<?php }

if (isset($_POST['submit'])){
    $startdate = $_POST['date1'];
    $enddate = $_POST['date2'];
    $vendor_id_fk = $_POST['vendor'];
    $total = ($_POST['total'])?$_POST['total']:"";
    $average = ($_POST['average'])?$_POST['average']:"";
    $remarks = ($_POST['eval_remarks'])?$_POST['eval_remarks']:"";
    $suggestion = ($_POST['suggestion'])?$_POST['suggestion']:"";
    $evaldate = date('Y-m-d');
    $user_id_fk = $_SESSION['uid'];
    $eval_id_fk = $_POST['eval_id_fk'];

    if ($suggestion != "-"){
        $insert_eval_pr_query = "INSERT INTO vendor_eval_period ";
        $insert_eval_pr_query .= "VALUES
(NULL, '$startdate', '$enddate', '$vendor_id_fk', '$total', '$average', '$remarks', '$
suggestion', '$evaldate', '$user_id_fk')";
        mysql_query($insert_eval_pr_query);

        $vdr_ev_pr_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();

        foreach($eval_id_fk as $vdr_eval_id_fk) {
            $insert_eval_pr_det_query = "INSERT INTO
vendor_eval_period_details ";
            $insert_eval_pr_det_query .= "VALUES
(NULL, '$vdr_ev_pr_id_fk', '$vdr_eval_id_fk')";
            mysql_query($insert_eval_pr_det_query) or die
(mysql_error());

            $update_eval_query = "UPDATE vendor_eval SET period = '1'
WHERE id = '$vdr_eval_id_fk'";
            mysql_query($update_eval_query);
        }
        header("location:./vendor_eval_pr_hm.php");
    } else {
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>Please give also your <font
color=\"red\"><b>status</b></font> suggestion ! hit the back button to change
your data</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
    }
}
```

```

    }
  }

$vendor_criteria_query = "SELECT id, name FROM vendor_criteria;";
$vendor_criteria_SQL = mysql_query($vendor_criteria_query);

$page_title = "Vendor Evaluation Form Page";
$page_id = "9";
$page_id_right = "32";
$category_page = "vendor_eval";

$vendor_id = (isset($_POST['vendor']))?$_POST['vendor']:"-";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START-----
---//>
<form method="POST" action="">
  <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>VENDOR PERIODIC EVALUATION FORM</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>
      <table border="0">
        <tr><td align="left"><b>START DATE</b></td>
          <td>:</td>
          <td><input type="text" name="date1" id="call1"
size="10" maxlength="10"
value="<?=(isset($_POST['date1']))?$_POST['date1']:"";?>&nbsp;   
          <a
href="javascript:NewCal('call1','yyyymmdd')">
            </a></td>
          <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<b>END</b>:</td>
          <td><input type="text" name="date2" id="cal2"
size="10" maxlength="10"
value="<?=(isset($_POST['date2']))?$_POST['date2']:"";?>&nbsp;   
          <a
href="javascript:NewCal('cal2','yyyymmdd')">
            </a>
          </td>
        <tr><td align="left"><b>COMPANY NAME</b></td><td>:</td><td colspan="3"><?=>
vendor_list_static($vendor_id)?></td><td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td></tr>
      </table>
    </td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <?php if (isset($_POST['gen-vdr-eval-per']) AND !empty($_POST['date1']) AND
!empty($_POST['date2']) AND $_POST['vendor'] != "-" ) {
      $datestart = $_POST['date1'];
      $dateend = $_POST['date2'];

      $get_eval_data_query = "SELECT vendor_eval.id,
vendor_eval.po_number, vendor_eval.avg_score ";
      $get_eval_data_query .= "FROM vendor_eval ";
      $get_eval_data_query .= "WHERE vendor_eval.vendor_id_fk =
'".$vendor_id."' AND vendor_eval.period = '0' AND vendor_eval.date BETWEEN
'".$datestart."' AND '".$dateend."'";
      $get_eval_data_SQL = mysql_query($get_eval_data_query);
    }
  }
}

```



```

        if (!empty($name)){
            mysql_query($add_crit_query);
            header("location:$this_page");
            exit();
        }
        else {
            $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
            $status .= "<tr><td>You can't insert an empty criteria
!</td></tr>";
            $status .= "</table><br>";
        }
    }

    if (isset($_POST['update_crit'])){
        $nid = trim($_POST['nid']);
        $name = trim($_POST['name']);
        $update_crit_query = "UPDATE vendor_criteria ";
        $update_crit_query .= "SET name='". $name. "' ";
        $update_crit_query .= "WHERE id = '". $nid. "'";
        mysql_query($update_crit_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    }

    if (isset($_GET['del_id'])){
        $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
        $delete_crit_query = "DELETE FROM vendor_criteria ";
        $delete_crit_query .= "WHERE id = '". $did. "'";
        mysql_query($delete_crit_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    }

    $page_title="Vendor Criteria Page";
    $page_id_left ="9";
    $page_id_right ="33";
    $category_page = "vendor_eval";

    ?>

    <?php source_header($page_id_left,$page_title);?>

    <!-------CONTENT-START----->
    -----//>

    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr><td><h2>CRITERIA LIST</h2></td></tr>
        <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
        <tr><td ><?=$status?></td></tr>
        <tr><td ><form method="POST" action="">
            <fieldset><legend>NEW CRITERIA</legend>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" >
                <tr valign="middle">
                    <td><b>MESSAGE</b></td>
                    <td>&nbsp;</td>
                    <td><input type="text" name="name"
size="80"></td>
                    <td width="">&nbsp;<input type="submit"
name="add_crit" class="button" value="ADD"></td>
                </tr></table>
            </fieldset></form></td></tr>
        <tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td ><fieldset><legend>CRITERIA LIST</legend><br />
        <?php
        paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum,$offset,$crit_list_query); ?>
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-

```

```

top: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px; ' >
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">

            <tr class="listview" valign="middle">
                <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO</b></td>
                <td width="45" align="left">&nbsp;<b>ID</b></td>
                <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>MESSAGE</b></td>
                <td width="30" colspan="2"
align="center">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b></td>
            </tr>

            <?php
                if (mysql_num_rows($crit_list_SQL) >= 1) {
                    ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
                    while($crit_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($crit_list_SQL)){
                        $row_color = ($count % 2)? "odd": "even";
                        if (isset($_GET['nid']) && $_GET['nid'] ==
$crit_list_array[0]) {?>
                            <form method="POST" action="">
                                <input type="hidden" name="nid"
value="<?=$crit_list_array[0]?>">
                                <tr bgcolor="#ffcc99" align="left"
valign="top">
                                    <td
width="25">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                                    <td>&nbsp;<?=$crit_list_array[0]?></td>
                                    <td>&nbsp;<input type="text"
name="name" size="80" value="<?=$crit_list_array[1]?>"></td>
                                    <td width="*" align="center"
colspan="2"><input type="submit" class="button" name="update_crit"
value="UPDATE"></td>
                                </tr>
                                </form>
                            <?php
                                } else { ?>
                                    <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
valign="top">
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$crit_list_array[0]?>
</td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$crit_list_array[1]?>
</td>
                                        <td width="*">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<a
href="<?=$this_page?>&nid=<?=$crit_list_array[0]?>">
                                            </a>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
                                        <td width="*">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<a
href="<?=$this_page?>" onclick="return confirmDel(this, 'Evaluation criteria
', '<?=$crit_list_array[0]?>')">
                                            </a>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
                                        </tr>
                                    <?php
                                        } $count++;
                                    }
                                } else {?>
                                    <tr><td colspan="9" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /></td></tr>
                                <?php } ?>
                            </table></div>
                                <?php
                                paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $crit_list_query) ?>
                                </fieldset>
                            </td></tr>
                        </table>
                    
```

```
</-----CONTENT-END----->
-----//>

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                                </tr>
                                </tbody>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php source_footer()?>
```

18. members.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 7;
$pageNum = 1;

if(isset($_GET['page'])) { $pageNum = $_GET['page']; }
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

$branch_list_query = "SELECT branch.branch_id, branch.name FROM branch;";
$branch_list_SQL = mysql_query($branch_list_query);

$department_list_query = "SELECT departments.id, departments.name FROM
departments;";
$department_list_SQL = mysql_query($department_list_query);

$level_list_query = "SELECT user_level.id, user_level.name FROM user_level;";
$level_list_SQL = mysql_query($level_list_query);

$manager_list_query = "SELECT user.id, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name) AS
fullname FROM user WHERE user.level_id_fk = '3';";
$manager_list_SQL = mysql_query($manager_list_query);

$members_list_query = "SELECT user.id, user.name, user.given_name,
user.username, user.status, branch.branch_id, departments.name,
user_level.name, user.jointdate ";
$members_list_query .= "FROM user LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$members_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk ) ";
$members_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user_level ON (user_level.id =
user.level_id_fk) ";
$members_list_query .= "ORDER BY user.name ASC";
$members_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage;";

$members_list_limit_query = $members_list_query." ".$members_limit_query;

$members_list_SQL = mysql_query($members_list_limit_query);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?page=".$pageNum;

if(isset($_POST['add_user'])) {
    $username = trim(strtolower($_POST['username']));
    if(!empty ($username)) {
        $password = trim(md5(DEFAULT_PASS));
        $fname = strtolower(trim($_POST['fname']));
        $lname = strtolower(trim($_POST['lname']));
```

```
$email = strtolower(trim($_POST['email']));
$status = strtolower(trim($_POST['status']));
$branch = trim($_POST['branch']);
$department = strtolower(trim($_POST['department']));
$manager = strtolower(trim($_POST['manager']));
$level = strtolower(trim($_POST['level']));
$jointdate = date('Y-m-d');
function checkemail($email){
    return preg_match("/^[^s()<>@,;:\\"/\\[\]?=]+@w[\w-
]*(\.\w[\w-]*)*\.[a-z]{2,}$/i",$email);
}
if(!$email) OR (!checkemail($email)){
    $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
    $status .= "<tr><td>You did not enter a valid e-mail
address.</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table><br>";
} else {
    $check_username_query = "SELECT user.username FROM user WHERE
user.username = '$username'";
    $check_username_SQL = mysql_query($check_username_query);
    if (mysql_num_rows($check_username_SQL) >= 1) {
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>Another account with this username
(<b>".$username."</b>) already created. Please choose another
username!</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
    }
    else {
        $add_user_query = "INSERT INTO user VALUES ";
        $add_user_query
        .= "(NULL, '".$fname."', '".$lname."', '".$username."', '".$password."', '".$email."',
        '".$status."', '".$branch."', '".$department."', '".$manager."', '".$level."', '".$
        jointdate.'")";
        mysql_query($add_user_query);
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>Username <b>".$username."</b> has been
created.</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
        //header("location:$this_page" );
    }
}
else { $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
    $status .= "<tr><td>You can't insert an empty
username</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table><br>";
}
}
else { $status="&nbsp;"; }

if (isset($_GET['del_id'])){
    $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
    $delete_user_query = "DELETE FROM user ";
    $delete_user_query .= "WHERE id = '$did.'";
    mysql_query($delete_user_query);
    header("location:$this_page");
    exit();
}

if (isset($_POST['rst_all_pass'])){
    $rst_all_password = trim(md5(DEFAULT_PASS));
    $rst_all_pass_query = "UPDATE user SET password =
'".$rst_all_password.'"";
    mysql_query($rst_all_pass_query);
}
```

```
$status ="<br><table class=yellowbox>";
$status .="<tr><td>All users password has been resetted !</td></tr>";
$status .="</table><br>";
}

$page_title="Members List";
$page_id_left ="11";
$page_id_right ="45";
$category_page = "admin";
?>
<?php source_header($page_id_left, $page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
<!--//>
<form method="POST" action="" >
<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
  <tr><td><h2>MEMBERS LIST</h2></td></tr>
  <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
  <tr><td><?=$status?></td></tr>
  <tr><td>
    <br />
    <fieldset><legend>NEW ACCOUNT</legend>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" >
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right" colspan="7"></td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"><b>FIRST NAME</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td><input type=text size=30 name='fname'></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td align="right"><b>LAST NAME</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td><input type=text size=30 name='lname'></td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"><b>USERNAME</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td><input type=text size=30 name='username'></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td align="right"><b>PASSWORD</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td>' <b><i><?=strtolower(DEFAULT_PASS)?></i></b>
'&nbsp;</td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"></td>
        <td></td>
        <td></td>
        <td>&nbsp;</td>
        <td align="right"></td>
        <td></td>
        <td>(Default password for every user, they must change it
after login)</td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"><b>EMAIL</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td colspan="5"><input type="text" size="30" name="email"
value="<?=DEFAULT_MAIL_DOMAIN?>"></td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"><b>STATUS</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td colspan="5"><input type="text" size="30"
name="status"></td></tr>
      <tr valign=top>
        <td align="right"><b>BRANCH</b></td>
        <td>:</td>
        <td>
          <select name="branch">
```

```

                                <option SELECTED>-----</option>
<?php
    while($branch_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($branch_list_SQL)){?>
        <option
value="<?=$branch_list_array[0]?>"><?ucwords($branch_list_array[1])?></option>
<? } ?>

                                </select>
                                </td>
                                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                                <td align="right"><b>DEPARTMENT</b></td>
                                <td>:</td>
                                <td>
                                    <select name="department">
                                        <option SELECTED>-----</option>
<?php
    while($department_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($department_list_SQL)){?>
        <option
value="<?=$department_list_array[0]?>"><?ucwords($department_list_array[1])?><
/option>
<? } ?>

                                </select>
                                </td></tr>
                                <tr valign=top>
                                <td align="right"><b>MANAGER</b></td>
                                <td>:</td>
                                <td colspan="5">
                                    <select name="manager">
                                        <option SELECTED>-----</option>
<?php
    while($manager_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($manager_list_SQL)){?>
        <option
value="<?=$manager_list_array[0]?>"><?ucwords($manager_list_array[1])?></optio
n>
<? } ?>

                                </select>
                                </td></tr>
                                <tr valign=top>
                                <td align="right"><b>LEVEL</b></td>
                                <td>:</td>
                                <td colspan="5">
                                    <select name="level">
                                        <option SELECTED>-----</option>
<?php
    while($level_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($level_list_SQL)){?>
        <option
value="<?=$level_list_array[0]?>"><?ucwords($level_list_array[1])?></option>
<? } ?>

                                </td></tr>
                                <tr valign=top>
                                <td align="right"><b>JOINT DATE</b></td>
                                <td>:</td>
                                <td colspan="5"><?date('Y-m-d')?></td></tr>
                                </table></fieldset>

                                </td></tr>
                                <tr><td><input type="submit" name="add_user" class="button"
value="ADD ACCOUNT"></td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td><input type="submit" name="rst_all_pass" class="button"
value="RESET ALL PASSWORD"></td></tr>
                                <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
                                <tr><td>
                                    <fieldset><legend>MEMBERS LIST</legend>

```

```

        <?php
        paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $members_list_query) ?>
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
        5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr class="listview" valign="middle">
            <td width="25">&nbsp;<b>NO.</b></td>
            <td >&nbsp;<b>FIRSTNAME</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>LASTNAME</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>USERNAME</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>STATUS</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>BRANCH</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>DEPARTMENT</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>LEVEL</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>REG. DATE</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="center"
        colspan="2">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b></td>
        <?php
        if (mysql_num_rows($members_list_SQL) >= 1) {
            ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
            while($members_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($members_list_SQL)){
                $row_color = ($count % 2)? "odd": "even"; ?>
                <tr class="<?=$row_color?" valign="top">
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[1] )?ucwords($members_list_array[1]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[2] )?ucwords($members_list_array[2]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=$members_list_array[3]?></td>
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[4] )?ucwords($members_list_array[4]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[5] )?ucwords($members_list_array[5]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[6] )?ucwords($members_list_array[6]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td
        align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[7] )?ucwords($members_list_array[7]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td align="left">&nbsp;<?=( $members_list_array[8] )?ucwords($members_list_array[8]):
        "&nbsp;<?=$row_color?">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td width="25" align="center" valign="middle"><a
        href="./member_details.php?id=<?=$members_list_array[0]?>">
                        </a></td>
                    <td width="25" align="center" valign="middle"><a
        href="<?=$this_page?">&nbsp;<?=$members_list_array[3]?> ', '<?=$members_list_array[0]?>'>
                        </a></td>
                </tr>
        <?php $count++;
            }
        } else {?>
            <tr><td colspan="11" align="center" bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No
        Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
            <?>
        ?>
        </table>
        </div>
        <?php
        paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $members_list_query) ?>
        </fieldset></td></tr>

    </table>
    
```

```
</form>
<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-//>

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                                </tr>
                                </tbody>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
                                </tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
```

19. member_details.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$member_id = ((isset ($_GET['id']) && $_GET['id'] != '')?trim
($_GET['id']): '');

$sold_user_query = "SELECT user.id, user.name, user.given_name, user.username,
user.email, user.status, user.branch_id_fk, user.dept_id_fk, user.mgr_id_fk,
user.level_id_fk, user.jointdate ";
$sold_user_query .= "FROM user ";
$sold_user_query .= "WHERE user.id = '". $member_id. "'";
$sold_user_SQL = mysql_query($sold_user_query);
$sold_user_array = mysql_fetch_array($sold_user_SQL);

$branch_list_query = "SELECT branch.branch_id, branch.name FROM branch ORDER BY
branch.name ASC";
$branch_list_SQL = mysql_query($branch_list_query);

$department_list_query = "SELECT departments.id, departments.name FROM
departments ORDER BY departments.name ASC";
$department_list_SQL = mysql_query($department_list_query);

$level_list_query = "SELECT user_level.id, user_level.name FROM user_level ORDER
BY user_level.name ASC";
$level_list_SQL = mysql_query($level_list_query);

$manager_list_query = "SELECT user.id, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name) AS
fullname FROM user WHERE user.level_id_fk = '3'";
$manager_list_SQL = mysql_query($manager_list_query);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?id=".$member_id;

$status="&nbsp;";

if (isset($_POST['update_user'])){
    $this_page = $_SERVER['REQUEST_URI'];
    $update_id = $_POST['update_id'];
    $fname = strtolower(trim($_POST['fname']));
    $lname = strtolower(trim($_POST['lname']));
    $email = strtolower(trim($_POST['email']));
    $status = strtolower(trim($_POST['status']));
    $branch = trim($_POST['branch']);
    $department = strtolower(trim($_POST['department']));
    $manager = strtolower(trim($_POST['manager']));
    $level = strtolower(trim($_POST['level']));
```

```
function checkemail($email){
    return preg_match("/^[^s()<>@,;:\\"\/\[\]\?]=]+\w[\w-
]*(\.\w[\w-]*)*\.[a-z]{2,}$/i",$email);
}
if(!$email) OR (!checkemail($email)){
    $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
    $status .= "<tr><td>You did not enter a valid e-mail
address.</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table><br/>";
} else {
    $update_user_query = "UPDATE user ";
    $update_user_query .= "SET name = '". $fname. "',
given_name= '". $lname. "', email= '". $email. "', status= '". $status. "',
branch_id_fk= '". $branch. "', dept_id_fk= '". $department. "',
mgr_id_fk= '". $manager. "', level_id_fk= '". $level. "' ";
    $update_user_query .= "WHERE id = '". $update_id. "' ";
    mysql_query($update_user_query);

    $status = "<br/><table class=\"yellowbox\">";
    $status .= "<tr><td>Account data has been updated !</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table><br/>";
}
}
elseif(isset($_POST['reset_pass'])) {
    $update_id = $_POST['update_id'];
    $pass_reset = trim(md5(DEFAULT_PASS));
    $reset_pass_query = "UPDATE user SET password = '". $pass_reset. "'
WHERE id = '". $update_id. "' ";
    mysql_query($reset_pass_query);

    $status = "<br/><table class=\"yellowbox\">";
    $status .= "<tr><td>This account's password has been resetted
!</td></tr>";
    $status .= "</table><br/>";
}
else {$status="&nbsp;";}

$page_title = "Member Details";
$page_id = "11";
$page_id_right = "45";
$category_page = "admin";
?>

<?php source_header($page_id,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START-----
---//>
<form method="POST" action="<?=$_SERVER['REQUEST_URI'];?>">
<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>MEMBER DETAILS</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td><?=$status?></td></tr>
    <tr><td>[&nbsp;<a href="./members.php">Back to the Members
Page</a>&nbsp;<];</td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>
        <fieldset><legend>ACCOUNT INFORMATION</legend>

        <input type="hidden" name="update_id" value="<?=$member_id?>">
        <table border="0">
            <tr valign=top>
                <td align="right" colspan="7"></td></tr>
            <tr valign=top>
                <td align="right"><b>FIRST NAME</b></td>
                <td>:</td>

```



```

<?php
    while($manager_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($manager_list_SQL)){
        $compare_manager = ($manager_list_array[0] ==
    $old_user_array[8])?"SELECTED":"";?>
        <option value="<?=$manager_list_array[0]?>"
    <?=$compare_manager?>><?=ucwords($manager_list_array[1])?></option>
    <? } ?>

        </select>

        </td></tr>
        <tr valign=top>
            <td align="right"><b>LEVEL</b></td>
            <td>:</td>
            <td colspan="5">
                <select name="level">
                    <option value="-">-----</option>
<?php
    while($level_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($level_list_SQL)){
        $compare_level = ($level_list_array[0] ==
    $old_user_array[9])?"SELECTED":"";?>
        <option value="<?=$level_list_array[0]?>"
    <?=$compare_level?>><?=ucwords($level_list_array[1])?></option>
    <? } ?>

        </td></tr>
        <tr valign=top>
            <td align="right"><b>JOINT DATE</b></td>
            <td>:</td>
            <td colspan="5"><?=$old_user_array[10]?></td></tr>
    </table></fieldset>
    </td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td><input type="submit" class="button" name="update_user"
    value="UPDATE ACCOUNT"></td></tr>
    <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td>[&nbsp;<a href="./members.php">Back to the Members
    Page</a>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</form>
<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-//>

            </td>
            <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table>
</td>
        <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
    width="165"><?=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
    </tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
    
```

20. item_type.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 7;
$pageNum = 1;

if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;
    
```

```
$type_list_query = "SELECT request_items.id, request_items.name,  
request_type.id, request_type.name, request_items.consumable ";  
$type_list_query .= "FROM request_items LEFT JOIN request_type ON  
(request_type.id = request_items.req_type_id_fk) ";  
$type_list_query .= "ORDER BY request_items.id ASC";  
$type_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";  
$type_list_limit_query = $type_list_query . " " . $type_limit_query;  
$type_list_SQL = mysql_query($type_list_limit_query);  
  
$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF'] . "?page=" . $pageNum;  
  
$status = "&nbsp;";  
  
function select_consume() { ?>  
    <select name="consume">  
        <option value="-">-----</option>  
        <option value="1">YES</option>  
        <option value="0">NO</option>  
    </select>  
  
<?php }  
  
function select_cat_type() {  
    $disp_cat_type_q = "SELECT id, name FROM request_type";  
    $disp_cat_type_SQL = mysql_query($disp_cat_type_q);  
    <select name="category">  
        <option value="-">-----</option>  
<?php while($disp_cat_type_array = mysql_fetch_array($disp_cat_type_SQL)) { ?>  
        <option  
value="<?=$disp_cat_type_array[0]?>"><?=strtoupper($disp_cat_type_array[1])?></  
option>  
<?php } ?>  
    </select>  
  
<?php }  
  
if (isset($_POST['add_type'])) {  
    $name = trim($_POST['name']);  
    $category = trim($_POST['category']);  
    $consume = trim($_POST['consume']);  
  
    if (!empty($name) AND $consume != "-" AND $category != "-") {  
        $add_type_query = "INSERT INTO request_items VALUES ";  
        $add_type_query .= "(NULL, '$name', '$category', '$consume')";  
        mysql_query($add_type_query);  
        header("location:$this_page");  
        exit();  
    }  
    else {  
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";  
        $status .= "<tr><td>Missing information ! Cannot create new request  
item.</td></tr>";  
        $status .= "</table><br>";  
    }  
}  
  
$display_cat_item_q = "SELECT id, name FROM request_type";  
$display_cat_item_SQL = mysql_query($display_cat_item_q);  
  
if (isset($_POST['update_type'])) {  
    $nid = trim($_POST['nid']);  
    $name = trim($_POST['name']);  
    $category = trim($_POST['category']);  
    $consume = trim($_POST['consume']);  
  
    $update_type_query = "UPDATE request_items ";
```

```

        $update_type_query .= "SET name='". $name. "',
req_type_id_fk='". $category. "', consumable='". $consume. "' ";
        $update_type_query .= "WHERE id='". $nid. "'";
        mysql_query($update_type_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    }

    if (isset($_GET['del_id'])){
        $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
        $delete_type_query = "DELETE FROM request_items ";
        $delete_type_query .= "WHERE id='". $did. "'";
        mysql_query($delete_type_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    }

    $page_title="Item Management Page";
    $page_id_left = "11";
    $page_id_right = "49";
    $category_page = "admin";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id_left,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
<!--//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>REQUEST ITEM LIST</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td ><?=$status?></td></tr>
    <tr><td ><form method="POST" action="">
        <fieldset><legend>ADD ITEM</legend>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1"
width="100%">
            <tr valign="middle">
                <td><b>NAME</b>:<br /><input type="text" name="name"
size="40"></td>
                <td><b>CATEGORY</b>:<br
/><?=$select_cat_type()?></td>
                <td><b>CONSUMABLE</b>:<br
/><?=$select_consume()?></td>
                <td width=""><br /><input type="submit"
name="add_type" class="button" value="ADD NEW"></td>
            </tr>
        </table>
        </fieldset></form>
    </td></tr>
    <tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td ><fieldset><legend>ITEM LIST</legend><br />
    <?php paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$type_list_query)
?>
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr class="listview" valign="middle">
            <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO</b></td>
            <td width="" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NAME</b></td>
            <td width="85" align="left">&nbsp;<b>CATEGORY</b></td>
            <td width="75"
align="left">&nbsp;<b>CONSUMABLE</b>&nbsp;</td>
            <td width="" colspan="2"
align="center">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b></td>
        </tr>
    </div>

```

```

<?php
    if (mysql_num_rows($type_list_SQL) >= 1) {
        ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
        while($type_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($type_list_SQL)){
            $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even";
            if (isset($_GET['nid']) && $_GET['nid'] ==
$type_list_array[0]) {?>
                <form method="POST" action="">
                <input type="hidden" name="nid"
value="<?=$type_list_array[0]?>">
                <tr bgcolor="#ffcc99" align="left" valign="top">
                    <td width="25"
align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td>&nbsp;<input type="text" name="name"
value="<?=ucwords($type_list_array[1]?>"></td>
                    <td width="85" align="left">
                        <select name="category">
                        <?php while($display_cat_item_array =
mysql_fetch_array($display_cat_item_SQL)){
                            $compare_cat =
($display_cat_item_array[0] == $type_list_array[2])?"SELECTED":"";?>
                            <option
value="<?=$display_cat_item_array[0]?>"
<?=$compare_cat?>><?=strtoupper($display_cat_item_array[1])?></option>
                            <? } ?>
                        </select>
                    </td>
                    <td width="75" align="center">
                        <?php
                            $cons_status = array("1","0");
                            $cons_name = array("YES","NO");
                            echo "<select name = \"consume\">\n";
                            foreach($cons_status as $key =>
$status) {
                                $name = $cons_name[$key];
                                $compare_cons = ($status ==
$type_list_array[4])?"SELECTED":"";
                                echo "\t<option value
=\"\$status\" $compare_cons>$name</option>\n";
                            }
                            echo "</select>\n";
                        ?>
                    </td>
                    <td width="*" align="center"
colspan="2"><input type="submit" class="button" name="update_type"
value="UPDATE"></td>
                </tr>
                </form>
                <?php } else { ?>
                <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
valign="top">
                    <td width="25"
align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                    <td>&nbsp;<?=ucwords($type_list_array[1])?>
</td>
                    <td>&nbsp;<?=strtoupper($type_list_array[3])?></td>
                    <td
align="center">&nbsp;<?=( $type_list_array[4] == "1")?"YES":"NO"?>&nbsp;</td>
                    <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>&nid=<?=$type_list_array[0]?>">
                        </a></td>
                    <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>" onclick="return confirmDel(this, 'Item
<?=ucwords($type_list_array[1])?> ', '<?=$type_list_array[0]?>')">

```

```

                                                    </a></td>
        </tr>
        <?php
            } $count++;
        }
    } else {?>
        <tr><td colspan="6" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
        <?php } ?>
    </table></div>
    <?php
paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $type_list_query) ?>
        </fieldset>
    </td></tr>
</table>

<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-->

        </td>
        <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>

```

21. navigation.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 10;
$pageNum = 1;

if(isset($_GET['page'])) { $pageNum = $_GET['page']; }
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

$nav_list_query = "SELECT id, sort, name, link, category, img_link, permit FROM
navigation ORDER BY sort ASC";
$nav_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";
$nav_list_limit_query = $nav_list_query . " " . $nav_limit_query;
$nav_list_SQL = mysql_query($nav_list_limit_query);

$level_list_query = "SELECT id, name FROM user_level ORDER BY id ASC ";
$level_list_SQL = mysql_query($level_list_query);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF'] . "?page=" . $pageNum;

$status = "&nbsp;";

if (isset($_POST['add_nav'])) {
    $sort = trim($_POST['sort']);
    $name = trim($_POST['name']);
    $link = trim($_POST['link']);
    $category = strtolower(trim($_POST['category']));
    $img_link = trim($_POST['img_link']);
    $permit = trim($_POST['permit']);
    if (!empty($name)) {

```

```
        $add_nav_query = "INSERT INTO navigation VALUES ";
        $add_nav_query
.= "(NULL, '$sort', '$name', '$link', '$category', '$img_link', '$permit');" ;
        mysql_query($add_nav_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
    }
    else {
        $status = "<br><table class=yellowbox>";
        $status .= "<tr><td>You can't insert an empty menu !</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
    }
}

if (isset($_POST['update_nav'])) {
    $nid = trim($_POST['nid']);
    $sort = trim($_POST['sort']);
    $name = trim($_POST['name']);
    $link = trim($_POST['link']);
    $category = strtolower(trim($_POST['category']));
    $img_link = trim($_POST['img_link']);
    $permit = trim($_POST['permit']);

    $update_nav_query = "UPDATE navigation ";
    $update_nav_query .= "SET sort='". $sort. "', name='". $name. "',
link='". $link. "', category='". $category. "', img_link='". $img_link. "',
permit='". $permit. "' ";
    $update_nav_query .= "WHERE id = '". $nid. "' ";
    mysql_query($update_nav_query);
    header("location:$this_page");
    exit();
}

if (isset($_GET['del_id'])) {
    $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
    $delete_nav_query = "DELETE FROM navigation ";
    $delete_nav_query .= "WHERE id = '". $did. "' ";
    mysql_query($delete_nav_query);
    header("location:$this_page");
    exit();
}

$page_title="Navigation Page";
$page_id_left = "11";
$page_id_right = "50";
$category_page = "admin";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id_left,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
---//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
    <tr><td><h2>MENU EDITING</h2></td></tr>
    <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
    <tr><td ><?=$status?></td></tr>
    <tr><td >
        <fieldset><legend>PERMISSION INFO</legend>
<?php while($level_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($level_list_SQL)) { ?>
    <?=$level_list_array[0]?> =
<?=ucwords($level_list_array[1])?>,
<?php } ?>
        </fieldset></td></tr>
    <tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
    <tr><td ><form method="POST" action="">
```

```

        <fieldset><legend>ADD NEW MENU</legend>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1"
width="100%">
            <tr valign="middle">
                <td><b>SORT</b>:<br /><input type="text" name="sort"
size="2" maxlength="2"></td>
                <td><b>NAME</b>:<br /><input type="text"
name="name"></td>
                <td><b>LINK</b>:<br /><input type="text"
name="link"></td>
                <td><b>CATEGORY</b>:<br /><input type="text"
name="category"></td>
                <td><b>IMAGE LINK</b>:<br /><input type="text"
name="img_link"></td>
                <td><b>PERMISSION</b>:<br /><input type="text"
name="permit"></td>
                <td width="*"><br /><input type="submit"
name="add_nav" class="button" value="ADD"></td>
            </tr></table>
        </fieldset></form></td></tr>
<tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td ><fieldset><legend>NAVIGATION LIST</legend><br />
<?php paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$nav_list_query) ?>
<div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr class="listview" valign="top">
            <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>ID</b></td>
            <td width="40" align="left">&nbsp;<b>SORT</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NAME</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>LINK</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>CATEGORY</b></td>
            <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>IMAGE LINK</b></td>
            <td width="*"
align="right">&nbsp;<b>PERMISSION</b>&nbsp;</td>
            <td width="30" colspan="2"
align="center">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b></td>
        </tr>
<?php
    if (mysql_num_rows($nav_list_SQL ) >= 1) {
        ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
        while($nav_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($nav_list_SQL)){
            $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even";
            if (isset($_GET['nid']) && $_GET['nid'] ==
$nav_list_array[0]) {?>
                <form method="POST" action="">
                    <input type="hidden" name="nid"
value="<?=$nav_list_array[0]?>">
                    <tr bgcolor="#ffcc99" align="left" valign="top">
                        <td width="25"
align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                        <td>#<?=$nav_list_array[0]?></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="sort"
value="<?=$nav_list_array[1]?>" size="2"></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="name"
value="<?=ucwords($nav_list_array[2]?>"></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="link"
value="<?=$nav_list_array[3];?>"></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="category"
value="<?=$nav_list_array[4];?>"></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="img_link"
value="<?=$nav_list_array[5];?>"></td>
                        <td align="right"><input type="text"
name="permit" value="<?=$nav_list_array[6];?>">&nbsp;</td>

```

```

                                <td width="*" align="center"
colspan="2"><input type="submit" class="button" name="update_nav"
value="UPDATE"></td>
                                </tr>
                                </form>
                                <?php } else { ?>
                                    <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left">
                                        <td width="25"
align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$nav_list_array[0]?> </td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$nav_list_array[1]?> </td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$ucwords($nav_list_array[2])?></td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$nav_list_array[3]?></td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$strtoupper($nav_list_array[4])?></td>
                                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$nav_list_array[5]?></td>
                                        <td
align="right">&nbsp;<?=$nav_list_array[6]?>&nbsp;</td>
                                        <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>&id=<?=$nav_list_array[0]?>">
                                            </a></td>
                                        <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>" onclick="return confirmDel(this, 'Link
<?=$ucwords($nav_list_array[2])?> ', '<?=$nav_list_array[0]?>')">
                                            </a></td>
                                        </tr>
                                <?php
                                    } $count++;
                                } else {?>
                                    <tr><td colspan="10" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
                                <?php } ?>
                                </table></div>
                                <?php
                                paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $nav_list_query) ?>
                                </fieldset>
                                </td></tr>
                                </table>

<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-->

                                </td>
                                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                                </tr>
                                </tbody>
                                </table>
                                </td>
                                <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?=$sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
                                </tr>
                                <?php source_footer()?>

```

22. motd.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 10;
$pageNum = 1;

```

```
if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

$motd_list_query = "SELECT id, message FROM motd ORDER BY id ASC";
$motd_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";

$motd_list_and_limit = $motd_list_query." ".$motd_limit_query;
$motd_list_SQL = mysql_query($motd_list_and_limit);

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF']."?page=".$pageNum;

$status = "&nbsp;";

if (isset($_POST['add_motd'])) {
    $message = strtolower(trim($_POST['msg']));
    $add_motd_query = "INSERT INTO motd VALUES ";
    $add_motd_query .= "(NULL, '$message')";
    if (!empty($message)) {
        mysql_query($add_motd_query);
        header("location:$this_page");
        exit();
    }
    else {
        $status = "<br><table class=\"yellowbox\">";
        $status .= "<tr><td>You can't insert an empty message !</td></tr>";
        $status .= "</table><br>";
    }
}

if (isset($_POST['update_motd'])) {
    $nid = trim($_POST['nid']);
    $message = trim($_POST['msg']);
    $update_motd_query = "UPDATE motd ";
    $update_motd_query .= "SET message='".$message."' ";
    $update_motd_query .= "WHERE id='".$nid."'";
    mysql_query($update_motd_query);
    header("location:$this_page");
    exit();
}

if (isset($_GET['del_id'])) {
    $did = trim($_GET['del_id']);
    $delete_motd_query = "DELETE FROM motd ";
    $delete_motd_query .= "WHERE id='".$did."'";
    mysql_query($delete_motd_query);
    header("location:$this_page");
    exit();
}

$page_title = "MOTD Page";
$page_id_left = "11";
$page_id_right = "51";
$category_page = "admin";

?>

<?php source_header($page_id_left,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
---//>

<table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
<tr><td><h2>MOTD : MESSAGE OF THE DAY LIST</h2></td></tr>
<tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
<tr><td ><?=$status?></td></tr>
```

```

        <tr><td ><form method="POST" action="">
            <fieldset><legend>NEW MESSAGE</legend>
            <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" >
        <tr valign="middle">
            <td><b>MESSAGE</b></td>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
            <td><input type="text" name="msg"
size="80"></td>
            <td width="*">&nbsp;<input type="submit"
name="add_motd" class="button" value=" ADD "></td>
        </tr></table>
        </fieldset></form></td></tr>
        <tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td >
            <fieldset><legend>MOTD LIST</legend><br />
        <?php paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$motd_list_query);
?>
        <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
        <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr class="listview" valign="middle">
        <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO</b></td>
        <td width="45" align="left">&nbsp;<b>ID</b></td>
        <td width="*" align="left">&nbsp;<b>MESSAGE</b></td>
        <td width="50" colspan="2"
align="center">&nbsp;<b>CMD</b></td>
        </tr>
        <?php
        if (mysql_num_rows($motd_list_SQL) >= 1) {
            ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
            while($motd_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($motd_list_SQL)){
                $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even";
                if (isset($_GET['nid']) && $_GET['nid'] ==
$motd_list_array[0]) {?>
                    <form method="POST" action="">
                    <input type="hidden" name="nid"
value="<?=$motd_list_array[0]?>">
                    <tr bgcolor="#ffcc99" align="left" valign="top">
                        <td width="25">&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$motd_list_array[0]?></td>
                        <td><input type="text" name="msg" size="80"
value="<?ucwords($motd_list_array[1]?>"></td>
                        <td width="*" align="center"
colspan="2"><input type="submit" class="button" name="update_motd"
value="UPDATE"></td>
                    </tr>
                    </form>
                <?php
                } else { ?>
                    <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
valign="top">
                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>
                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$motd_list_array[0]?> </td>
                        <td>&nbsp;<?ucwords($motd_list_array[1]?>
</td>
                        <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>&nid=<?=$motd_list_array[0]?>">
                            </a></td>
                        <td width="25" align="center"><a
href="<?=$this_page?>" onclick="return confirmDel(this, 'Message ',
'<?=$motd_list_array[0]?>')">
                            </a></td>
                    </tr>
                <?php
                } $count++;
    
```

```
        } else {?>
            <tr><td colspan="5" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
            <?php } ?>
        </table></div>
        <?php
paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$motd_list_query) ?>
        </fieldset>
        </td></tr>
    </table>

<!-------CONTENT-END----->
-->

        </td>
        <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
```

23. log_history.php

```
<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();

$rowsPerPage = 15;
$pageNum = 1;

if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}
$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

$log_list_query = "SELECT log_history.id, CONCAT(user.name, ' ',user.given_name)
AS fullname, log_history.ip_addr, log_history.time, log_history.activities ";
$log_list_query .= "FROM log_history LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id =
log_history.user_id_fk) ";
$log_list_query .= "ORDER BY log_history.time DESC";
$log_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";

$log_list_limit_query = $log_list_query." ".$log_limit_query;

$log_list_SQL = mysql_query($log_list_limit_query);

$page_title="Log History Page";
$page_id_left ="11";
$page_id_right ="52";
$category_page = "admin";
?>

<?php source_header($page_id_left,$page_title);?>

<!-------CONTENT-START----->
-->

<form method="POST" action="">
    <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
        <tr><td><h2>LOG HISTORY</h2></td></tr>
```

```

        <tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
        <tr><td ><?<=paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$log_list_query)
?></td></tr>
        <tr><td>
            <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
                <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
                <tr class="listview" align="left" valign="middle">
                    <td width="25" align="left">&nbsp;<b>NO</b></td>
                    <td >&nbsp;<b>RECORD ID</b></td>
                    <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>NAME</b></td>
                    <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>IP ADDRESS</b></td>
                    <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>TIME</b></td>
                    <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>STATUS</b></td>
                <?php
                if (mysql_num_rows($log_list_SQL) >= 1) {
                    ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
                    while($log_list_array = mysql_fetch_array($log_list_SQL)){
                        $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
                        <tr class="<?=$row_color?" align="left"
valign="top">
                            <td width="25"
align="left">&nbsp;<?=$count?></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;<?=$log_list_array[0]?></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;<?<=ucwords($log_list_array[1])?></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;<?=$log_list_array[2]?></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;<?=$log_list_array[3]?></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;<?=$log_list_array[4]?></td>
                        </tr>
                        <?php $count++;
                    }
                } else {?>
                <tr><td colspan="6" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
                <?php }
                ?>
            </table></div></td></tr>
        <tr><td ><?<=paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$log_list_query)
?></td></tr>
    </table>
</form>

</-----CONTENT-END----->
-//>

        </td>
        <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table>
</td>
    <td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"
width="165"><?<=sub_menu($page_id_right, $category_page)?></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer()?>
    
```

24. agreement.php

```

<?php
require_once('./inc/config.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/functions.inc.php');
require_once('./inc/libbutton.inc.php');
chkSession();
    
```

```
$rowsPerPage = 5;
$pageNum = 1;

if(isset($_GET['page'])) {$pageNum = $_GET['page'];}

$offset = ($pageNum - 1) * $rowsPerPage;

$agree_list_query = "SELECT agreement.id, file.code, branch.name AS bname,
departments.name AS dept, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name) AS fullname,
agreement.status, CONCAT(manager.name, ' ', manager.given_name) AS mname,
agreement.mgr_status, agreement.date, agreement.ackdate ";
$agree_list_query .= "FROM agreement ";
$agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = agreement.user_id_fk) ";
$agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = agreement.file_id_fk) ";
$agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id = user.branch_id_fk)
";
$agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id = user.mgr_id_fk)
";
$agree_list_query .= "ORDER BY fullname ASC";
$agree_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";

$adm_join_list_limit_query = $agree_list_query." ".$agree_limit_query;

$agree_list_SQL = @mysql_query($adm_join_list_limit_query);

$mgr_agree_list_query = "SELECT agreement.id, file.code, branch.name AS bname,
departments.name AS dept, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name) AS fullname,
agreement.status, CONCAT(manager.name, ' ', manager.given_name) AS mname,
agreement.mgr_status, agreement.date, agreement.ackdate ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "FROM agreement ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = agreement.user_id_fk) ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = agreement.file_id_fk) ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id =
user.branch_id_fk) ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS manager ON (manager.id =
user.mgr_id_fk) ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "WHERE branch.branch_id = '$_SESSION['bid']. ' AND
departments.id = '$_SESSION['did']. ' AND user.level_id_fk = '4' ";
$mgr_agree_list_query .= "ORDER BY fullname ASC";
$mgr_agree_list_limit_query = "LIMIT $offset, $rowsPerPage";

$mgr_join_list_limit_query = $mgr_agree_list_query."
".$mgr_agree_list_limit_query;

$mgr_agree_list_SQL = mysql_query($mgr_join_list_limit_query) or die('Invalid
Query : ' . mysql_error());

$agree_data_query = "SELECT agreement.id, CONCAT(user.name, ' ', user.given_name)
AS fullname, departments.name, branch.name, agreement.status, ";
$agree_data_query .= "CONCAT(mgr.name, ' ', mgr.given_name) AS mgr_name,
agreement.mgr_status, agreement.date, agreement.ackdate, ";
$agree_data_query .= "file.code, CONCAT(chk.name, ' ', chk.given_name) AS chkname,
CONCAT(val.name, ' ', val.given_name) AS valname, file.date, file.notes ";
$agree_data_query .= "FROM agreement LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id =
agreement.user_id_fk) ";
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS mgr ON (mgr.id = agreement.manager_id)
";
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN file ON (file.id = agreement.file_id_fk) ";
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS chk ON (chk.id = file.checked) ";
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN user AS val ON (val.id = file.validated) ";
```

```
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN departments ON (departments.id =
user.dept_id_fk) ";
$agree_data_query .= "LEFT JOIN branch ON (branch.branch_id = user.branch_id_fk)
";
$agree_data_query .= "WHERE user.id = '". $_SESSION['uid'] . "'";

$agree_data_SQL = mysql_query($agree_data_query);

$agree_data_array = mysql_fetch_array($agree_data_SQL);

$q_agree = "SELECT agreement.status, agreement.mgr_status ";
$q_agree .= "FROM agreement LEFT JOIN user ON (user.id = agreement.user_id_fk)
WHERE user.id = '". $_SESSION['uid'] . "' ";
$agree = @mysql_query($q_agree);
$showAgree = mysql_fetch_array($agree);

$file_agreement = "./txt/agreement.txt";
$dispAgree = implode("", file($file_agreement));

$this_page = $_SERVER['PHP_SELF'] . "?page=" . $pageNum;

if(isset($_POST['ack_manager'])){
    $mgr_agree_ack_id = $_POST['mgr_agree_ack_id'];
    foreach($mgr_agree_ack_id as $ack_id_value) {
        $sql = "UPDATE agreement SET manager_id = '". $_SESSION['uid'] . "',
mgr_status = '1', ackdate = '". date('Y-m-d') . "' WHERE id = '$ack_id_value.'";
        mysql_query($sql);
    }
    header("location:$this_page");
}

function super_agree(){
    $code_file = "XXXX/ITAF/" . $_SESSION['bid'] . "/" . date('my');
    $super_agreement_file_query = "INSERT INTO file VALUES
(NULL, '$code_file', '". date('Y-m-d') . "', '1', '1', '1', '1')";
    mysql_query($super_agreement_file_query);

    $file_id_fk = mysql_insert_id();
    $super_agree_query = "INSERT INTO agreement VALUES
(NULL, '$file_id_fk', '". $_SESSION['uid'] . "', '1', '1', '1', '". date('Y-m-
d') . "', '1')";
    mysql_query($super_agree_query);
}

if(isset($_POST['adm_agree'])){
    super_agree();
    header("location:$this_page");
}

if(isset($_POST['mgr_agree'])){
    super_agree();
    header("location:$this_page");
}

if(isset($_POST['svAgree'])){
    $updAgreeTxt = trim($_POST['ctAgree']);

    if (!file_exists($file_agreement)) {
        fopen($file_agreement, 'w+');
    }
    if (is_writable($file_agreement)){
        if (!$handle = fopen($file_agreement, 'w')) {??
            <div style="yellowbox" align="center">Can't open file
<b><?=$file_agreement?></b></div>

```



```

Admin)&nbsp;";"&nbsp;";<b>Yes, I agree with the IT policies (For Admin
Only)</b>&nbsp;";?>
        </td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td>
        <textarea cols="80" rows="10" name="ctAgree"
wrap="virtual">
                <?=trim($dispAgree)?>
        </textarea></td></tr>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td><input type="submit" name="svAgree" class="button"
value="UPDATE AGREEMENT TEXT"></td></tr>
</table>
</td></tr>
<tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>
<tr><td height="1" bgcolor="#ccccff"></td></tr>
<tr><td >&nbsp;</td></tr>

        <tr><td><?=paging_dyn($rowsPerPage,$pageNum,$offset,$agree_list_query)?><
/td></tr>
        <tr><td >
                <div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px;
margin-top: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'\>
                <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1" width="100%">
                <tr class="listview" align="left" valign="middle">
                        <td width="25">&nbsp;<b>NO.</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>FILE NO.</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>BRANCH</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>DEPARTMENT</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>NAME</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>AGREE</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>MANAGER</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>ACKNOWLEDGE</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>DATE</b></td>
                        <td width="*">&nbsp;<b>ACK. DATE</b></td>
                </tr>
<?php
        if (mysql_num_rows($agree_list_SQL ) >= 1) {
                ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
                while($agree_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($agree_list_SQL)){
                        $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
                <tr class="<?=$row_color?>" align="left"
valign="top">
                        <td>&nbsp;<?=$count?>.</td>

                        <td>&nbsp;<?=( $agree_list_array[1])?$agree_list_array[1]:"&nbsp;<?> -
";?></td>

                        <td>&nbsp;<?=( $agree_list_array[2])?ucwords($agree_list_array[2]):"&nbsp;<?> -
";?></td>

                        <td>&nbsp;<?=( $agree_list_array[3])?ucwords($agree_list_array[3]):"&nbsp;<?> -
";?></td>

                        <td>&nbsp;<?=( $agree_list_array[4])?ucwords($agree_list_array[4]):"&nbsp;<?> -
";?></td>

                                <td>
<?php                                if($agree_list_array[5] == 1)
{?>&nbsp;<?>YES<?>}else{?>&nbsp;<?>PENDING<?>}?></td>

                        <td><?=( $agree_list_array[6])?ucwords($agree_list_array[6]):"&nbsp;<?> -
";?></td>

                                <td>
<?php                                if($agree_list_array[7] == 1)
{?>&nbsp;<?>YES<?>}else{?>&nbsp;<?>PENDING<?>}?></td>

```



```

        <td width="*">&nbsp;  <b>ACKNOWLEDGE</b></td>
        <td width="*">&nbsp;  <b>DATE</b></td>
        <td width="*">&nbsp;  <b>ACK. DATE</b></td>
        </tr>
<?php
    if (mysql_num_rows($mgr_agree_list_SQL) >= 1) {
        ($pageNum == 1)? $count = 1: $count = $offset;
        while($mgr_agree_list_array =
mysql_fetch_array($mgr_agree_list_SQL)){
            $row_color = ($count % 2)?"odd":"even"; ?>
            <tr class="<?=$row_color?" align="left" valign="top">
                <td>&nbsp;  <input type="checkbox"
name="mgr_agree_ack_id[]" value="<?=$mgr_agree_list_array[0]?"></td>
                <td>&nbsp;  <?=$count?>.</td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[1] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[1]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[2] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[2]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[3] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[3]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[4] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[4]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

                <td><?php
                    if($mgr_agree_list_array[5] == 1)
{?>&nbsp;  <?>YES<?>else{?>&nbsp;  <?>PENDING<?>?></td>

                <td><?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[6])?></td>
                <td><?php
                    if($mgr_agree_list_array[7] == 1)
{?>&nbsp;  <?>YES<?>else{?>&nbsp;  <?>PENDING<?>?></td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[8] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[8]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

                <td>&nbsp;  <?=( $mgr_agree_list_array[9] )?ucwords($mgr_agree_list_array[9]
):"&nbsp;  <?=-";?></td>

            </tr>
            <?php $count++;
            }
        } else {?>
            <tr><td colspan="11" align="center"
bgcolor="#e5e5e5"><br />No Data Entries<br /><br /></td></tr>
            <? } ?>

        </table></div>
    </td></tr>

    <tr><td><?=$paging_dyn($rowsPerPage, $pageNum, $offset, $mgr_agree_list_query
)?></td></tr>
    <tr><td >&nbsp;  </td></tr>

<?php } ?>
<!--MGR-END-->
</>
<!--USR-START-->
--</>
<?php if($_SESSION['level'] == 4 || $_SESSION['level'] == 2) { ?>
<tr><td>
<table border="0" width="500">
    <tr><td><div style='border: 1px solid #CECECE; padding: 2px; margin-top:
5px; margin-bottom: 5px;'>
        <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
    
```



```

        </table>
<?php } ?>
<!-------FOR APPROVER -----//>
<!-------FOR COORDINATOR -----//>
<?php
    if($_SESSION['level'] == 4){ ?>
        <table border="0" width="100%" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
            <tr align="center">
                <td>
<?=( $showAgree[0] == "1")?"<b>YES, I AGREE</b>": "&nbsp;"; ?>
                <hr></td>
                <td width="100">&nbsp;</td>
                <td>
<?=( $showAgree[1] == "1")?"<b>I ACKNOWLEDGED</b>": "&nbsp;"; ?>
                <hr></td></tr>
            <tr><td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>Manager's Name>Nama Manajer:</td></tr>
            <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>

            <tr><td><b><?=( $agree_data_array[1])?ucwords($agree_data_array[1]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></b></td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>

                <td><b><?=( $agree_data_array[5])?ucwords($agree_data_array[5]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></b></td></tr>
            <tr><td colspan="3">&nbsp;</td></tr>
            <tr><td>Date/Tgl.:
<b><?=( $agree_data_array[7])?ucwords($agree_data_array[7]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></b></td>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>
                <td>Date/Tgl.: <b><?=( $agree_data_array[8] != "0000-
00-00")?ucwords($agree_data_array[8]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></b></td></tr>
        </table>
<?php } ?>
<!-------FOR COORDINATOR -----//>
        </td></tr>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
<?=( !$showAgree[0])?agree_button(): "" ;?>
        <tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
            <tr><td>
                <table border="0" cellpadding="1" cellspacing="1">
                    <tr><td align="left"><b>FILE NO</b></td>
                        <td align="left">:</td>

                    <td><?=( $agree_data_array[9])?ucwords($agree_data_array[9]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></td>
                        <td align="left" rowspan="4">&nbsp;</td>
                        <td rowspan="4" align="left"
valign="top"><b>NOTES</b>:<br/>

                    <td><?=( $agree_data_array[13])?nl2br($agree_data_array[13]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></td></tr>
                    <tr><td align="left"><b>CHECKED</b></td>
                        <td align="left">:</td>

                    <td><?=( $agree_data_array[10])?ucwords($agree_data_array[10]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></td></tr>
                    <tr><td align="left"><b>VALIDATED</b></td>
                        <td align="left">:</td>

                    <td><?=( $agree_data_array[11])?ucwords($agree_data_array[11]): "&nbsp; -
; ;?></td></tr>
                    <tr><td align="left"><b>DATE</b></td>
                        <td align="left">:</td>

```

```
                <td><b><?=( $agree_data_array[12])?ucwords($agree_data_array[12]):"&nbsp;
-";?></b></td></tr>
                </table></fieldset></td></tr>
</table>
</td></tr>
<?php } ?>
</-----USR-END----->
//>
<tr><td>&nbsp;</td></tr>
</table>
</form>
</-----CONTENT-END----->
-//>

                </td>
                <td width="3">&nbsp;</td>
                </tr>
            </tbody>
        </table>
</td>
<td align="left" bgcolor="#ccccff" valign="top"></td>
</tr>
<?php source_footer();?>
```

25. logout.php

```
<?php
require('./inc/config.inc.php');
session_start();
if (isset($_SESSION['auth_erequest'])){
    $old_user = $_SESSION['auth_erequest'];
    $outTime = date('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    $query = "INSERT INTO log_history VALUES
(NULL, '$_SESSION[uid]', '$_SERVER[REMOTE_ADDR]', '$_SESSION[auth_erequest]', 'LOGO
UT)";
    mysql_query($query) or die('Invalid Query ' . mysql_error());
    session_unset();
    session_destroy();
    if (!empty($old_user)) {
        Header ('Location:./index.php');
    }
    else{
        echo "<p>You cannot logout.</p>";
    }

    echo "</body>\n";
    echo "</html>";

}
else {
    Header ('Location:./login.php');
}
?>
```

CURRICULUM VITAE

MUHAMMAD ARYO NURDIAN PRATAMA

Personal Info

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Birth Place Jakarta
Birth Date August 3rd 1986
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 Bekasi - 17145
Telephone +62-21-884-1343
Mobile +62-815-91-25052
E-mail aryo_np@yahoo.com
 pratama.muhammad@vdi.de

Education

1992 - 1998 Tunas Jakasampurna Elementary School
1998 - 2001 Tunas Jakasampurna Junior High School
2001 - 2003 Labschool Senior High School (2 Years Acceleration Program)
2003 - ... Swiss German University – Information Technology Faculty

Working Experience

October 2004 – February 2005 **Swiss German University – Asia**
 Information Technology Lab
 Status : Internship student
 Task : Lab Administrator
 Using : MS Windows (XP, Server 2003), RHEL 4 AS,
 Symantec Ghost 8, Oracle 10g, Compiere, Oscar,
 VMWare

September 2005 – December 2005 **Swiss German University – Asia**
 Information Technology fac.
 Status : Student

	<p>Task : System Analyst & System Design for O.F.S.E. Project Using : PHP, CSS, HTML, JS, Macromedia Dreamweaver 8, MS Project 2003, MS Visio 2003</p>
December 2005 – January 2005	<p>Swiss German University – Asia Information Technology div. Status : Freelance Task : Designing IT Lab infrastructure. Using : RHEL 4 AS, MS Windows Server 2003</p>
February 2006 – July 2006	<p>AEG Power Supply System GmbH Datenverarbeitung Status : Internship student Task : Intranet Administrator, Programming Helpdesk Using : MS Exchange Server 2003, TYPO3 v4, PHP, CSS, HTML, XML, JS, MS Windows (XP, Server 2003) , SuSE 10.0, Macromedia Dreamweaver 8</p>
August 2006 – January 2007	<p>Verein Deutscher Ingenieur e.V. Representative for Indonesia</p>
January 2007 - ...	<p>VDI FK-Indonesien Representative for Indonesia</p>
February 2007 – August 2007	<p>PT. Schenker Petrolog Utama Information Technology div. Status : Internship student Task : System Architect for S.T.O.R.I.X. Project Using : Eclipse, RHEL 4 AS, OpenSuSE 10.2, PHP, XML, CSS, HTML, JS, MS Project 2007, MS Visio 2007, MS Office 2007, OTRS, Macromedia Dreamweaver 8</p>

Training and Workshop

August – November 2004 Siemens Vocational Training Center.

Mechanical and Electrical Training.

October 2005

Swiss German Univ. – Bajau.

Introduction About Redhat Enterprise Linux.

April 2006

AEG Power Supply System GmbH, Belecke.

TYPO3 Workshop.

Language Skill

Indonesia	Advanced
English	Advanced
German	Fair (Grundstufe I)

Computer Skill

Programming Language

C, C++, Java, VB, PHP, CSS, HTML, XML, JS

Database

MySQL, Oracle 10g, MS SQL Server 2000

Project Management Tools

MS Project 2007, Open Workbench

Graphic Application

Adobe Photoshop CS 2

Multimedia Applications

Macromedia Flash, Swish Max

Office Application

MS Office 2007, Open Office 2.0, Adobe Acrobat Professional 7, MS Visio 2007

Operating System

Microsoft Windows (ME, XP, Server 2003, Vista), Slackware 11, OpenSuSE 10.2, Ubuntu 5.10, Ubuntu 7.04, RHEL 4 AS, Solaris 10

Seminar and Course

March 2002	Internet Usage in Labschool High School with Mr. Ono W. Purbo
March 2002	Cisco system & HAI Magazine Internet training
August 2003	Brain Power in Swiss German University with Mr. Wolfram Stanek
October 2004	Communication Skill in Swiss German University
January 2005	XML Web-based programming in Swiss German University
August 2005	IBH Summerschool on University of Constance
May 2007	Business Intelligence and Data Mining
May 2007	Introduction to Human Language Technology
May 2007	Web Services Technologies
May 2007	Introduction to Free/Open Source Technology
May 2007	Introduction of HDV Technology

Organizational Experience

1999 - 2001	Tunas Jakasampurna Junior High School Boyscoutt Head of Tunas Jakasampurna Junior High School Boyscoutt
2002 - 2003	Merpati Putih (Indonesia Traditional Martial Arts) Vice Chief in Labschool Indonesian traditional Martial-arts organisation Merpati Putih.
2002 - 2003	SMU Labschool Islamic Youth Organization Head of Documentation Department
2003 - 2004	SGU Student Organization Member of Information Technology SGU Student Council House of Representatives
2005 - 2006	SGU Student Organization Chief of Information Technology SGU Student Council House of Representatives

Interest

Management Information System, Technology, Books, Art & Architecture, Photography, Travelling, Martial Arts, Outdoor Activities.

Reference

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